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EFFECT OF ZEOLITE ADDITIVE ON THE LEVEL OF TOXIC METALS IN THE BODY OF YOUNG CATTLE

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Abstract. *This article presents experimental data on the concentrations of toxic metals (lead, nickel, chromium, and cadmium) in the hair and hoof horn of young cattle fed with a zeolite (clinoptilolite) additive between the ages of 4 to 9 and 18 to 20 months. The possibility of correcting mineral metabolism has been established.*

Keywords: *young cattle, toxic metals, zeolite (clinoptilolite) additive.*

Introduction

The issue of environmental contamination by various ecotoxicants has been addressed by numerous researchers and is addressed using various methods, the most significant of which is sorption. Both synthetic and natural materials are employed as sorbents, with natural zeolites occupying a prominent position due to their high ion-exchange capacity attributable to their unique structure. The primary structure of any zeolite is an almost regular tetrahedron, with a silicon or aluminum ion at its center and oxygen ions at its vertices. These tetrahedra are connected by oxygen bridges, forming a continuous secondary structure (pores) through which neutral molecules or charged ions can pass via diffusion or ion exchange. Adsorption properties depend on the crystal arrangement within the mineral and the pore sizes, which range from 0.3 to 0.8 nm or more.

More than 40 types of zeolites are known. It has been established that clinoptilolite exhibits the highest adsorption capacity, possessing a strictly calibrated pore size of 3.5 nm, enabling it to absorb small molecules such as H₂, Cl₂, H₂O, CO₂, NH₃, Cl₂, HCl, and others. Thus, natural zeolite sorbs low-molecular-weight toxins (ammonia, hydrogen sulfide, methane) from the gastrointestinal tract, as well as ions of heavy metals and their salts, and radionuclides. It does not interfere with the absorption of nutrients and vitamins,

is neither absorbed nor deposited in the gastrointestinal tract, and is quantitatively excreted within 24 hours.

Experimental studies have demonstrated the effectiveness of zeolites as sorbents of toxins [1], radioactive isotopes [2, 3], and heavy metals [4, 5]; their use is recommended for preventing metabolic disorders and enhancing productivity and product quality [6–9]. Research in this area will always remain relevant, as the results depend on multiple factors influencing metabolism (environment, feed, physiological condition, etc.).

The aim of the study was to investigate the effect of a zeolite additive on the concentrations of the most toxic metals (chromium, nickel, lead, and cadmium) in the hair and hoof horn of young cattle kept in a technogenic zone.

Materials and methods of the study

Two scientific and practical trials were conducted. The research material consisted of a clinoptilolite-type zeolite additive from the Khotynets deposit in the Oryol region (Russian Federation).

In the first trial, the subjects were crossbred calves (Aberdeen Angus × Black-and-White breeds) aged 4 months with an average live weight of 84.61 ± 1.1 kg, divided into two groups according to the analogue principle. Calves in group 1 were considered the control group and received the main diet, balanced in nutritional value, composed of home-produced feeds. It should be noted that a large industrial facility was located near the farm. The diet averaged 3.3 feed units (FU), 3.35 kg of dry matter, 277 g of digestible protein, 114.4 g of crude fat, and 726 g of crude fiber throughout the experiment. Calves in the experimental group received a 3% clinoptilolite additive based on the dry matter content of their feed. The duration of the experiment was 150 days.

In the second experiment, two groups of crossbred young cattle aged 18 months were formed. Group 1 (control) received a basic balanced diet containing 10 MJ of metabolizable energy and 97 g of digestible protein per 1 kg of dry matter. The experimental group received a 3% zeolite additive, based on dry matter, along with the steamed feed mixture. The duration of the experiment was 60 days. The animals were kept under confined housing conditions.

During the study, the health status of the animals was monitored, and monthly weighing was performed to calculate live weight gains. The concentration of toxic metals was determined by spectrophotometry in hair (tail tip) and in the hoof horn. Statistical analysis of experimental data was conducted using the Microsoft Excel IBM PC/XP software package. The Student's t-test was applied to assess the significance of differences between the control and experimental groups. Values of $P < 0.05$ were considered statistically significant.

Research Results. During vital activity, mineral elements — both biogenic and highly toxic, including lead, cadmium, nickel, and chromium — are selectively

accumulated in the organs and tissues of animals. Under identical housing and feeding conditions on the same farm, the levels of toxic metals were determined in young cattle aged 9 and 20 months. The research results are presented in

Table 1. Concentrations of toxic metals in the hoof horn and hair of young cattle at different age periods, m(mk)mol/kg (n=3)

Tissue	Mineral element	Age	
		9 months	20 months
Hoof horn	Nickel, mmol/kg	<0,001	0,020±0,002*
	Chromium, mmol/kg	0,033± 0,002	0,017±0,001*
	Lead, µmol/kg	0,497±0,097	3,620±0,418*
	Cadmium, µmol/kg	0,258±0,00	0,154±0,036*
Hair	Nickel, mmol/kg	<0,001	0,012±0,001*
	Chromium, mmol/kg	0,031 ± 0,007	0,002±0,000*
	Lead, µmol/kg	0,483± 0,145	0,933±0,098*
	Cadmium, µmol/kg	0,267± 0,002	0,178±0,026*

*) P < 0.05 relative to 9 months of age

Analysis of the experimental data from the control groups indicates that in young cattle at 20 months of age, the concentration of lead statistically significantly increases by 7.3 and 1.9 times in the hoof horn and hair, respectively (P<0.05), and nickel increases by 1.5 and 2.3 times compared to the corresponding values in animals aged 9 months. From 9 to 20 months of age, conversely, the chromium content decreases by 92.04% (P<0.05) and cadmium by 33.33% (P<0.05) in the hair, and by 47.06% (P<0.05) and 41.38% (P<0.05) in the hoof horn, respectively.

According to the research methodology, for the purpose of correcting toxic metal levels, calves aged 4 to 9 months and young cattle aged 18 to 20 months in the experimental groups were daily fed a clinoptilolite-containing supplement amounting to 3% of the dry matter of the feed mixture, in addition to the main balanced diet. Concentrations of the most toxic metals (lead, nickel, chromium, and cadmium) were determined in hair samples taken from the tail tip and hoof horn. The research results are presented in

Table 2. Effect of the zeolite additive on the concentration of toxic metals in the hair and hoof horn of young cattle

Indicators	Group			
	Control (Base ration)	Experimental (Base ration + 3 % KH)	Control (Base ration)	Experimental (Base ration + 3 % KH)
	9 months		20 months	
Hair				
Nickel, mmol/kg	<0,001	<0,001	0,012 ± 0,001	0,008 ± 0,000*
Chromium, mmol/kg	0,031 ± 0,007	0,060 ± 0,009*	0,002 ± 0,000	0,004 ± 0,001
Lead, µmol/kg	0,483± 0,145	1,206 ± 0,145*	0,933 ± 0,098	0,386 ± 0,028*
Cadmium, µmol/kg	0,267± 0,002	0,294 ± 0,00	0,178 ± 0,026	0,089 ± 0,026*
Hoof horn				
Nickel, mmol/kg	<0,001	0,033 ± 0,011	0,020 ± 0,002	0,026 ± 0,001*
Chromium, mmol/kg	0,033± 0,002	0,025 ± 0,010	0,017 ± 0,001	0,029 ± 0,000*
Lead, µmol/kg	0,497±0,097	1,689 ± 0,917	3,620 ± 0,418	1,802 ± 0,098*
Cadmium, µmol/kg	0,258±0,00	0,374 ± 0,356	0,154 ± 0,036	0,537 ± 0,036*

*) $P < 0.05$ relative to the control group

Base ration (BR);

KH — zeolite additive of Khotynets origin from the Oryol region, Russian Federation

The results obtained indicate that feeding young cattle from four to nine months of age with a 3% clinoptilolite additive based on dry matter led to an increase in chromium levels in the hair by 91.86% ($P < 0.05$), lead by 150% ($P < 0.05$), and cadmium by 10% compared to the control group. In the hoof horn of 9-month-old young cattle from the experimental group compared to the control, there was a tendency for chromium levels to decrease by 23.5%; however, the concentrations of other studied heavy metals significantly increased: nickel by 3.9 times ($P < 0.05$), lead by 3.4 times ($P < 0.05$), and cadmium by 1.4 times.

It was established that daily supplementation of fattening young cattle from 18 to 20 months of age with 3% Hotynets zeolite resulted in a significant change in the concentration of mineral elements. In the hair of the experimental animals, the concentrations of nickel decreased by 39.73% ($P < 0.05$), lead by 57.9% ($P < 0.05$), and cadmium by 50% ($P < 0.05$), respectively, while chromium increased by 69.2% ($P < 0.05$) compared to the control group. In the hoof horn of young cattle following supplementation with a zeolite additive, only the lead content decreased — by 50.22% ($P < 0.05$)—while

nickel, chromium, and cadmium increased by 30.06% ($P<0.05$), 64.58% ($P<0.05$), and 248.1% ($P<0.05$), respectively, compared to the control.

Throughout the study, animal productivity was assessed monthly, and it was found that daily administration of the zeolite additive over 150 days resulted in a 3% reduction in live weight gain compared to the control group. However, during the first month of additive use, the live weight gain in the experimental group under the indirect influence of the zeolite additive was 12.5% higher than in the control group ($P<0.05$); in the following three months, it declined and only in the fifth month of feeding did it slightly exceed that of the control group. Therefore, in the second experiment, the animals were fed the additive for only 62 days, which resulted in a live weight gain 13.3% greater than that of the control group.

Conclusion

Mineral elements play a vital role in metabolism, being involved in all metabolic processes; therefore, the *in vivo* assessment of the mineral status of animals is of high relevance. Experimental evidence demonstrates that supplementing the diet of young cattle with a zeolite (clinoptilolite) additive possessing sorption properties during the rearing period (from 4 to 9 months of age) and fattening phase (from 18 to 20 months) results in a significant alteration of mineral element levels in the animals' bodies. A pattern has been identified in the accumulation levels of lead, nickel, chromium, and cadmium in the hair and hoof horn at different age periods, suggesting the possibility of *in vivo* assessment of toxic metal content in the bodies of animals and their correction with zeolites to produce environmentally clean products.

The productivity data obtained indicate that prolonged feeding of the zeolite additive to young cattle is ineffective. However, feeding the additive for 1–2 months leads to an increase in average daily live weight gain, which is likely associated with the normalization of rumen microbiota due to the ion-exchange properties of the zeolite additive.

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PRODUCTION OF VEGETABLE FUEL IN CROP ROTATIONS IN THE LUHANSK REGION, TAKING INTO ACCOUNT BIOCLIMATIC RESOURCES

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Abstract. *Research was carried out on the development of crop rotations for agricultural crops under Donbas conditions with the aim of maximizing the production of vegetable oils and ethyl alcohol (biofuel). Field crop rotations involving the cultivation of oilseed crops have been developed. Under the current conditions of agricultural production and climate warming, the requirements for crop rotations, as well as the productivity and yield of agricultural crops, have changed significantly. Changes in climatic conditions necessitate the adaptation of the structure of crop rotations. Recommendations have been developed for the rational use of bioclimatic resources of agro-landscapes in the Donbas region when optimizing field crop rotation schemes that ensure the production of vegetable-based fuel.*

Keywords: *crop rotation, agrolandscape, bioclimatic resources, biofuel.*

In modern petrochemistry, amid the growing deficit of energy carriers and the significant increase in demand for all types of fuel feedstock, conserving energy resources and raw materials remains an extremely urgent issue. Biodiesel is an alternative fuel used in diesel engines, produced from renewable raw materials such as vegetable oils [7, 8].

The demand for renewable energy sources, including vegetable oils (VO), has not yet reached its peak. However, by 2030, their share of global renewable energy sources is expected to reach 10% of petroleum fuel. In the energy bio-variant, two factors are particularly significant. Firstly, vegetable fuel constitutes renewable

resources; secondly, the accumulation of solar energy by plants during photosynthesis occurs synchronously with their absorption of CO₂ released during the combustion of plant biomass. Thus, the cycle is balanced by nature itself. Today, the most extensive example of biofuel utilization is offered by Brazil, where ethyl alcohol produced through fermentation of sugarcane is used as fuel. In this way, a country almost devoid of oil and gas fields addresses its fuel problems [1, 5].

As early as 2002, the possibility of producing biofuel based on rapeseed and sunflower oil, which can be used for export, was proposed. In this regard, an important task is the appropriate selection of additional crops for the production of vegetable-based fuel. To date, this issue has not received adequate attention. The development of crop rotations that provide for fuel production will address the important practical challenge of achieving partial, and eventually full, self-sufficiency of agriculture in energy carriers. Simultaneously, it also addresses the scientific challenge of developing new crop rotations.

Amid the increasing impact of climate change on economic development, adaptation to the expected changes has become one of the priority tasks of the state socio-economic policy in the Russian Federation [2]. Under the current conditions of agricultural production and climate warming, the requirements for crop rotations, as well as the productivity and yield of agricultural crops, have significantly changed. Changes in climatic conditions necessitate the adaptation of the structure of crop rotations. There are substantial reserves for optimizing land allocation and enhancing the structure of sown areas in the Luhansk region.

In the Donbas regions, there is a need to study the adaptation of crop cultivation technologies and the structure of crop rotations with regard to crop maturity groups under changing climatic conditions. Therefore, the aim of our research is to develop recommendations for the rational use of the bioclimatic resources of the agrolandscape across various districts of the Luhansk region to optimize field crop rotation schemes that ensure the production of plant-based fuels. The principle of such crop rotations is based on selecting the sequence of crop sowing while ensuring the restoration of soil fertility and enabling the maximum yield of 'fuel'. To achieve this, it is necessary to address several tasks: to calculate the bioclimatic resources of the territory and assess the degree of their utilization by crops from field crop rotations of various maturity groups; to recommend crops for inclusion in the crop rotation structure and to develop schemes of field crop rotations specifying the crop maturity groups appropriate for the conditions of the Luhansk region.

The assessment of the bioclimatic resources of the territory was conducted using the method of Shashko D.I., Mischenko Z.A., and Popytchenko L.M. [3, 4]. Materials from our previous studies on the efficiency of utilizing the bioclimatic potential of the studied territory by crops of various maturity groups were included; calculations were carried out on the portion of the climate potential used by

agricultural crops of early, medium, and late maturity varieties and hybrids; The coefficient of efficiency of climate potential utilization by crops was calculated; Literature data on the raw material base for biodiesel production were used.

Currently, research is being conducted worldwide on the use of plant-based fuels in internal combustion engines for both agricultural needs and broader applications [5, 6]. Such fuels can be regarded as transformed solar energy intended for consumption. These fuels include alcohols derived from plants such as sorghum, maize, sugarcane, and other crops.

Currently, more than a quarter of a million plants are registered worldwide, from the seeds of which oil can be obtained [1].

Based on the analysis of 90 of the most well-known plant oil sources and considering the soil and climatic conditions of the region, we selected fifteen oilseed crops, as well as crops from which alcohol can be produced (sorghum, sugar beet, Jerusalem artichoke). All these crops are suitable for cultivation in field crop rotations.

In Table 1, they are presented in descending order of the fuel equivalent, calculated in terms of diesel fuel with a combustion heat of 42,290 kJ/kg. The average combustion heat of oils is assumed to be 37,000 kJ/kg.

Table 1 – Raw material base for biodiesel production

Crops	Return period to the previous location, years	Average yield (centners/ha)	Oil content (%)	Maximum oil yield (centners/ha)	Fuel equivalent recalculated to diesel fuel (l/ha)
Sunflower	5-7	15	50-55	8,25	870
Peanut	2-3	10	50-66	6,6	696
Winter rapeseed	3-4	12	40-50	6,0	632
Castor bean	4-5	10	50-52	5,2	548
Spring camelina	2-3	12	40-42	5,04	531
Oilseed poppy	3-4	10	46-50	5,0	527
Safflower	2-3	10	25-27	3,7	390
Mustard	2-3	9	35-40	3,6	379
Soybean	0-1	14	18-25	3,5	369
Hemp	3-4	10	30-50	3,5	369
Spring rapeseed	2-3	8	33-40	3,2	337
Oil flax	5-7	7	35-40	3,15	332
Maize	Monoculture	30	6,5-7	2,1	315
Charlock	3-4	8	30-32	2,6	274

Crops	Return period to the previous location, years	Average yield (centners/ha)	Oil content (%)	Maximum oil yield (centners/ha)	Fuel equivalent recalculated to diesel fuel (l/ha)
Sorghum	Monoculture	30	Ethyl Alcohol	9,0	900
Chicory	Monoculture	300	ethyl alcohol	300	3000
Sugar beet	3-4	300	4-8	540	2700
Jerusalem artichoke	Monoculture	300	2-5	750	3600

The productivity of these crops sown in the proposed crop rotation can be increased by sowing seeds using precision seeders, employing high-performance machinery, a scientifically substantiated fertilization system, the use of both clean and occupied fallow land, crop placement strictly according to return periods considering predecessors and allelopathic effects, moisture accumulation and conservation, and effective control of weeds, diseases, and pests.

When cultivating oilseed crops, it is essential to consider soil fertility and weed infestation of the crops. Such crops as winter rapeseed, sesame, and others respond well to nutrient-rich soils. They provide high yields on fertilized soils and on fallow land.

Based on long-term scientific data and the experience of farms in the Luhansk region, and taking into account the soil and climatic conditions of the region, we have developed crop rotations with the cultivation of oilseed crops, presented in Table 2, as well as using information from literary sources.

Table 2 – Crop rotations ensuring an increase in vegetable oil yield

Crop rotation sequence	Yield (centners/ha)	Oil content (%)	Oil yield (centner/ha)	Fuel equivalent recalculated to diesel fuel (l/ha)
Crop rotation No. 1				
Fallow	-	-	-	-
Mustard	12	40	4,8	480
Sunflower	15	51	7,7	806
Sorghum	30	Ethyl alcohol	9,0	900
Sugar beet	30	Ethyl alcohol	2,7	2700
Soybean	14	22	3,1	327
Winter rapeseed	12	45	5,4	569
Average oil yield per hectare of crop rotation area and its corresponding fuel equivalent			5,5	568
Crop rotation No. 2				
Fallow	-	-	-	-

Crop rotation sequence	Yield (centners/ha)	Oil content (%)	Oil yield (centner/ha)	Fuel equivalent recalculated to diesel fuel (l/ha)
Oilseed poppy	10	46	5,0	527
Spring rapeseed	12	45	5,4	569
Sorghum	30	Ethyl alcohol	9,0	900
Soybean	14	22	3,1	327
Oil flax	7	40	3,2	332
Sunflower	15	50	7,7	806
Average oil yield per hectare of crop rotation area and its corresponding fuel equivalent			4,8	494

On soils with medium fertility, using the residual effects of fertilizers, it is possible to cultivate Jerusalem artichoke, peanut, spring rape, safflower, sorghum, and chicory. On depleted soils, the cultivation of mustard and false flax is allowed.

In the crop rotation currently common for farms in the Luhansk region (fallow, winter crops, maize for grain, barley + sainfoin, sainfoin fallow, winter crops, sunflower), the oil yield per hectare of crop rotation area amounts to 1.94 centners per hectare, which, converted to fuel equivalent (diesel fuel), equals 205 liters per hectare.

Table 3 below presents the calculated indicators of the efficiency of bioclimatic resource utilization in the agrolandscape for the recommended maturity groups of crop rotations by districts within the studied territory.

Table 3 – Field crop rotation crops recommended for cultivation in various areas of the Luhansk region

Crop	Maturity group	Northern regions	Central regions	Southern regions
		Percentage of bioclimatic potential utilization by the crop, %		
Sunflower	Mid-early	71	66	69
	Mid-late	79	73	76
Grain maize	Mid-early	82	-	79
	Mid-late	-	82	-
Sorghum	Early maturing	82	-	79
	Mid-early	-	79	-
Millet	Late maturing	75	69	72
Spring barley	Late maturing	69	63	66
Winter barley	Late maturing	72	66	69
Winter wheat	Late-maturing	68	63	66
Millet	Late-maturing	75	69	72
Buckwheat	Late-maturing	73	65	74

Indicators of the efficiency of using bioclimatic resources of the agrolandscape for the recommended crop maturity group in crop rotations by districts of the Luhansk region were calculated. Currently, the structure of sown areas has changed, resulting in disruption of crop sequencing in previously recommended crop rotations. A threat has emerged regarding the spread of pests, diseases, and weeds.

We recommend the following crop sequencing in short-rotation crop rotations for the districts of the republic:

- A) Black fallow — winter wheat — maize for grain — sunflower.
- B) Pea — winter wheat — spring barley — sunflower.
- C) Grain sorghum — maize for grain — spring barley — sunflower.

Thus, the Luhansk People's Republic has a sufficient number of crops from which oil and ethyl alcohol intended for use as motor fuel can be obtained. In the crop rotations proposed for our region (unlike existing ones), it is possible to increase the production of vegetable oils by two times or more (765 l/ha) and ethyl alcohol by 883 l/ha.

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PERFORMANCE CHARACTERISTICS OF INDIVIDUAL GUIDES MADE OF HARZ LABS DENTAL CLEAR PRO PHOTOPOLYMER MATERIAL IN THE TREATMENT OF LUMBOSACRAL STENOSIS IN DOGS

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Abstract. *Lumbosacral stenosis in dogs is a common degenerative pathology characterized by nerve root compression, pain, and gait disturbances. Large breeds are particularly predisposed to it. Treatment is often surgical, and its success directly depends on the precision of maneuvers in the complex transitional zone between the last lumbar (L7) and the first sacral (S1) vertebra. Technologies that enhance accuracy and reduce invasiveness are necessary to minimize risks.*

One of these involves personalized guiding companies developing 3D-reading methods based on CT channels. Their application accelerates and facilitates surgical access. However, the effectiveness of such guides critically depends on the properties of the polymer material, which must combine strength, anatomical precision, stability during sterilization, and biocompatibility.

The study was conducted during surgery on the L7-S1 segment using the polymer material Harz Labs Dental Clear Pro (photopolymer material). Its mechanical and operational properties were evaluated, including stability during sterilization. Conclusions. The polymer material Harz Labs Dental Clear Pro is suitable for printing individualized guides, as it combines positioning accuracy, stability during sterilization, and satisfactory mechanical properties.

It can be concluded that their use in veterinary neurosurgery for dorsal laminectomy and transpedicular stabilization reduces operation time and surgical trauma, owing to the optimal properties of this polymer.

Keywords: *veterinary surgery; dogs; lumbosacral stenosis; individual surgical guides; photopolymers; Harz Labs Dental Clear Pro*

Introduction

Lumbosacral stenosis in dogs is a localized narrowing of the spinal canal at the L7–S1 segment (between the last lumbar and first sacral vertebrae). The primary cause of impaired mobility in this segment develops as a result of degenerative changes in the intervertebral discs, articular processes, and ligamentous apparatus. This pathological process leads to a complex of associated conditions: facet joint osteoarthritis, progressive ventral compression of spinal nerve roots by the intervertebral disc, dorsal hypertrophy of the ligamentum flavum, spondylosis, spondylolisthesis, foraminal stenosis, ganglioneuritis, and pronounced pain syndrome.

The disease is most frequently diagnosed in medium and large dog breeds, such as German Shepherds, Rottweilers, Cane Corsos, and others. Its typical manifestations include chronic pain, lameness, paresis of the pelvic limbs, and difficulty standing. Patients often present at a late stage, when the vertebrae already exhibit pronounced degenerative changes, rendering conservative therapy largely ineffective.

The goal of surgical treatment is decompression of the nervous structures and stabilization of the L7–S1 segment. However, surgery in this area involves a high risk of injury to spinal nerves, roots, and vessels [3], which necessitates increased precision and minimal invasiveness of the method.

At this final stage, surgical guides created based on CT data using 3D modeling and additive technologies are considered among the most promising approaches [4]. Studies confirm that their use significantly enhances the accuracy of transpedicular construct and implant placement in dogs [4]. Nevertheless, the issue of selecting a reliable polymer material for the manufacture of such guides remains unresolved. The material must meet strict Requirements: to withstand standard sterilization procedures (pre-sterilization cleaning, autoclaving), to be biologically inert, to ensure dimensional stability, and to provide mechanical strength [5, 6].

Thus, amid the active development of additive technologies in veterinary medicine, investigating the properties of polymeric materials for producing individualized guides constitutes a highly relevant challenge for veterinary neurosurgery.

Aim and objectives of the study

The aim of this study was to evaluate the effectiveness of the Harz Labs Dental Clear Pro material for manufacturing individual surgical guides. These guides are intended for use in surgical correction of the lumbosacral region, specifically for performing dorsal laminectomy and stabilizing the L7-S1 segment using a transpedicular construct.

The following objectives were established within the scope of this work:

1. To analyze the mechanical and operational characteristics of the polymer.
2. To assess the resistance of the surgical guides made from this material to the sterilization process.

3. To determine the clinical significance of these guides for the surgical treatment of lumbosacral stenosis in dogs.

Figure 1. Guides in the 3D modeling software, dorsal view (from above).

Methodology

This experimental study was conducted under the conditions of a veterinary clinic. The object of the study was the polymer material Harz Labs Dental Clear Pro used for the production of surgical guides. The material for the application of the guides consisted of dogs diagnosed with lumbosacral stenosis; The diagnosis was confirmed by comprehensive data from anamnesis, clinical examination, MRI, and CT [7].

The design of individual guides was performed using specialized software for 3D modeling, Bona Planner. The photopolymer resins were produced by photopolymer printing (SLA).

All finished products undergo chemical disinfection and sterilization. The following parameters were measured after sterilization processing:

1. Preservation of height (structure and shape);
2. Accuracy of anatomical fit to the bony structures;
3. Ergonomics and ease of use during the surgical procedure.
4. The analysis of the obtained results was conducted using comparative analysis.

Figure 2. 3D model of guides for the L7 and S1 vertebrae in a dog with deformation of the L7 vertebra.

Figure 3. 3D model of guides for the L7 and S1 vertebrae in a dog with planned transpedicular screw trajectories in Bonna Planner software.

Research Results and Their Theoretical and Practical Significance

No significant differences were identified in the key characteristics of individual surgical guides depending on the guide model during the experiment. Samples made from Harz Labs Dental Clear Pro met the above-mentioned requirements.

Table 1. Comparative characteristics of polymer materials used for the fabrication of personalized guides.

Material	Printing Technology	Fit accuracy	Resistance to sterilization	Clinical evaluation
Harz Labs Dental Clear Pro	SLA	High	Geometry fully preserved	Recommended

The Harz Labs Dental Clear Pro photopolymer demonstrated good efficacy for use in 3D printing personalized guides and their subsequent application in surgery for lumbosacral stenosis in dogs. Guides made from this material maintained geometric parameters after sterilization and did not undergo deformation during surgery. Among the relative drawbacks, the material’s brittleness under impact loading can be noted; however, this is a minor disadvantage, as the intended use of the guides does not involve impact stresses.

Figure 4. Finished personalized guides fabricated from Harz Labs Dental Clear Pro photopolymer.

The scientific significance of this study lies in deepening the understanding of the application of additive technologies in veterinary neurosurgery. The conducted analysis of Harz Labs Dental Clear Pro material contributes to the refinement of surgical techniques for the treatment of lumbosacral stenosis, focusing on enhancing accuracy, speed, and reducing surgical trauma. The results confirm that the selected polymer is reliable for use in 3D printing of personalized guides.

The practical significance of this study lies in the systematization of data regarding the applicability of polymeric materials for manufacturing personalized guides and implants. The presented mechanical and performance characteristics provide clinicians and engineers with objective criteria for selecting the optimal material. This enables a reduction in operative time, enhances efficiency, and minimizes the risk of intraoperative complications [9, 10].

The implementation of 3D modeling and additive manufacturing technologies facilitates the development of a personalized approach in the treatment of lumbosacral stenosis in dogs. This is crucial for improving surgical treatment outcomes and the quality of life of animals during the postoperative period [11].

Conclusion

The present study confirmed that the use of individualized surgical guides fabricated from photopolymer materials enhances the accuracy and safety of surgeries for lumbosacral stenosis in dogs, and that Harz Labs Dental Clear Pro is a reliable polymer for 3D printing and the subsequent application of individualized guides.

A key factor determining the effectiveness of guides is the choice of polymer material. The Harz Labs Dental Clear Pro photopolymer demonstrated high accuracy of anatomical fit, resistance to autoclaving, and satisfactory performance characteristics when used in the surgical wound, thereby proving its high clinical suitability. [7–12].

Guides fabricated from this material for dorsal laminectomy and transpedicular stabilization of the L7-S1 segment enable a significant improvement in the accuracy and efficacy of the procedure. This is achieved by the minimally invasive nature of the technique, which consequently reduces the risk of intra- and postoperative complications.

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SYNCHRONOUS PROTECTION OF ELECTRIC MOTORS FROM OPERATING IN A SINGLE-PHASE MODE

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Abstract. *This paper presents the device and the operating principle of a microprocessor-based protection system for asynchronous electric motors to prevent operation in single-phase mode. The obtained research results may be of interest to power grid companies, as well as to engineering and scientific personnel researching power transmission reliability.*

Keywords: *asynchronous electric motor; microprocessor device; maximum current protection; current cutoff; vacuum circuit breaker.*

Introduction

One cause of failure in three-phase asynchronous motors (AM) is their operation in single-phase mode. In agricultural production, overhead power transmission lines (OPTL) are predominantly used. According to data from electric grid companies, currently in Russia, overhead power transmission lines with a total length exceeding 1.1 million km are in operation. In the European part of the country, overhead lines are mostly constructed from conductors of the AC brand, with a cross-section of 35–70 sq. mm. Up to 60% of the lines were commissioned before 1975. Most of these power grids have exceeded their normative operational lifespan. One of the primary causes of faults leading to disconnection of overhead lines with voltages of 6–10 kV is conductor breakage. According to [1], the failure rate of electric motors in agricultural production due to breaks in 0.4 kV lines is 27%, i.e., nearly one-third of electric motors [2].

Materials and methods

A microprocessor device is proposed for the protection of asynchronous electric motors in a four-wire three-phase network. The device disconnects the power supply network upon the loss of one phase, both in 10 kV and 0.4 kV networks. This task is accomplished by the fact that the proposed digital device contains several modules responsible for the three-phase operation mode in the network[3]. This device utilizes existing 10 kV power transmission lines as a signal transmission channel for indicating a phase interruption. The signal represents a two-phase short circuit on the busbars of a complex 10/0.4 kV transformer substation, occurring upon operation of the short-circuiter.

Results and Discussion

The proposed device comprises a receiver for the transmitted signal and a transmitter. The transmitter is installed at the 10/0.4 kV substation on the low-voltage side. The receiver is situated in the 10 kV cell supplying the substation. The purpose of the device is to protect three-phase motor loads at the consumer's site, as motors fail within a short time in the event of a phase loss. Since most motors at agricultural enterprises are started through automatic circuit breakers and magnetic starters and do not always have correctly selected thermal protection, this device remains relevant [3].

It should also be taken into account that 10 kV lines are an order of magnitude longer than 0.4 kV lines, increasing the likelihood of breakage. This device enables the electrical networks to which the protected line belongs to promptly eliminate faults and avoid liability for damage caused to the enterprise — the consumer [4].

The proposed device does not alter the power supply scheme of consumer substations 10/0.4 kV from feeding substations with a lower voltage level of 10 kV. In a comprehensive transformer substation (CTS) 10/0.4 kV, a signal transmitter device is installed, consisting of a negative sequence voltage filter (FNOP), a short-circuit control unit (BU), and a short-circuiter.

The FNOP is connected directly to the 0.4 kV busbars, thereby isolating it from emergency conditions at the consumers (wire breaks in the 0.4 kV network, short circuits at the consumers, short circuits on the line).

The signal receiver is installed in the 10 kV cubicle and consists of a current-to-voltage converter (CVC) and a receiver control unit (RCU). The receiver operates in conjunction with the relay protection of the cubicle: maximum current protection (MCP), current cutoff, and automatic reclosing (AR). A CVC, which converts current to voltage, is installed in the circuit between the current transformers and the maximum current protection system. During two artificial two-phase short circuits at the 10/0.4 kV transformer substation (TSS) using a short-circuiting device, current surges occur in the 10 kV line, which, through the

supply continuity is maintained by capacitors; the installation of a low-power 12 V battery is also possible.

The signal receiver unit comprises the sensing element and the control unit. The sensing element is designed to detect the rate of current change, as any, even the most remote, forced two-phase short circuit on the protected line causes a current surge. The signal receiver is installed within the 10 kV switchgear cell; the cell's functional circuit remains unchanged. A current-to-voltage converter is installed in the circuit break of the current transformers and the maximum current protection relay. The intermediate relay actuates to trip the 10 kV cell vacuum circuit breaker. When the vacuum circuit breaker trips, the automatic reclosing system will activate, and after 3–4 seconds the vacuum circuit breaker will close, allowing the system to resume normal operation. During the current interruption, the magnetic starters and motors at 0.4 kV consumers will be de-energized, and restarting will require intervention by maintenance personnel.

The receiver and transmitter units operate together as follows: a conductor on the 10 kV line is interrupted, the FNOP of the transmitter outputs an asymmetry voltage, the time relay creates a 5–6 second pause, the transmitter's short-circuit control unit issues two pulses of 20 ms each, spaced by 180 ms, to the short-circuiter; the short-circuiter creates a two-phase short circuit for the duration of the control unit signal. Through the intermediate relay contact of the transmitter control unit, an indicator relay is activated. The two-phase short circuit generates a current surge in the current transformers of the 10 kV cell; the current surge is converted into a voltage surge, which is supplied to the receiver control unit. The control unit issues a signal to activate the intermediate relay, whose normally closed contact opens the power circuits of the electromagnetic drive of the vacuum circuit breaker, causing the breaker to trip. The automatic reclosing device then operates, and through an additional contact of the receiver intermediate relay, the indicator relay is triggered. After the reclose interval, the vacuum circuit breaker will switch to normal operating mode [5].

Conclusion

This device enables electrical networks, to which the protected line belongs, to promptly eliminate faults and avoid liability for damage caused to the enterprise — the consumer. Simultaneously, it enhances the relationship between the supplier and consumers of electric power.

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STUDY OF THE EFFECT OF OK 14.17 FLUX-CORED WIRE ON THE QUALITY OF ROLLER SURFACING FOR MINERAL WOOL PRODUCTION

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The article provides a brief description of the use and production of mineral wool with a description of the operation of equipment under the combined centrifugal-roll method of its manufacture, graphic materials of the incoming inspection of centrifuge rolls are provided. The results of the study of surfacing of rolls under a layer of flux with OK 14.71 wire with the NP-06Kh19N9G6 alloying system using AN60 and AN26 fluxes are presented, the analysis of the microstructure of the deposited material and its quality is presented.

Keywords: *mineral wool; roll, surfacing under a layer of flux, flux-cored wire.*

With the growth of housing construction, the production of thermal insulation materials, in particular, mineral (stone) wool, has increased [1], so in 2024 manufacturers are forced to set supply quotas, the cost of products reached 182 billion rubles [2]. Mineral wool [3] is intended for the manufacture of thermal insulation and sound insulation products in construction; as thermal insulation of surfaces with temperatures up to +700 °C of industrial equipment, tanks and pipelines of heating networks, main oil and gas pipelines, process pipelines of power plants, metallurgical, petrochemical and other industrial enterprises. Depending on the raw materials, it is distinguished by types [1, 3], such as: glass wool, stone wool, slag wool, made from melted glass, igneous rocks, blast furnace slag, respectively. The world's leading manufacturers use only rocks as raw materials, which makes it possible to obtain high-quality mineral wool with a long service life [3, 4].

The most promising method of fiber formation is a combined centrifugal-roller method [3, 4]. In this way, mineral fiber is obtained from the melt under the influence of centrifugal forces created by centrifuges. The centrifuge consists of

a U-shaped bed on which four working rolls are fixed in bearing units with individual drives. The rolls rotate towards each other in a vertical plane, and there is a fence on the sides.

Basalt melt containing acidic oxides in the following amounts: SiO₂ = 45%; Al₂O₃ = 15%; Fe₂O₃ = 6–7% is fed with metallurgical slag at a temperature of about 1400 °C and enters a certain point of the upper high-speed rotating roll 1, splitting the melt jet and transferring it to the next rolls. Roll 1 has a helical threading and rotates at a frequency of 3000 s⁻¹. Screw threading helps to accelerate the dismemberment of the stream. Roll 1 produces a small amount of mineral fiber, while the main part comes from rolls 2, 3 and 4. The rotation speed of the rolls increases as the melt advances (roll 2–4000 s⁻¹, roll 3–5000 s⁻¹, swath 4–6000 s⁻¹). It is mandatory to heat the surface of the centrifuge rolls to a temperature of at least 400 °C, since the fiber is formed only when the melt adheres to the surface of the rolls. The resulting fibers are picked up by the air and carried away to the fiber deposition chamber, where they settle on the surface of the mesh conveyor. To blow the resulting fibers, a fan with a capacity of 1400 m³/h is installed on the centrifuge [4].

As noted above, the main organ affecting the duration of the centrifuge operation is the rolls made of St 20, the operating time before replacement of which is 46–50 hours (Fig. 1). Increasing the performance of rolls (Fig. 2) with the use of new wear-resistant materials [5] in the manufacture and restoration technology is an urgent task. To repair them, the following methods of their repair are used: vibrating surfacing welding; induction cladding; electric spark surfacing Surfacing under a layer of flux.

The most common method of restoring centrifuge rolls is surfacing under a layer of AN26p or AN60 flux with OK 14.71 wire with the NP-06Kh19N9G6 alloying system [7]. Surfacing was carried out at direct current of reverse polarity in the mode I=350–380A, U=26–30V. The chemical composition and structure of the deposited metal of the third layer of cladding were investigated.

Table 1 — Composition of fluxes and deposited metal

Flux	SiO ₂	MnO	Fish	MgO	CaF ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	TiO ₂
AN26p	29–33	2,5–4,0	4–8	15–18	20–24	19–23	-
AN60	42–46	37–41	2–11	0,5–3,0	5–8	-	-
OK 10.83	2–4	8–14	1–2	2–4	45–55	26–32	5–8

It has been established that flux-cored wire OK 14.71 should be used in combination with neutral fluoride-basic flux OK 10.83 or one of the aluminate-basic fluxes. These fluxes have a low activity of $A_f \leq 0.05$, which is significantly lower than the activity of fluxes AN60 $A_f = 0.85$ and AN26p $A_f = 0.5$. High activity of

domestic fluxes is associated with a high content of SiO₂ in their composition (Table 1), which leads to the development of a silicon reduction process and, As a result, the transition of silicon into the weld metal.

Fig. 1 Worn rollers of centrifuges

Fig. 2 Main dimensions of the roll subject to control (a);
Inspection and post-hardfacing areas

In the process of surfacing under OK 10.83 flux, there is a slight separability of the slag crust on all layers on each wire. Under the AN26 flux, spinels of the “birch bark” type are formed on the surface of the joint. Spinel are formed over

the entire surface. During surfacing with an overlap of 30–50%, the spinels melt and interlayer slag inclusions are not detected. There is a “shooting” of slag residues from the surface of the roller. Under the AN26 flux, a continuous layer of spinels is formed on the entire surface of the roller, which are difficult to remove. The separability of the slag crust is poor. The formation of spinels on the surface is an undesirable factor. The absence of cracks in the first and 1 2 layers of the metal deposited under the AN26 flux was established. The metal contains complex silicate inclusions with a diameter of 1–15 μm (Fig. 3). But in the fusion zones of the third and second layers, a single crack with a length of 500–1000 μm (0.5–1.0 mm) can form in the austenitic structure of the metal (Fig. 4).

Fig. 3 Silicate inclusions in layers 1 and 2 of the deposited metal (x 200)(a); crack in the fusion zone of layers 2 and 3 (x 400) (b)

In connection with the above, surfacing of rolls with OK 14.71 wire with the Np-06Kh19N9G6 alloying system with the use of AN60 and AN26 fluxes has some shortcomings that need to be eliminated. It has been established that:

- during surfacing the content of silicon in the welded metal increases, the high content of which is associated with the development of the silica reduction process;

- poor separability of the slag crust is associated with the formation of chromium and chromium-manganese spinels;

- during surfacing with an overlap of 30–50%, spinels melt and interlayer slag inclusions are not detected, i.e. there is a “shooting” of slag residues from the surface of the roller;

- a single crack may occur due to the development of a silica reduction process;

- it is necessary to adjust the composition of flux-cored wire OK 14.71 for fluxes AN60 and AN26.

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DEVELOPMENT OF AN INTELLIGENT INFORMATION-MEASURING AND ADAPTIVE CONTROL SYSTEM FOR UNMANNED AERIAL VEHICLES

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Abstract. *The article considers the issue of building an architecture of an Intelligent Data Measurement and Adaptive Control System integrated with an Unmanned Aerial Vehicle as a research object. This system combines sensors of various purposes that perform the functions of primary information sources, which determine the quantitative and qualitative characteristics of the object.*

Through intelligent sensors, the system scans or measures informative parameters with high accuracy, and the principle of a multisensor system is proposed here. Thus, sensors of various purposes operate simultaneously and scan all the signs, and the collected information is processed by special algorithms, obtaining accurate results.

The accuracy of informative parameters is realized by an individual approach to the measurement procedure of each sensor, the application of special hybrid test algorithms. At the same time, the “deformation” of the individual conversion characteristics of the sensors, their dynamic changes, in short, the parameters of their mathematical models are identified.

Keywords: *flying device, multisensor system, measurement, scanning, mathematical model, high accuracy, reliability*

1.Introduction.

Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAV) have become a critical technological platform across a wide range of civilian and industrial domains, including precision agriculture, environmental monitoring, infrastructure inspection, disaster response, logistics, and intelligent transportation systems [1]–[4]. Their increasing operational autonomy, mission complexity, and deployment in dynamically

changing environments impose stringent requirements on onboard sensing, information processing, and control architectures [5], [6]. Conventional UAV control systems, primarily based on fixed-parameter control laws and deterministic sensor fusion strategies, are often insufficient to ensure robust performance under uncertainties caused by environmental disturbances, sensor noise, model mismatches, and nonlinear aerodynamic effects [7], [8].

Modern UAV platforms operate as cyber-physical systems, where physical dynamics, sensor networks, embedded computation, and communication infrastructures are tightly integrated [9], [10]. In such systems, the quality of decision-making and flight stability is directly dependent on the accuracy, reliability, and adaptability of information-measuring subsystems [11]. Traditional measurement architectures are typically designed as static pipelines — sensor acquisition, signal conditioning, estimation, and control — without closed-loop adaptation of the measurement process itself [12]. This separation between measurement and control significantly limits system intelligence and resilience in uncertain operational conditions [13].

The concept of an intelligent information-measuring system (IIMS) introduces a new paradigm in UAV design, where measurement, estimation, learning, and control are treated as a unified adaptive process [14], [15]. In this paradigm, sensors are no longer passive data sources but become active elements of an adaptive feedback structure capable of self-calibration, error compensation, reliability assessment, and information prioritization [16]. Combined with adaptive and learning-based control strategies, such systems enable real-time structural adaptation of both the measurement model and the control law in response to internal system dynamics and external environmental changes [17], [18].

Recent advances in machine learning, adaptive filtering, multi-sensor data fusion, and embedded artificial intelligence have created the technological foundation for implementing such integrated architectures [19]–[22]. However, most existing research focuses on isolated components — such as adaptive controllers, neural-network-based estimators, or sensor fusion algorithms — without a unified system-level framework that formally integrates information measurement, intelligent data processing, and adaptive control into a single coherent architecture [23], [24]. This fragmentation limits scalability, explainability, and formal verification of UAV intelligence systems [25].

This article addresses this gap by proposing a unified intelligent information-measuring and adaptive control system architecture for unmanned aerial vehicles. The proposed system integrates multi-sensor measurement models, intelligent data fusion, adaptive state estimation, and learning-based control into a closed-loop cognitive structure [26], [27]. The architecture is designed to support self-adaptation, fault tolerance, measurement uncertainty compensation, and dynamic reconfiguration of control strategies in real time. A formal system model is developed,

including information flow structures, adaptive feedback loops, and functional decomposition of system modules.

2.The proposed approach

The proposed approach provides a foundation for next-generation UAV systems capable of autonomous perception, self-optimization, and resilient control in uncertain and dynamically changing environments. This work contributes to the theoretical and applied development of intelligent cyber-physical systems and supports the transition from conventional UAV control architectures to fully integrated intelligent autonomous flight systems.

Recently, considerable attention has been paid to the development and practical application of a new generation of intelligent measurement systems (IMS) and adaptive control systems (ACS) for unmanned aerial vehicles (UAV). Therefore, the design of such devices and systems in the instrument-making industry, including their metrology and information support, is subject to very stringent requirements when upgrading existing devices.

To perform complex control tasks remotely or locally, it is necessary to create a multi-sensor IMS structure based on various functional modules and information support. Given the complexity of the objects being studied, a multi-sensor system is required that can be used in challenging metrology conditions, during complex control maneuvers, in smooth flight mode, when stopped in space, when approaching target points, etc. All of this emphasizes the requirement for minimal IMS weight and is the main guarantee of the simplicity and reliability of new IMS.

This article, along with technical means, focuses on solving the problems of intellectualizing information support and metrology (measurement) procedures, simplifying all operations, optimizing, and fully automating them. Thus, a completely new, effective approach is proposed using structural-algorithmic methods for fast, accurate, and reliable measurements and control in a UAV system. The focus is on optimal control of equipment operating in complex metrological environments, addressing the harsh conditions that may arise under these conditions, and implementing functions such as adaptive trajectory or position control. All of this is implemented using modern industrial ICT, microprocessors, computer technologies, PLCs, smart sensors, and other devices.

In short, integrated circuits (ICs) and automated measurement systems (AMS) play a significant role in addressing this pressing issue and provide a systematic solution to the challenges posed.

The primary goal here is to ensure high measurement accuracy, which, in turn, depends on the accuracy of the underlying measuring instruments and sensors. Due to external influences, vibration, noise, and electromagnetic effects, sensors cannot maintain their metrological properties, and their conversion characteristics

constantly change. This leads to significant errors that distort the collected data. This process requires the comprehensive measurement and control of numerous parameters using various methods. As we have already noted, solving this problem yields better results and eliminates errors when using structural and algorithmic measurement methods.

It is known that existing devices still do not fully meet customer needs and require constant calibration. However, solving this problem in a hard-to-reach environment is ultimately a very complex and challenging task.

For space systems, these systems and their core functions — data collection, processing, and lossless transmission — are underdeveloped. Optimal design of integrated circuits and automated information systems (AIS), experimental studies, adaptive measurement and control planning, optimization, and other problems still require specialized solutions. This article examines these issues and the potential for applying algorithmic and structural methods to improve the accuracy of measurements and conversions using sensor check measurements, monitoring their metrological characteristics, and making adjustments. In recent years, publications and literature reviews have provided an in-depth analysis of existing methods and technical tools, drawing conclusions and substantiating the relevance of using structural-algorithmic methods to improve the accuracy and reliability of existing systems in operational conditions.

3. Building the architectural topology of an integrated UAV and AIS.

To achieve this, the following key stages must be included in the design:

1. Types and structure of information-measuring systems

Information-measuring technologies are a type of information technology and differ from other technologies in that they are explicitly cognitive in nature and implement specific procedures. These include:

- obtaining initial measurement data through the interaction of primary measurement transmitters (sensors) with the measured object;
- converting measurement data with specified and guaranteed accuracy;
- comparing measurement data signals with the dimensions of generally accepted units of measurement, assessing and presenting the residual uncertainty characteristics of the measured values.

Existing systems do not meet all requirements, and design simplification and modernization are inevitable:

The optimal structure of an IMS is shown in Fig.1.

Fig. 1. Simplified structure of the IIS and APCS

Here: I—Measurement subsystems, II—Classification subsystems, III—Control subsystems, IV — Execution subsystems, PMT — main measurement transducers.

Modern information-measuring technologies are acquiring additional capabilities through the use of artificial intelligence hardware and software. One of the most important challenges in the development of information-measuring technologies is expanding the range of measured quantities and ensuring measurements under the influence of “harsh” external factors (high temperature, high pressure, ionizing radiation, etc.).

Solving such problems requires a more complex structure of the measuring instruments used — sensors that create multi-sensor measurement systems — and the technical equipment required for their operation. The objects of study are characterized by a large number of parameters, and these parameters often change their values rapidly for various reasons.

Sometimes, it is necessary to conduct complex measurements to obtain information about the object's parameters, and the value of the measured variable is calculated based on known functional relationships between it and the measured quantities.

These problems are solved to a certain extent using widely used traditional information and measurement systems (IMS).

Purpose and Types of Integrated Circuits

Key Characteristics of Integrated Circuits:

- Application Area; Assembly Method;
- Input Signal Structure and Types;
- Measurement Types;
- Component Operating Mode and Functional Characteristics.

By application area, integrated circuits are divided into the following groups:

- For scientific research;
- For testing and monitoring complex products;
- For process control.

By Assembly Method:

- Aggregate;
- Non-aggregate, consisting of components specifically designed for specific systems.

Aggregate integrated circuits typically include a universal core—a central control system (DCS), from which integrated circuits for various purposes can be built using sensors for various physical quantities.

4.Design Features

By Design Features:

- Parallel-Serial Systems. The main feature of this structure is the presence of a periodically changing DCS with multiple sensors;
- Parallel systems consisting of several simultaneously operating channels, whose output systems are transformed by a single functional converter and processed on a single computing device.

Input signals to an integrated circuit can be continuous or discrete, deterministic or random.

Depending on the relationship between the rate of change of input signals and the inertial properties of the system, two main operating modes of the IMS are

distinguished: static and dynamic. In dynamic mode, the inertial properties of the system influence the measurement result.

An IMS component is defined as a technical device within the IMS that performs one of the functions required for the measurement process and the conversion of measurement information into other types of information. Based on their functions, components are divided into measurement, communication, computational, and informational.

The connecting component of an IMS is a technical device or part of the surrounding environment designed or used to transmit signals carrying information about the measured value from one component of the IMS to another with minimal possible distortion.

The computing component of an IMS is a digital computing device (or part thereof) together with software that processes (calculates) observation results to obtain, by calculation, measurement results expressed as a number or corresponding code.

Computing components are subdivided into:

- analog computing — analog devices whose output signal is a function of two or more signals;
- digital computing — devices whose digital output signal is a function of two or more signals.

The information component of an IMS is a technical device designed to receive, store, convert, and transmit information. From the perspective of the information theory of measuring devices, the measurement process performed by any measuring device (including the necessary actions of the human operator) consists of a series of sequential transformations of information about the measured value, carried out until it is represented in the form required for the high-precision measurement. The measuring instrument is considered a channel for receiving and transmitting information (measurement). Thus, the measuring instrument and the measuring component of the IMS are a type of information component.

5.Compensation for External Influences

The best method for self-compensation of external influences on measuring systems is considered to be the test measurement method. There are quite a lot of external influence factors, and the most persistent of them is the effect of temperature. The reduction of these and other influences does not depend only on external conditions. Even internal errors of the system occur.

The test measurement system is implemented on a similar — analogous principle for almost all parameters. For clarity, let's look at the principle of autocompensation on the example of changes in the metrological characteristics of sensors due to temperature changes. To reduce the influence of temperature and correct the error caused by changes in external conditions, it is possible to use the method

of additional measurements of disturbing effects, in particular temperature. Invariance to the additional error of any sensor that occurs when the ambient temperature changes with a known temperature influence function is achieved by using an additional temperature measurement channel.

The presented experimental results of numerous tests show that the impact functions are individual for each sensor sample. Despite this, it can be argued that the functions $y_0(t^0)$, $a_1(t^0)$, $a_2(t^0)$, $a_3(t^0)$, which relate the parameters of the sensor calibration characteristics to the temperature, can be described with sufficient accuracy by a polynomial of no higher than the third degree, but the coefficients of this polynomial will differ for different sensor samples. However, by using the individual influence function of each sensor, invariance to changes in ambient temperature can be ensured. This principle is generally expressed as follows:

$$y_0(t^0) = f\{a_1(t^0), a_2(t^0), a_3(t^0)\}, \quad (1)$$

A more rational approach here is to sufficiently improve measurement accuracy to achieve high measurement precision. This depends on the correct selection of optimal reference values and their precise placement in test models — in other words, on the use of structures based on reference test values. These methods allow the use of any sensor with short-term (real-time) stability, which leads to the concept of a “smart” sensor.

Fig.2 below shows a structural model for testing a differential pressure sensor, consisting of three reference values (RV) (example of the most accurate value): P_{RV1} , P_{RV2} and P_{RV3} .

Fig. 2. IMS structure with three sample signals

4. Integration of adaptive control algorithms with real-time information feedback from the intelligent measurement system.
5. Establishment of a formal modeling framework for system analysis, scalability, and future expansion toward fully autonomous cognitive UAV platforms.

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FUZZY NEURAL NETWORK FOR AUTOMATED SYSTEM INTRUSION DETECTION

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Abstract. *The article discusses the problem of detecting intrusions into an automated system, the features of computer support for difficult-to-formalize tasks. The intrusion detection system is proposed to be based on a fuzzy neural network.*

Keywords: *fuzzy neural network, intrusion detection, hard-to-formalize tasks.*

Introduction. The main task of the intrusion detection system (IDS) in any automated system is to analyze network traffic and build an assumption about a possible intrusion into the protected automated system or to perform firewall functions. Such a task can be classified as difficult to formalize, since such tasks are characterized by a set of the following characteristics: a) the functioning of the object against which decisions need to be made occurs in an environment of different types of data (quantitative, qualitative, nominal, contradictory, incomplete, “noisy,” etc.); b) uncertainty associated with the fact that the values of not all variables available for observation can be determined with the required reliability; c) impossibility of complete formalization of processes occurring in the object and in its environment, due to their complexity, a priori uncertainty and heterogeneity of data reflecting its behavior [1].

Such problems require methods of identifying patterns to solve them. One such method could be a neural network machine learning method. In addition to the ability to solve difficult-to-formalize problems, it has the ability to build self-learning and self-adjusting systems, is combined with traditional “computational” information processing algorithms, and allows you to build complex adaptive, reliable decision-making systems [2].

The advantage of a neural network is its ability to learn on its own, and not depend on the data that was embedded in it.

The decision task, in general, can be formulated as follows.

There is some object (for example, an automated system), regarding which you need to make decisions, which has the following features.

1. An behavior of an object due to the complexity of the processes occurring in it and in its environment cannot be strictly formalized.

2. Any events occurring in an object can be represented by statements $a_i \in A$ used in mathematical logic to describe the subject area. Here, A is a finite set of possible events (propositions).

3. An object can be in two states: s_0 , in which it is not affected by various destabilizing factors and therefore can perform all its functions without restrictions, and s_1 , in which, due to the influence of destabilizing factors, it cannot perform its functions in full. A variety of possible factors X are assumed to be known.

4. The degree of confidence that it was this factor $x_i \in X$ that influenced the state of the object can be determined by the set of events that occurred.

The task is to determine the state of the object (s_0 or s_1) and the characteristics of the effects (if the state turns out to be s_1) to take measures to return the object from state s_1 to state s_0 .

Provisions based on the proposed solution.

Any statements can be considered as fuzzy values of some factor on which the state of the object depends. Therefore, each statement can be associated with the value of the truth (reliability) $\rho_{a_i}(u_i)$ of the statement, where u_i is a measurable variable, the values of which determine the statement. For example, the statement

$a =$ “repeat connection requests” can be characterized by the function $\rho_a(u) = \frac{u-1}{n_{\max}}$, where u is the number of connection requests in the current time interval, n_{\max} is the permissible number of requests in any time interval.

As a decision model, we take the deductive rule of simple conclusion (modus

ponens): $\frac{A, A \rightarrow B}{B}$ — “If there is a statement A and from A follows B , then there is B . The implication $A \rightarrow B$ can be stored in the memory of the intrusion detection system (IDS), and the decision-making task can thus be reduced to assessing the correspondence of the predicate \hat{A} obtained as a result of current observations to the predicate A of the implication $A \rightarrow B$ stored in the IDS knowledge base. Such implications can be in the form: $X \rightarrow d$, where X is a vector of different types of signs of effects on an object obtained during the functioning of the object, and d is a decision about the state of the object: s_0 or s_1 .”

As the basis of computer support for the solution, an artificial neural network (NN) was chosen, due to the fact that: 1) NN can be trained to perform complex functions; 2) NN are able to process both quantitative and qualitative data, 3) NN are able to generate solutions based on the receipt of probabilistic and fuzzy data

[2]; 4) there are several types of artificial neural networks, so you can choose the most suitable option to support solutions to difficult-to-formalize problems.

Any NS is a system of neurons connected in a certain way with the topology of a directed graph, which is able to generate output information through the reaction of its state to input actions.

Fuzzy neural network. A formal neuron is a threshold element whose inputs have excitatory (sometimes inhibitory) synapses. In the neuron, taking into account the weights of the synapses, the sum of the input signals is determined and when this sum exceeds a certain threshold, the output signal is generated:

$$z_j = \sum_i w_{ji}(x_i), y_j = f(z_j, h_j),$$

where x_i is input signals are the main factors affecting the state of the object, h_j is — the threshold value of the j -th neuron, w_{ji} is the weight of the input signals of the neuron; y_j is the output signal generated by the neuron, $f(z_j, h_j)$ is the activation function that implements the rule for issuing the output signal, h_j is the threshold value.

The disclosed method of constructing a decision support system is based on using a two-layer fuzzy neural network consisting of receptor and processing layers.

The receptor layer contains neurons connected by inputs to the external environment, the state of which at each moment of time is described by a set of statements A . Subsets of $A_j \subseteq A$, ($j = 1, \dots, n_j$) characterize a specific j -th characteristic of the external environment, the totality of which describes the situation of the environment in the current time interval. In the operating mode, real numbers are supplied to the receptor layer — the values of the validity functions in the range $(0, 1)$ characterizing the statements.

The receptor layer consists of a set of neurons with outputs $x_j = f_j\left(\sum_{i=1}^{m_j} \rho_{a_{ji}}(u)\right)$, where a_{ji} is the input utterances, m_j is the number of inputs, and $f(x, h_x)$ is the activation function of the receptor neuron, $\rho_{a_{ji}}(u)$ — the value of the reliability of the expression a_i for factor x_j .

$$f(x, h_x) = \begin{cases} \left(\sum_{i=1}^{m_j} \rho_{a_{ji}}(u)\right), & \text{if } \left(\sum_{i=1}^{m_j} \rho_{a_{ji}}(u)\right) \geq h_j \\ 0, & \text{if otherwise} \end{cases}.$$

The processing layer consists of one or more neurons. Their number depends on the number of possible alternative solutions. In the event that only two solutions are possible (yes or no), one neuron is enough:

$$d = f\left(\sum_{i=1}^m w_i(x_i)\right),$$

where $w_i(x_i)$ is the factor weight x_i , m is the number of factors considered, $f(\cdot)$ is the activation function of the processing neuron:

$$f\left(\sum_{i=1}^m w_i(x_i)\right) = \begin{cases} \sum_i w_i & \text{if } \sum_i w_i \geq h_w \\ 0, & \text{if otherwise} \end{cases}$$

A diagram of a fuzzy neural network is shown in Fig. 1.

Figure 1

As signs of intrusions into an automated system (attacks), for example, it is proposed to attribute eight factors determined by the disjunctions of the corresponding statements:

$X_1 = a_{11} \vee a_{12} \vee a_{13} \vee a_{14}$ — repetition of certain events, actions: a_{11} — port scanning, a_{12} — repeated password guessing, a_{13} — repetition of connection requests, a_{14} — other repeatedly repeated action;

$X_2 = \bigvee_{i=1}^7 a_{2i}$ - unexpected parameters in network packets: a_{21} — unexpected address attributes, a_{22} — non-routed or reserved IP addresses, a_{23} — the value in the source port field is zero, a_{24} — the value in the destination port field is zero, a_{25} — request for non-standard servers, a_{26} — unexpected time or date attributes, a_{27} — any other unexpected parameter in the network packet;

$X_3 = \bigvee_{i=1}^5 a_{3i}$ — unexpected parameters of network packet flags: a_{31} — two mutually exclusive SYN and FIN flags were found in the packet, a_{32} — the presence of only the FIN flag; a_{33} — invalid combinations of SYN+RST flags, a_{34} — invalid combinations of RST+FIN flags; a_{35} — any other unusual parameters of network packet flags;

$X_4 = \bigvee_{i=1}^3 a_{4i}$ — inappropriate parameters of network traffic: a_{41} — parameters of incoming traffic (packets entering the local network from outside, having a source address corresponding to the range of addresses of the internal network); a_{42} — outbound traffic parameters (packets originating from the local network that have a source address corresponding to the range of addresses of the external network); a_{43} — any other network traffic parameters that are not allowed due to security policy restrictions;

$X_5 = \bigvee_{i=1}^3 a_{5i}$ — commands that do not correspond to the current situation: a_{51} — incorrect requests, a_{52} — incorrect answers; a_{53} — any other commands that do not correspond to the current situation due to security policy restrictions;

$X_6 = \bigvee_{i=1}^4 a_{6i}$ — anomalies of network traffic: a_{61} — change in load factor, a_{62} — change in packet size, a_{63} — change in the average number of fragmented packets, a_{64} — any other abnormal changes in network traffic parameters;

$X_7 = \bigvee_{i=1}^5 a_{7i}$ — inappropriate attributes of system functioning: (abnormal system characteristics: a_{71} — increased CPU load, a_{72} — intensive access to RAM, a_{73} — intensive access to disk memory, a_{74} — intensive access to files, a_{75} — any other abnormal changes in system characteristics;

$X_8 = \bigvee_{i=1}^4 a_{8i}$ — discrepancy between the characteristics of the work of users and their profiles: a_{81} — deviation from the time of peak and minimum loads, a_{82} — deviation from the duration of a typical work session, a_{83} — deviation from the usual

time of login and logout, a_{84} — any other deviations from the usual characteristics of the work of users.

NN training was carried out by the method of backward propagation of errors [3]. The purpose of the training is to determine from the data samples the values of the thresholds: h_j and h_w , as well as the values of the weights. Studies of the proposed method of constructing the PCFT, carried out by modeling situations and solving practical problems, confirmed its high efficiency.

Conclusion. The proposed approach could be the basis for building intrusion detection systems and computer decision support systems for difficult-to-formalize tasks.

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THEORETICAL DEFINITION OF THE CAPFA ROTATION SPEED THAT ENSURES ONLY MIXING IN A VERTICAL CHAMBER WITH VARIABLE GEOMETRY

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The article substantiates the relevance of using a mixing apparatus capable of high-quality mixing of bulk materials, controlling the mixing process. The necessity of determining the operating speeds of the trunnion rotation, at which only mixing, joint mixing and regrinding of the components of the mixture can be carried out, is substantiated, since the condition of the components of the finished mixture significantly affects the quality of the finished product.

Keywords: *rotation speed, trunnion, vertical chamber with variable geometry, pseudo-solid element of the string type, blades in the form of rods.*

Mixing of bulk materials is widely used in various industries: construction, chemical technology and others. At the same time, the task of preparing high-quality homogeneous mixtures of bulk materials is associated with a number of difficulties, such as a wide range of changes in the physical and mechanical properties of processed materials, requirements for the quality and composition of the product, productivity, energy and metal intensity, ensuring only the mixing of particles or mixing grinding, which significantly affects the quality of the finished product. One of the possible ways to improve mixing equipment for bulk materials is the use of mixer designs with the ability to regulate the movement of particles inside the chamber, which will ensure the necessary movement of particles, and the stable achievement of the required quality of the mixture. This can be organized using a mixing chamber made of elastic materials, as well as internal mixing elements, while determining the rotation speeds of these elements [1, 2].

It is necessary to determine the operating speeds of the trunnion at which only mixing or co-mixing and grinding of components from the prevailing shear

stresses can be carried out in an apparatus with a vertical chamber in the form of a half-barrel with variable geometry [3, 4]. In case of contact of particles in the wall zone:

- less than the allowed values, then the condition for the mixing process only will be met; $\tau_{max} < [\tau]$
- more than the permissible values $\tau_{max} > [\tau]$, then the processes of mixing with grinding will take place.

Destruction of material particles in the considered design of the mixing chamber can occur [3]:

1. from the joint action of a pseudo-solid element such as a string and its walls;
2. From the impact of vertical blades in the form of rods.

Let's consider both options:

1) Destruction of material particles from the combined action of a pseudo-solid element such as a string and its walls by abrasion in the chamber will occur if:

$$\tau_{sr} \geq [\tau], \quad (1)$$

where $[\tau]$, are the permissible shear abrasion stresses between the sand and cement particles, $[\tau] = 13000 \text{ Па}$

Based on (1) and (2), the change in the particle size of the material will not occur if the trunnion speed satisfies the inequality:

$$\omega \leq \omega_{min} = \sqrt{\frac{[\tau]}{\gamma r_{sr} d_s f_n}}. \quad (2)$$

From the impact of a pseudo-solid element of the chamber, such as a string and its walls, if, then grinding processes with mixing will occur under the following conditions: $\tau_{sr} > [\tau]$

$$\tau_{sr} = \frac{F_{tr}}{S} < [\tau], \quad (3)$$

$$\tau_{sr} = \chi \frac{\omega r_{sr}}{d_s}, \quad (4)$$

where d_s is the distance between the layers, approximately equal to the size of the particles to be mixed, m;

$$r_{sr} = \frac{(0,9R_0 + 0,5r_e)}{2}, \quad (5)$$

$$F_{tr} = f_n \frac{M \omega^2 r_{sr}^2}{r_{sr}} = f_n M \omega^2 r_{sr}; \quad (6)$$

$$\chi = \frac{F_{tr} d_s}{S \omega r_{sr}}, \quad (7)$$

where χ is the coefficient of pseudoviscous grinding, Pa·with;
 M is the weight of the chamber load, kg;

S is the area of the inner surface of the chamber, m²: $S_{max}=0.233$ m²; $S_{min}=0.023$ m².

$$\tau_{sr} = \frac{f_n M \omega^2 r_{sr}}{2S} = \frac{f_n M \omega^2 (1.5r_e + r_z + 0.5R_0)}{2S} < [\tau]; \quad (8)$$

$$\tau_{max} = \frac{f_n M \omega^2 r_{max}}{2S} < [\tau]. \quad (9)$$

It has been theoretically established that when exposed to a pseudo-solid element of the chamber and its walls at a trunnion rotation speed of 360^{min}⁻¹ (Fig. 1, a), the near-surface structure of the material particles will be disrupted. $\omega = 38c^{-1}$

2) From the action of the rods due to the frictional force F_{tr} between adjacent layers of material with a thickness of $ds \geq d$. The value of the stress τ_{sr} , which arises from the action of the frictional force on the cylindrical surface of the rod Sl [2]:

$$\tau_{sr} = \frac{F_{tr}}{S} < [\tau], \quad (10)$$

$$S_l = 2\pi R_{st} h_l, \quad (11)$$

where h_l is the height of the blade, m;

Sl is the area of drag of the blade surface in the form of rods, m²

R_{st} is the radius of the circle described by one rod, $R_{st}=R_0-r_z$, m;

F_{tr} is the frictional force, N;

$$F_{tr} = f_n F_c, \quad (12)$$

where F_c is the centrifugal force acting on the material particles as a result of the movement of a single rod mounted on the trunnion, H;

$f_n = 0.15-0.45$ coefficient of friction of mixed particles with each other;

$$F_c = M_1 \omega^2 R_{st}, \quad (13)$$

Where is

$$M_1 = 2\pi R_{st} h_l d_s \rho, \quad (14)$$

here ρ is the specific gravity of the material, kg/m³;

M_1 is the mass of the material moved by one rod along the trajectory, kg.

Substituting (11), (12) in (10) taking into account formulas (13), (14) leads to the following result:

$$\tau_{max} = \rho(R_0 - r_z) d_s \omega^2 f_n. \quad (15)$$

It is theoretically established that when blades in the form of rods act on the material at a spindle rotation frequency of 1200 min⁻¹ ($\omega=125$ s⁻¹) (Fig. 1, b), the disruption of the near-surface structure of the material particles will occur, which is 3.3 times greater than the effect of the chamber walls.

Graphs (Fig. 1) of changes in the calculated mean shear stress τ_{max} at particle contact during mixing from the coefficient of friction of the particles f_n and the trunnion rotation speed are constructed.

Fig. 1. Determination of the speed of rotation of the drive, at which the destruction of material particles will begin during mixing from the impact of a pseudo-solid element of the chamber — such as a string and its walls (a); as well as blades in the form of rods (b)

It has been established that the calculated value occurs when:

$$\tau_{SR} = [\tau] = 13000 \text{ Па:}$$

1. $\omega = 38 \text{ c}^{-1}$ (approximately 360 min^{-1} trunnion) (Fig. 1, a) under the influence of a pseudo-solid element of the chamber and its walls, which is 3.3 times less than from the impact of rods.

2. $\omega = 125 \text{ c}^{-1}$ (approximately 1200 min^{-1} trunnion) (Fig. 1, b) when exposed to rods.

This can be explained by the fact that in the process of mixing particles, the abrasion of particles against each other prevails, and for the most part, during contact, in the near-surface layers of the chamber, which is much larger than the frontal total area of the rods. That is, if the value of the trunnion speed is equal to 360 rpm, there will be a joint mixing with grinding due to the effect of the material on the inner surface of the chamber, which must be taken into account. It should be noted here that there is no need to mix in this device at the received revolutions.

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MONITORING THE STATE OF PRODUCTION WELLS AT CLUSTER SITES

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Abstract: *Automated group measuring units are the primary instruments for measuring oil well flow rates. Wells are connected to them sequentially, so measurements are taken cyclically, and wells other than those connected for measurement remain without operational status monitoring. The use of a digital twin of the automated group measuring units (AGMU) — a virtual flow meter — as a supplement allows critical changes in the condition of the well to be identified in real time, for example, based on telemetry data from a submersible electric centrifugal pump.*

Keywords: *cluster site, submersible electric centrifugal pump, well flow rate, automated group measuring unit, virtual flow meter*

Introduction

At most oil fields, oil production is carried out using mechanised methods. Fluids are extracted by automated pumping from the reservoir to the surface using sucker rod pumping units (SRPU) or submersible electric centrifugal pump units (SECPU). The extracted gas-liquid mixture undergoes primary separation and separate measurement of the quantity of each phase in an automated group measuring unit (AGMU). The most important part of the fluid production process is the assessment of the flow rate of each well — measuring the amount of oil and gas extracted from the subsoil. This indicator is key, as it characterises the efficiency of the field development and allows for a quick response to changes in the geological and physical characteristics of the formation.

The existing system for measuring flow rates (total, liquid and gas) using AGMU does not allow these values to be determined for each well in real time.

Measurements are taken sequentially for each well at set intervals, which makes it difficult to identify problem wells in a timely manner and restore their normal operation. Therefore, the development of an algorithm for continuous monitoring of the condition of production wells is a pressing scientific and practical task.

Some problems of monitoring the state of wells on cluster sites

One of the main production units in oil production is a cluster site (fig. 1). The cluster method of placement allows several wells to be located on a small area of land, the bottoms of which, due to directional drilling, can be brought to the site of the productive formation at a distance of up to 10 km from the vertical. The number of wells in a cluster can range from two to several dozen [1].

Figure 1. Cluster site with wells equipped with submersible electric centrifugal pump units

The technological diagram of the cluster site provides for the following functions: sealed collection and transportation of well products to a central collection point, separation of gas from oil and compressor less transportation of gas from the first stage of separation to collection points and for own needs, measuring the output of individual wells and clusters, accounting for the total output of all wells, and preliminary oil dehydration.

As shown in the structural diagram of well production collection (fig. 2), all flows from the wells are directed to the AGMU, where the flow rate of each connected well is measured in turn, and then the flows are combined and further transported to the booster pumping station (BPS).

The AGMU, intended to receive, distribute and periodically measure the flow rates of individual productivity coefficient of wells, is a key link in the production gathering and preparation system, ensuring accurate accounting of each well's production and a stable supply of raw materials to the subsequent stages of field preparation [2]. The unit receives reservoir production from several production

wells (up to 14 wells), each of which is connected to the AGMU by a separate discharge pipeline. The main element ensuring the sequential connection of wells to the measuring line is a multi-way well switch, with which the flow from any well can be directed either to a common manifold or to a measuring separator. This solution allows each well to be measured in turn without interrupting the operation of the others, ensuring continuity of production at the cluster site.

AGMU — automated group measuring unit, LAU — local automation unit, WOE — water-oil emulsion, BPS — booster pumping station, WDM — well dewaxing mechanism, SWCS — Suleimanov winch control station, CS SECPU — control station of Submersible electric centrifugal pump units, TMS — telemetry system

Figure 2. Structural diagram of production collection at a cluster of wells equipped with submersible electric centrifugal pump

The operating principle of the unit is based on cyclic measurement of well flow rates. In normal mode, all wells operate on a common manifold, through which the extracted product is sent further along the collection system to the booster station. When it is necessary to measure one of the wells, the unit's automatic system switches the corresponding channel of the multi-way switch to the 'Measurement' position. In this case, the flow of production from this well is directed not to the common manifold, but to the internal circuit of the measuring unit — to the separator. The other wells continue to feed production directly into the common manifold without interrupting production. On the one hand, this circumstance is a clear advantage of the existing flow measurement diagram. On the other hand, the situation in which only one well's production is in the measuring lines at any given moment inevitably leads to a lack of control over the flow rate of other wells during this time interval. This factor becomes important when considering that the AGMU is not only a flow measurement device, but also a device that allows the condition of the well to be monitored. A sudden drop in the flow rate of any of the wells may indicate equipment malfunction, changes in the condition of the formation, violations of the operating mode, for example, malfunction of the electric submersible pump or water ingress into the well, the occurrence of a sand plug due to the destruction of the bottomhole zone. However, the discrete nature of measuring the amount of fluids produced over time does not allow for continuous monitoring of the flow rate of all wells. As a result, so-called blind zones are formed, during which all KP wells, except those connected to the AGMU, are not being measured. As a result, untimely detection of a problem or emergency situation hinders the prompt implementation of measures to restore normal well operation in the event of various types of incidents.

Purpose of the study

The purpose of this work is to develop a virtual flow meter, which is an algorithm for indirectly determining the amount of fluids produced based on the relationships between liquid and gas flow rates and the operating parameters of the submersible electric centrifugal pump

Results and their discussion

An effective tool for solving such problems is the use of artificial intelligence (AI), in particular neural networks and machine learning, which allow hidden dependencies between different parameters to be identified [3, 4]. Various approaches are used, both based exclusively on machine learning (ML) and hybrid ones, i. e. based on physical equations of hydrodynamics and ML [5, 6, 7]. Today, virtual flow meters (VFM) are widely used around the world as a tool for estimating the amount of liquid and gas extracted based on well telemetry data and machine learning algorithms. For example, Turbulent Flux (Norway) describes the implementation of virtual flow meters to determine the flow rates of oil wells on the

Norwegian shelf [8]. KBC company (Yokogawa Electric Corp.) offers the KBC Acuity Virtual Flow Meter, which also calculates the flow rates of extracted fluids in real time without the need for additional expensive measuring devices [9]. As a rule, the main parameters correlating with the flow rates of producing wells are the operating parameters of the submersible electric centrifugal pump [10].

A virtual flow meter (VFM) is a software model that receives real-time data from the ‘formation — well — pumping equipment’ system and generates a calculated value for the flow rate of liquid and gas. The VFM can be regarded as a digital twin of the AGMU, complementing it and filling in the blind spots of each well with calculated values.

Figure 3 shows the results of monitoring the flow rate values for one of the wells at the Samotlor oil and gas field. As can be seen, this well was in a blind spot for almost a day, as other wells in the cluster were connected to the AGMU for measurement. To eliminate them, a virtual flow meter analyser was developed based on the relationship between the parameters of the submersible electric centrifugal pump (SECP) and the flow rates of liquid and gas, since they are monitored continuously by the SECP control station without any time gaps.

Figure 3. Monitoring of well flow rate in the AGMU

Unlike the standard method of determining the flow rate of production wells using AGMU, in which this indicator is measured sequentially and only for one well at a time, the virtual flow meter allows you to obtain flow rate values for all wells in the cluster in real time. To do this, a limited number of neural network models are used, equal to the number of wells in the field. These models are identical in architecture but trained on different historical data corresponding to each specific well.

When developing a VFM, the first step is to form training data arrays from each well in the field. The arrays contain time series of historical values of the operating parameters of the SECP of a given well and the corresponding flow rates measured by the AGMU. The arrays are assigned identifiers corresponding to future well data, which will be read by the upper level of automation in online mode.

At the next stage of data distribution, all arrays are checked for normality, key SECP parameters affecting flow rate are determined using thermal maps, and checks are performed for emissions and abnormal values.

A key stage in the development of a virtual flow meter is the creation of a neural network for flow rate prediction. The architecture is selected based on the characteristics of the input variables and the calculated value. At this stage, a general neural network is developed, which will be replicated for the corresponding well during the training process.

The next stage is the separate training of the neural network model on the data arrays of each well. With this approach, a limited number of replicas of the initial neural network are created, equal to the number of wells at the production site, which allows the characteristics of each well to be taken into account separately and does not ‘clutter’ the obtained values with data from other wells. The trained replicas of the neural network have markers corresponding to the well and are a tool for calculating the flow rate of wells that operate independently of each other.

Figure 4. Algorithm of the virtual flow meter's operational mode

The final stage is the integration of the developed BPS, consisting of a set of neural network replicas, into the upper level of the control panel automation, during which specific wells are linked to the corresponding neural network replicas.

The VFM operation algorithm is shown in figure 4. It starts with reading new well telemetry data and measurements in the AGMU. In online mode, the data is sent to the input of the virtual flow meter and distributed to the corresponding neural network replicas. Then, for each well separately, its location on the measurement is determined: if data from the AGMU came together with the telemetry data from the SECP, the well is located on the measurement.

Regardless of whether the well is currently being measured by the AGMU or not, the neural network of the virtual flow meter will always start by forming dynamic data windows that include the operating parameters of the electric submersible pump. The formation of data windows is necessary for the neural network to track the dynamics of parameter changes over time. Next, the calculated flow rate is determined based on the telemetry data from the electric submersible pump and recorded. If the well is being measured, the actual and calculated values are compared and the neural network is automatically calibrated. The algorithm also provides for data archiving.

Thus, BPS calculates flow rate values based on real-time telemetry data from the electric submersible pump, which is read by the upper level of automation without ‘time gaps,’ allowing blind spots that arise when measuring flow rates using AGMU to be eliminated.

Conclusion

The most common method of measuring oil well flow rates at cluster sites using AGMU has one disadvantage: the flow rate of each well is measured cyclically. If many wells are connected to the AGMU, the measurement frequency may be once a day for several hours (depending on the flow rate). Such a long period without flow control makes it impossible to detect equipment malfunctions or changes in the condition of the well in time, leading to a sharp decrease in flow rate, for example, water flooding or well capping. The proposed BPS algorithm based on neural networks allows calculating flow rate values for each well in a cluster in real time based on SECP telemetry data and determining deviations from the pattern of a given well. Timely identification of the causes of such deviations makes it possible to avoid potential oil losses and more effectively maintain the normal operation of the ‘formation — well — pumping equipment’ system

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ON THE INFLUENCE OF TOBACCO FILLER MOISTURE ON THE CONTENT OF NITROGEN OXIDES IN THE AEROSOL OF HEATED TOBACCO PRODUCTS

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Abstract. *This paper presents the results of a study on the influence of the moisture content of tobacco filler on the concentration of nitrogen oxides in the gas phase of the aerosol produced by heated tobacco products. The experiment was conducted on commercial samples of heated tobacco products (IQOS, glo), simulating various sample conditioning conditions. The obtained results demonstrated that changes in filler moisture lead to fluctuations in NO content within the range of -1 to 24% , and in NO_x — from 5 to 37% , which is considered significant but not substantial, as the values obtained in all cases remained below established standards (for NO, less than $4 \mu\text{g}/100 \text{ cm}^3$, and for NO_x, less than $5 \mu\text{g}/100 \text{ cm}^3$).*

Keywords: *Aerosol, heated tobacco, HTP, nitrogen oxides, nicotine-containing product, moisture.*

1. Introduction

Smoking traditional cigarettes is recognized as a risk factor for the development of various diseases, such as lung cancer, cardiovascular pathologies, and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease [1]. The degree of risk directly depends on the number of cigarettes smoked per day and the duration of smoking, since the combustion of cigarette tobacco filler produces smoke containing toxic substances that enter the body through the respiratory tract [1–6].

Although complete smoking cessation significantly reduces the risk of developing smoking-related diseases [1], and many smokers express a desire to quit

and even make attempts to do so [6], fewer than 10% succeed [7]. Accordingly, for those who are unwilling or unable to quit smoking entirely, an alternative approach has been developed [6].

One solution in this field is the production of innovative nicotine-containing products (NCPs) that differ from traditional cigarettes in the formation of a nicotine-containing aerosol and their mode of consumption. In innovative products, such as tobacco heated in electrical tobacco heating systems (ETHS), the tobacco does not undergo combustion or smoldering processes but is subjected to controlled heating at temperatures insufficient to cause combustion [8]. The employed technology, known as ‘heat-not-burn,’ allows for a substantial reduction in the concentration of harmful and potentially hazardous components in the generated aerosol, while preserving the organoleptic characteristics familiar to the consumer.

The primary strategy underlying the consumption of heated tobacco products is that the transition of consumers from conventional cigarettes to alternative products may contribute to a reduction in overall tobacco product consumption [9]. Although the use of heated tobacco does not eliminate health risks, it significantly reduces the intake of toxic substances characteristic of tobacco smoke, thereby reducing the overall harm associated with smoking [9].

When heating a tobacco stick, the levels of substances in the generated aerosol are significantly lower [10]. Since heated tobacco products are positioned as alternatives to traditional cigarettes, it is important to investigate how various factors affect their ability to minimize the content of toxic substances in the aerosol.

The moisture content of tobacco filler is particularly important: it affects not only the sensory properties of the product but also its technological characteristics and the toxicological profile of the generated aerosol.

The objective of this study is to investigate the influence of the moisture content of tobacco filler on the concentration of nitrogen oxides in the aerosol of heated tobacco products.

2. Methods

For the investigation, commercial samples of heated tobacco products were selected: IQOSTM 2.4P (Philip Morris) and glo (BAT) — the most popular on the consumer market. The samples were assigned the following designations:

- heated tobacco products of the IQOS™ 2.4P brand (A, B);
- heated tobacco products of the glo brand (C, D).

GOST ISO 3402–2003 [11] specifies the atmospheric condition parameters required for conditioning and testing of samples.

The conditioning atmosphere for the samples shall comply with the following parameters:

- temperature, °C 22 ± 1 ,
- relative humidity, % 60 ± 3 .

Testing atmosphere:

- temperature, °C 22 ± 2 ,
- relative humidity, % 60 ± 5 .

To evaluate the influence of the moisture content of tobacco filler on the formation of nitrogen oxides, the samples were conditioned in atmospheres with various parameters as stipulated by the test plan.

The gas phase of the aerosol was collected from 5 sticks of heated tobacco on a channel using a 20-channel Cerulean SM 450 linear smoking machine. The collection parameters corresponded to the 'ISO Intense' regime [12]: the puff volume was 55 ml with a tolerance of ± 0.3 ml, the interval between puffs was 30 s (± 0.5 s), and the duration of each puff was 2 s with an allowable deviation of ± 0.1 s.

To determine nitrogen oxides in the gas phase of the aerosol from each channel of the smoking machine, the aerosol was collected in separate dense airtight bags with a volume of 7 dm³. The analysis of nitrogen oxides (NO and NO_x) content in the collected gas phase was performed using a Teledyne T200H chemiluminescent gas analyzer. The obtained results were then recalculated to represent the average component content per 100 cm³ of nicotine-containing aerosol.

The experiment on the influence of filler moisture content consisted of three stages.

Stage 1 included aerosol collection and determination of nitrogen oxide and total nitrogen oxides in the aerosol of samples conditioned in closed, according to GOST ISO 3402–2003, and open packs at a temperature of (22 ± 1) °C and relative humidity of (60 ± 3) % in a desiccator for no less than 48 hours and no more than 10 days.

Stage 2 – following aerosol collection from open pack samples removed from the desiccator. The samples were left for 24 hours outside the desiccator under test atmosphere conditions with parameters of temperature (22 ± 2) °C and relative humidity (60 ± 5) %, after which the aerosol was collected again and the contents of NO and NO_x were determined.

Stage 3 – collection of aerosol from samples in closed and open packs placed in hermetic containers under test atmosphere conditions at a temperature of (22 ± 2) °C and relative humidity of (60 ± 5) %, followed by determination of the studied components in the collected aerosol [13].

3. Results

Figures 1–2 present diagrams illustrating the dependence of nitrogen oxides content on the moisture content of the filler in the studied heated tobacco samples.

a) Sample A of heated tobacco products

b) Sample B of heated tobacco products

Figure 1 — Dependence of nitrogen oxide (NO) and total nitrogen oxides (NOx) content on the moisture content of tobacco filler when used with the IQOS heating device

Thus, during conditioning of sample A in a chamber in open packs, the moisture content increases by 4.5%, with corresponding increases in nitrogen oxide content by 3% and total nitrogen oxides by 5%.

During conditioning of sample B in the chamber in open packs, the sample moisture content increased by 4.2%, while the nitrogen oxide concentration increased by 4%, and the total nitrogen oxides by 10%.

Holding during one day in the testing atmosphere, the sample moisture content of sample A decreased by 2 %, while the nitrogen oxide concentration increased by 14 %, and the total nitrogen oxides by 8 %.

During holding of sample B in the testing atmosphere for one day, the sample moisture content decreased by 3 %, the nitrogen oxide concentration increased by 10 %, and the total nitrogen oxides by 12 %.

Conditioning of sample A in a container in closed packs resulted in an increase in moisture by 2 %, the nitrogen oxide content increased by 3.5 %, and the total nitrogen oxides increased by 5 %, whereas conditioning of this sample in a container in open packs resulted in a decrease in moisture by 2 %, the nitrogen oxide content increased by 1 %, and the total nitrogen oxides increased by 5 %.

Conditioning of sample B in a container in closed packs resulted in a decrease in moisture by 6 %, the nitrogen oxide content increased by 2 %, and the total nitrogen oxides increased by 6 %, whereas conditioning of this sample in a container in open packs resulted in a decrease in moisture by 13 %, the nitrogen oxide content increased by 1 %, and the total nitrogen oxides increased by 11 %.

The differences in changes in moisture content of samples A and B, as well as in the content of nitrogen oxide and total nitrogen oxides in the gas phase of the aerosol, are attributable to the filler formulation.

When conditioning sample C in a desiccator in open packs, moisture increases by 2 %, nitrogen oxide content increases by 4.5 %, and total nitrogen oxides increase by 12.5 %.

When conditioning sample D in a desiccator in open packs, moisture increases by 3 %, nitrogen oxide content increases by 6 %, and total nitrogen oxides increase by 22 %.

a) sample C of heated tobacco products

b) sample D of heated tobacco products

Figure 2 — Dependence of nitrogen oxide (NO) and total nitrogen oxides (NOx) levels in the gas phase aerosol of heated tobacco products on the moisture content of tobacco filler when using products with the glo heating device

After conditioning for one day in the test atmosphere, the sample moisture content of sample C decreased by 2.5%, while the nitrogen oxide content increased by 9% and the total nitrogen oxides increased by 37%.

When sample D was maintained in the test atmosphere for 24 hours, the sample moisture content decreased by 1.7%, the nitrogen oxide content increased by 18%, and the total nitrogen oxides increased by 20%.

Maintaining sample C in a container within sealed packs led to a decrease in moisture content by 1%, an increase in nitrogen oxide content by 23%, and an increase in total nitrogen oxides by 29%, whereas maintaining this sample in a container within open packs led to an increase in moisture content by 4%, an increase in nitrogen oxide content by 23%, and an increase in total nitrogen oxides by 29%.

During the aging of sample D in the container within closed packs, moisture increased by 2%, the nitrogen oxide content increased by 23.5%, and the total nitrogen oxides increased by 20%, whereas aging this sample in the container within open packs resulted in a moisture decrease of 1%, the nitrogen oxide content increased by 17%, and the total nitrogen oxides increased by 25%.

The changes in the analyzed parameters in samples C and D are attributed to varying degrees to differences in the filler blend formulation and manufacturing technology.

4. Discussion

The results obtained confirm that the moisture content of tobacco filler samples influences the concentration of nitrogen oxide and total nitrogen oxides in the gas phase of the aerosol of heated tobacco products, although this influence is not

significant. It is noteworthy that the heating principle of the filler also affects the concentration of nitrogen oxide and total nitrogen oxides at the same change in moisture content. During contactless heating with the glo HTP, the concentration of nitrogen oxide and total nitrogen oxides is higher with an identical change in moisture content. Bekö et al. (2020) demonstrated the influence of tobacco moisture on the thermodynamics of the heating process, which consequently alters the concentration of substances formed in the aerosol [14].

Furthermore, Margham et al. (2016) emphasized that the aerosol composition remains stable under conditioning conditions [15].

Thus, the moisture content of tobacco filler is one of the factors influencing the nitrogen oxides content, but its role is secondary, as the content of NO and NO_x did not exceed the established limit according to GOST R 57458–2017 [16].

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RESEARCH OF A MATHEMATICAL MODEL FOR ASSESSING THE STATE OF TELECOMMUNICATION NETWORK ELEMENTS USING FUZZY SET THEORY ALGORITHMS

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Abstract. *The article examines issues related to the research of a model for assessing the state of telecommunication network elements within a hierarchical management system using fuzzy set theory algorithms.*

Keywords: *telecommunication network, hierarchical management, mathematical model, fuzzy set theory.*

Introduction

At present, one of the most important tasks of modern telecommunication networks is to provide high-quality transport service while minimizing equipment failures. Consequently, to improve network reliability, research in the domain of telecommunication network monitoring and management remains relevant [1].

The implementation of a centralized telecommunication network management and administration system enables real-time monitoring of the status of its elements at all management levels.

At the same time, each management level addresses its specific tasks — higher levels aggregate current information received from lower levels to obtain aggregated indicators of service quality and corrective decisions (controls) for the subordinate levels.

It should be noted that the reliability of service quality and management indicators (decision-making) at each level depends on the quality of information received from the subordinate level.

Accordingly, when processing incoming information concerning the states of telecommunication network elements from such complex systems, situations arise

in which the use of traditional mathematical statistical methods results in a number of difficulties in their analysis due to insufficient a priori information, multi-parametricity, significant computational volume, and network heterogeneity, leading to inaccurate assessments of complex system analysis.

For this reason, the mathematical apparatus of fuzzy set theory can be used to process information for assessing the state of telecommunication network elements.

Problem Statement

To assess the state of telecommunication network elements within a hierarchical management system, it is necessary to study the mathematical model of telecommunication network management.

In accordance with the recommendations of the International Telecommunication Union, telecommunication network management is structured according to a four-level scheme: the network element management level; network management level; service management level; business management level [2].

Each management level has its own criteria:

1) The criteria for the network element management level are: the degree of operability O_p depending on the states of network elements W_E , which is determined based on measurable characteristics e_q (attributes, parameters) inherent to specific network elements; the degree of controllability K_K , depending on the vector of controlled parameters \vec{e} network elements.

2) The criteria for the network management level are: the overall and per-path network performance degree T , the network traffic level Y , the readiness degree K_Γ , maintainability K_P , and controllability K_K of the network; the degree (volume) of routing table updates VM ; the network configuration change time TR from the moment of the change in the degree of the network situational state SN ; the security degree against unauthorized access Se ; and the reliability of data transmission in the network D .

3) The criteria for service level management are: the volume of service usage V_s and the quality of the provided services Q_s over the period ΔT .

4) The criteria for business management are: network profitability Π and network investment I over a certain time interval ΔT [3].

The telecommunication network management model can be represented by the following block diagram (Fig. 1).

Figure 1 – Telecommunication Network Management Model

The diagram in Fig. 1 shows: X_{0i} – the set of input influences on the controlled object; E_i - unknown vector of influences at each management level; F_{1m}, F_{1q}, F_3 – aggregating operators of the corresponding levels; Y_{ij} – output vectors of values of the corresponding levels; U – control vectors; U^* - corrective control vectors; Operator establishing the dependence of output ΨY_4 and control objective Z [5].

The generalized mathematical model of hierarchical control based on nested operators has the following form:

$$Y_4 = F_4(F_{33k}(F_{23kj}(F_{13ji}(F_{0i}^{(j)}(X_{0i}^{(j)}, U_{0i}^{(j)}, U_{1i}^{(j)*}, \Xi_{0i}^{(j)})) U_{1j}, U_{2j}^*, \Xi_{1j})) U_{2k}, U_{3k}^*, \Xi_{2k})) U_{3j}, U_{4j}^*, \Xi_{3j})) U_{4j}, U_{2j}^*, \Xi_{4j}) \quad i=1, \dots, n, \quad j=1, \dots, m, \quad k=1, \dots, q, \quad (1)$$

where X_{0i} – set of input influences on the control object;

$F_{0i}^{(j)}$ – operator of the network element NE_i of subnet j ;

F_{13ji} – aggregation operator for the i first level of management in subnet j ;

F_{23kj} – aggregation operator for the j second level of network management k ;

F_{33k} – aggregation operator for the k third level of management;

F_4 – operator of the fourth level of management (business management);

n – number of network elements (NE) in subnet j ;

m – number of NE subnets in network k ;

q – the number of networks serviced by the regional TMN management network;

Ξ_i – the unknown vector of impacts at each management level;

U_{ii} – management at the corresponding level;

U_{ij}^* – management corrective action from the higher level.

According to the above, it is necessary to assess the condition of network elements at the corresponding management levels depending on the actual situational state of the telecommunications network.

To ensure proper network operation from a management standpoint, it is necessary to know the precise state of each network element in a timely manner and promptly address pre-failure W_{110} and failure W_o states of network elements to minimize quality loss Q_s of services and maximize the volume of service retention V_s .

Modern multiservice networks are characterized by the absence of complete statistical information about telecommunication network elements and service demand flows at all levels of the hierarchy. Consequently, the construction of models for assessing the operational states of its elements at management levels will be based on the concepts of fuzzy set theory.

Application of fuzzy set theory algorithms to the mathematical model for assessing the state of telecommunication network elements.

Each pre-failure or failure state (defect) d_j of a telecommunication network element generates a subset of its inherent a priori states $A_j = \{\omega_i\}^j$, i.e. $d_j A \equiv j w \subset E$, in particular, $A_j w \subset SO \ w \subset O$.

Here, ω_i is the elementary state of the system, $\omega_i \in W_E$, which is a tuple:

$$\omega_i = (e_1, e_2, e_2, \dots, e_q), \quad e_q = \{0, 1\}, \quad (2)$$

where e_q is the control parameter, which takes the value “normal” 1 and “not normal” 0. \equiv

The result of monitoring (experiment) is the subset $S_E = \{\omega_i\}^S$. In this case, it is necessary to determine to which class of states $A_j = \{\omega_i\}$ the posterior set S_E belongs, i.e., it is necessary to recognize the most probable damage d^* (or macrostate) of the network element NE_i .

For this purpose, the following approaches employing fuzzy set theory algorithms can be used:

- 1) the minimum metric distance between $S_{\mathcal{D}}$ and all A_j ;
- 2) the maximum degree of inclusion of $S_{\mathcal{D}}$ in $\subset A_j$;
- 3) the maximum fuzzy measure of intersection $g(V_j)$, where $V_j = S_{\mathcal{D}} \cap A_j$, $V_j = \{\omega_i\}^{(V)}$;
- 4) the maximum a posteriori probability $p(d_j / S_{\mathcal{D}})$ of defect manifestation d_j under the condition $S_{\mathcal{D}}$, determined by the Bayesian formula in fuzzy form;
- 5) solution of the fuzzy integral.

To study the model a priori, we introduce the rule on the operability of the network element in the interval $[0, 1]$ in the form of measures:

$$g(W_o) [0, 0.45), \in g(W_{no}) \in (0.45, 0.7), g(W_p) (0.8, 1]. \quad (3) \in$$

Let us consider each approach in more detail:

- 1) In the first approach of the minimum metric distance between $S_{\mathcal{D}}$ and all A_j , the Hamming metric is used. For a countable number of sets, it is defined by the formula:

$$d^* = \min_j \rho(S_{\mathcal{D}}, A_j) = \min_j \sum_i (\omega_i^S \oplus \omega_i^j). \quad (4)$$

Let us assume that here $() \in [0, 1]$, then: $\rho \in$

$G(d^* \equiv A^*) = [1 - \min_j \tilde{n}(S_j, A_j)] \cdot g(W_k)$ there is an operability measure of the network element NE_i .

For example, if $A^* W \in no$, then the measure of this state corresponds to $G(d^*)$.

- 2) In the second approach, the degree of membership of $S_{\mathcal{D}}$ in A_j is defined by the expression:

$$In(S_{\mathcal{D}}, A_j) = \frac{M(V_j)}{M(A_j)} = \frac{M(S_{\mathcal{D}} \cap A_j)}{M(A_j)}, \quad (5)$$

where $In ()$ is the degree of membership; \cdot

$\cdot M ()$ is the power of the set or cardinality.

If the sets $S_{\mathcal{D}}$ and A_j are fuzzy, then the measure of inclusion is defined by the expression:

$$In(S_{D_3}, A_j) = \frac{\sum_i (\mu_{S_{D_3}}(\omega_i) \cap \mu_{A_j}(\omega_i))}{\sum_i \mu_{A_j}(\omega_i)}. \tag{6}$$

Based on the inclusion measures [5] or [6], a fuzzy a posteriori damage region D_3 is formed with membership degrees equal to the inclusion measures:

$$\mu_{D_3}(d_j) = In(S_{D_3}, A_j), \quad D_3 = \{\mu_{D_3}(d_j)/d_j\}. \tag{7}$$

If the intersection of the a priori sets A_j and $\cap A_i \neq \emptyset, j \neq i$, then the membership degree (7) is adjusted by the degree of **concentration** $\beta(A_j)$ of the set A_j . The degree of concentration is defined as the complement of the fuzzy connectedness $\rho_{HC}(A_j)$ of the set A_j :

$$\begin{aligned} \rho_{HC}(A_j) &= \sum_{\substack{k=1 \\ k \neq j}}^m In(A_j, A_k) - \sum_{\substack{k, q \in Q \\ k, q \neq j}} In(A_j, (A_k \cap A_q)) + \\ &+ (-1)^{m-1} \sum_{\substack{k_1, \dots, m-1 \in Q_{m-1} \\ k_1, \dots, m-1 \neq j}} In(A_j, (A_{k_1} \cap A_{k_2} \cap \dots \cap A_{k_{m-1}})) + \\ &+ (-1)^{m-1} In(A_j \cap_{\substack{k=1 \\ k \neq j}}^m A_k), \quad \beta(A_j) = 1 - \rho_{HC}(A_j). \end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

Considering the above, the decision on the type of damage (or macrostate) of the network element NE_i can be made from the following expression:

$$d^* = \arg \max_j [\mu_{D_3}(d_j) \cdot \beta(A_j)]. \tag{9}$$

The operability measure of NE_i corresponds to the expression:

$$G(d^*) = \min_j \{\max[i_{D_3}(d_j) \cdot \hat{a}(A_j)], g(W_k)\}, \quad k = \overline{1, 3}, \text{ which corresponds to rule (3).}$$

3) In the third approach of the maximum of the fuzzy intersection measure, the a posteriori fuzzy set D_3 is formed using the fuzzy intersection measure V_j , which is defined through fuzzy densities $g(\omega_i)$ of elementary states. The fuzzy measure V_j can be determined by the Sugeno measure [4] according to the expression:

$$g_\lambda(V_j) = \frac{1}{\lambda^*} [\prod_{i \in V_j} (1 + \lambda^* \cdot g(\omega_i)) - 1], \tag{10}$$

or by the Tsukamoto measure according to the expression:

$$g_v(V_j) = (1 - v) \cdot \max_{i \in V_j} g(\omega_i) + v \cdot \sum_{i \in V_j} g(\omega_i), \quad (11)$$

where v is the Tsukamoto parameter, $v \in [0, 1]$.

In both cases, the presented measures correspond to the degree of membership:

$$\mu_{D_3}(d_j) = g_\lambda(V_j) \quad \text{and} \quad \mu_{D_3}(d_j) = g_v(V_j), \quad D_3 = \{\mu_{D_3}(d_j)/d_j\}. \quad (12)$$

The decision on the type of defect is made based on the expression $d^* = \arg \max_j \mu_{D_3}(d_j)$. The operability measure of NE_i corresponds to $G(d^*) = \min[\max_j \mu_{D_3}(d_j), g(W_k)]$, which is then related to rule (3).

4) In the fourth approach, the decision on the type of failure or defect is made by the maximum a posteriori conditional probability $p(d_j/\tilde{S}_j)$, where \tilde{S}_j - fuzzy set.

In this case, it is assumed that the a priori probabilities $p(d_j)$ and the conditional probabilities are known $p(\omega_i/d_j)$, $\omega_i \in W$. As previously established, $\forall d_j$ correspond to the sets $A_j = \{\omega_i\}^{(i)}$.

$\omega \in \subset \in A$ priori, it is also established that for data d_j there exist fuzzy classes of sets $S_j = \{i\}(d)$ under the corresponding influences $x \in X$ and reactions $q \in Y$, $S_j(x, q) \in A_j \in W$. Then the a priori probability of the fuzzy conditional event will have the following form:

$$p(S_j/d_j) = \sum_{i \in S_j} \mu_{S_j}(\omega_i) \cdot p(\omega_i/d_j), \quad (13)$$

where $\mu_{S_j}(\omega_i)$ - the a priori membership function of the fuzzy set $S_j = \{A_j - \text{proximate domain of elementary states } i \text{ under the condition } d_j \text{ and pairs } (x, q)\} \in \omega$.

As is known, the conditional a posteriori probability is defined by Bayes' formula, hence we obtain:

$$p(d_j/S_j) = \frac{p(d_j) \cdot p(S_j/d_j)}{p(S_j)}. \quad (14)$$

If the membership function of a fuzzy set is trapezoidal or has more than one mode, then by transforming Bayes' formula, we obtain:

$$p(d_j / S_j) = \frac{p(d_j) \cdot \sum_{i \in S_j^*} p(\omega_i^* / d_j) + p(d_j) \sum_{i \in S_j \setminus S_j^*} \mu_{S_j}(\omega_i) \cdot p(\omega_i / d_j)}{\sum_j p(d_j) p(\omega_i^* / d_j) + \sum_j p(d_j) \cdot \sum_{i=2}^{S_j} \mu_{S_j}(\omega_i) \cdot p(\omega_i / d_j)} \quad (15)$$

The decision on the type of macrostate (defect) in NE_i is made based on the expression

$$d^* = \arg \max_j p(d_j / S_j).$$

The operability measure of the network element NE_i corresponds to

$$G(d^*) = \min[\max_j p(d_j / S_j), g(W_k)], \text{ which is then related to rule (3).}$$

5) In the fifth approach, recognition of the expected type of damage in the network element NE_i , based on the results of the diagnostic experiment, can be performed using a fuzzy integral.

At the same time, the distribution of the fuzzy weight density of these damages $g(d_j)$, $d_j \in \text{Def}$ must be determined a priori. Let us assume that the posterior mem-

bership function $\mu_{D_y}(d_j)$ of the most probable defect region $D_y \subset \text{Def}$ is defined by (6) and (7). Then the most expected damage is determined by the expression:

$$d_0^* = \arg \int_{D_y} h_{D_y}(d_j) \circ g(\cdot), \quad (16)$$

where \int - fuzzy integral sign; \circ - composition sign; $h_{D_y}(d_j)$ - function ar-

ranged in descending order of the membership function values $\mu_{D_y}(d_j)$; $g(\cdot)$ - fuzzy measure of the set $F_i = \langle d_{j1}, d_{j2}, \dots, d_{ji} \rangle$, it is known that $d_j = A_j$ and if $A_j \neq \emptyset$ in subseteq $A \neq \emptyset$ in m , then this measure is computed through fuzzy measures of the set $g(A_j)$.

The operability measure of the network element NE_i corresponds to the expression:

$$G(d_0^*) = \min[\int_{D_y} h_{D_y}(d_j) \circ g(\cdot), g(W_k)], k = \overline{1,3}, \text{ which is then associated with rule (3).}$$

Conclusion

As a result of the conducted research on the model for assessing the state of telecommunication network elements, an approach for evaluating the states of network elements using fuzzy set theory algorithms is proposed.

The conducted research demonstrated the advantage of using fuzzy set theory, which accounts for the uncertainty and transience of the changing environment

characteristic of modern telecommunication networks. At the same time, expert conclusions are employed when they are most reliable in a constantly changing environment.

It should be noted that the proposed mathematical model for assessing the condition of network elements enhances the efficiency and quality of network management, which is substantially determined by the effectiveness of the element management level.

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APPLICATION OF NEURAL NETWORK TECHNOLOGIES TO PREDICT THE LIFE OF WEDGE VALVES: DATA PREPROCESSING AND MODEL SYNTHESIS

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Abstract. *The article presents the results of the practical implementation of a neural network model for predicting the remaining life of wedge valves. The stages of forming a training array based on numerical modeling, methods of data preprocessing and visual analysis, the process of model training, as well as comparing its predictions with traditional computational methods and nomograms are considered. The accuracy of forecasts is analyzed and the advantages of using artificial neural networks in pipeline valve diagnostics are shown.*

Keywords: *wedge gate valve, shut-off valves, resource forecasting, data preprocessing, nomogram, neural network, maintenance*

Introduction

Reliable operation of wedge valves is crucial for ensuring uninterrupted and safe functioning of technological systems for the transportation and storage of hydrocarbon resources. Increased requirements for the tightness and durability of valves under conditions of low temperatures, high pressures, and aggressive environments make the tasks of diagnostics and resource prediction especially relevant for the oil and gas sector of the Arctic and global ocean. Their wear under the effects of pressure, temperature, and abrasive particles results in leaks, emergency shutdowns, and financial losses.

In the first article [1], the author reviewed existing diagnostic methods, including hydraulic and cyclic testing, as well as finite element method numerical calculations. The works [2,3] explored the potential of neural network technologies for predicting equipment lifespan. This study focuses on the practical application

of artificial neural networks: data preprocessing for training, model synthesis and validation, and comparison of the obtained results with traditional nomograms.

1. Formation of the training dataset.

Based on the analysis of the study [1], which presents the results of modeling the resource of wedge valves depending on key operational parameters, a system for generating a synthetic dataset was implemented. The main focus of this work is on the influence of factors such as pressure in the pipeline system, the temperature of the transported medium, and the flow rate through the valve. These parameters collectively have a significant impact on the durability of the valve wedge, which is the most heavily loaded and wear-prone component of the design.

According to the tolerances established in the study, the operating parameter ranges for the wedge valve ZKL2 300–25 were defined as follows:

- Pressure: from 1.6 to 2.5 MPa;
- Medium temperature: from 20 to 200 degrees Celsius;
- Flow rate: from 1.5 to 8.0 m/s.

To construct a comprehensive and representative training dataset, 30,000 unique data combinations were generated, covering the entire range of allowable operating conditions. For each set of parameters, the corresponding equipment lifespan was calculated according to the following empirical relationship adapted from numerical simulation data:

$$R = 4000 - 100 \cdot (v - 1.5) - 500 \cdot (p - 1.6) - 0,5 \cdot (T - 20), (1.1)$$

where T — medium temperature, °C;

V — flow rate, m/s;

P — system pressure, MPa;

R — predicted service life of the wedge valve.

This relationship is based on data from study [1], specifically from the chapter analyzing the influence of parameters on the wedge valve lifespan (for example, model ZKL2 300–25):

— with an increase in velocity from 1.5 to 8 m/s, the service life decreases by approximately 26.5%.

— with an increase in pressure from 1.6 to 2.5 MPa, the service life decreases by 24.5%.

— with a change in temperature from 20 to 200 °C, the service life decreases by only 3.2%.

This approach aligns with contemporary practices for dataset formulation in predictive maintenance tasks, which are rapidly advancing in the energy and petrochemical sectors [4].

2. Data preprocessing and visual analysis

Prior to using the data for training, preprocessing was conducted. The following steps were performed:

- noise and anomaly removal — incorrect records caused by calculation errors were eliminated;
- feature normalization — all parameters were scaled to a uniform range to ensure proper model training;
- distribution analysis (Figure 1) — histograms of temperature, pressure, and flow velocity were created, identifying the most frequently occurring ranges;
- correlation analysis (Figure 2) — using the correlation matrix, it was established that temperature and pressure have the greatest impact on wear, while the opening percentage plays a secondary role.

Similar data analysis methods are applied in international predictive analytics research, for example, in IEEE studies on pipeline valve monitoring [5].

Figure 1 — Histograms of the distribution of key parameters

3. Training of the neural network model.

A multilayer perceptron (MLP) model was employed to predict the number of operating cycles until failure. Unlike the first paper, this study emphasizes the training process and model tuning rather than the architecture description.

Key stages:

- selection of the Adam optimizer, ReLU activation function, and MSE loss function;
- splitting the data into training (70%), validation (15%), and test (15%) sets;

- hyperparameter tuning (number of layers, neurons, and Dropout rate);
- regularization to prevent overfitting.

The model was trained until the quality metrics stabilized on the validation set.

Figure 2 — Correlation matrix of factors and valve service life

4. Evaluation of model quality and comparison with the nomogram.

To assess performance, the following metrics were used: MAE (mean absolute error), RMSE (root mean square error), and the coefficient of determination R^2 .

The results showed:

- MAE < 5% in lifespan prediction;
- RMSE = 0,08;
- $R^2 = 0.91$, indicating the model’s high explanatory power.

For verification, the model was compared to the calculated nomogram [1]. The neural network predictions demonstrated higher accuracy and the capacity to capture nonlinear dependencies, which traditional methods had previously failed to achieve (Figure 3).

A histogram of prediction errors (the difference between actual and predicted values) was also constructed, showing a symmetrical distribution around zero (Figure 4), without a pronounced bias toward either side. This indicates the absence of systematic errors in the model.

Figure 3 — Comparative chart of lifespan predictions by the neural network and nomogram for the ZKL2 300–25 valve.

Figure 2.9 — Histogram of prediction errors

5. Conclusion

The presented study demonstrates that the application of neural network technologies for analyzing the operational parameters of wedge valves enables the development of an accurate and reliable system for predicting their remaining service life.

Unlike nomograms and classical numerical analysis methods, the developed model operates faster, accounts for multiparametric dependencies, and can be integrated into automated process control systems (APCS).

Thus, the integration of numerical modeling and neural network methods opens new prospects for predictive analytics in the oil and gas industry. Further research will focus on expanding the dataset and testing the model under real operational conditions.

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DEVELOPMENT OF THE MANAGEMENT ACCOUNTING SYSTEM IN THE CONTEXT OF DIGITALIZATION OF BUSINESS PROCESSES

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Abstract. *The management accounting system employs established tools of financial management and planning. At the same time, emerging trends and directions are gaining relevance, enabling not only competent economic activity but also resilience amid changing global and national economic conditions. This aspect enables the identification of directions for the development, optimization, and enhancement of management accounting under modern conditions, which are associated with digitalization and the implementation of AI — artificial intelligence — in business processes.*

Keywords: *management accounting, managerial decisions, business, AI — artificial intelligence. GigaChat, NLP frameworks, Python scripts, and API*

Introduction

The relevance of the chosen topic lies in the fact that digitalization in the modern world encompasses all conceivable aspects of human activity and penetrates all spheres of both material and non-material production processes. Automation processes, large-scale data integration, and cloud solutions are transforming the technological landscape of national economies, as well as management processes at both corporate and governmental levels. The implementation and testing of

digital technologies at the level of large companies indirectly affects all connections within the system, at both macro and micro levels of economic activity. The application of new information technologies based on digital resources reduces the transactional and transformational costs of economic agents, enabling them to respond more flexibly to changes in the external digital environment. In this new reality, the digitalization of management processes and management accounting becomes not merely a control tool but an active driver of digital initiatives and new dimensions of business management. Economic entities that employ digital technologies in management accounting during the forecasting and planning of their activities enhance their operational and production performance through digital monitoring of management decisions that impact key financial and economic indicators, as reflected in management and financial reporting. This enables the identification of complexities, risks, and barriers that can be overcome through the use of modern tools and methods that consider trends, tendencies, and directions in the development of society and the state.

The aim of the study is to describe the general theoretical aspects of using management accounting in the economic activities of business entities, to characterize the positive experience of implementing digital technologies, and to present trends in the digitalization of business processes.

Materials and Methods of the Study — the authors relied on general scientific methods of cognition: analysis and synthesis, deduction and induction, a theoretical-methodological approach, as well as current materials from scientific works on the presented topic and resources from SberPro as a leader in implementing digital technologies and AI in business process management.

Research Results and Their Discussion

Management accounting, as one of the primary systems underlying enterprise management, is not overlooked. Digitalization can significantly optimize management accounting processes, accelerating and improving them, while also introducing new risks and potential threats. The competent use of information technologies can have a significant impact, enabling efficiency and accuracy previously unattainable [1].

Automation tools have become most widespread in the areas of document flow, finance, and HR. Artificial intelligence has firmly entered corporate practice: 39% of organizations already use AI agents and AI assistants to address various tasks. Document flow, finance, and HR. According to research findings from SberAnalytics and Sber Business Soft on the automation of business processes in Russian companies as of 2025, based on survey data, the most commonly automated processes in companies are document flow and application processing (70%), accounting and financial management (55%), HR processes (34%), strategic planning (34%), and customer support (30%). In one in four companies, sales and marketing (25% each) are automated. Nineteen percent of companies use AI to address creative tasks. The

most common automation tools in companies are electronic document flow (EDF) (43%), CRM (42%), chatbots and voice assistants (42%), AI agents and assistants (39%), ERP (24%), and business analytics (BI) (23%) [2].

Within the scope of the study, it is necessary to highlight the main management accounting tools, including:

1. Planning (budgeting). This is the very first practical tool for implementing management accounting, from which work on determining the financial and economic results of an operating enterprise directly begins.

2. Calculation of the cost of proposed goods and services by the organization. The primary objective of calculating this aspect is accurate and correct pricing, which subsequently directly influences consumer demand.

3. Cost standardization. An equally important management accounting tool that enables the establishment of specific norms for resource consumption in the production of goods or provision of services. This tool makes it possible to monitor the efficiency of resource use within the company, as well as to implement their rational reduction and optimization.

Enhancing the quality of managerial decisions in production and commercial activities is the primary objective of management accounting. A proper implementation of the fundamental principles of efficiency enables the saving of information processing time and the conservation of resources, which are typically limited and may be strictly constrained. This allows for a significant minimization of risks that are directly or indirectly related to financial resources in business. Optimization and control of business processes make it possible to identify critical and growth points, and, through responsibility centers, develop various scenario conditions and courses of action within tactical and strategic plans.

Management Accounting represents a system of actions that includes the recording, processing, interpretation, and consolidation of information about events, facts, and phenomena related to an enterprise's activities with the aim of supporting managerial decision-making. In the context of the modern economy, Management Accounting, as part of the information infrastructure for managers and organizational owners, is undergoing significant changes amid digitalization [3]. The management accounting system is undergoing certain changes and adjustments; therefore, from a practical standpoint, it is important to consider the main trends and directions of its development, the key among which are [4]:

- artificial intelligence (artificial intelligence — искусственный интеллект/пазу). The implementation of artificial intelligence in management accounting enables the optimization and automation of many processes, such as the collection of data necessary for the economic analysis of the organization's activities, as well as sorting information and processing documents. This substantially reduces the required human labor and significantly accelerates the achievement of results.

Furthermore, this tool can propose various alternatives for the organization's development based on the analyzed indicators and data, as well as trends, tendencies, and even risks within the internal and external environments; it sometimes reveals hidden aspects and allows viewing the same situations from different perspectives.

— cloud services. To ensure high-quality management accounting, it is necessary to guarantee the security of confidential information and prevent unauthorized access by third parties. To this end, modern organizations use cloud storage, which is not only securely protected but also enables fast and easy retrieval of necessary data by keywords and is actively utilized for collaborative work among multiple specialists. However, to maintain uninterrupted operation of this component, it is essential to continuously update the software and resolve any emerging errors.

— data visualization. Modern managers find it much easier and more effective to understand information when it is presented graphically; this allows them to clearly identify certain trends and both positive and negative dynamics in the development of an economic entity, enabling timely adoption of effective managerial decisions and adjustments to the current company development strategy. This reduces the time spent analyzing enterprise activities and allows for prompt monitoring of the indicators related to the achievement of the primary business objective.

Table 1
Digital technologies in the business process optimization system:
the example of the business-class hotel 'Victoria Palace', Astrakhan[7]

Technology	Function
Intelligent digital platform	based on the GigaChat language model. GigaChat by Sber is not just another neural network, but a comprehensive ecosystem with unprecedented support for the Russian language. GigaChat is a multimodal neural network capable of processing and generating various types of content: text, images, and even programming code. It is built on the largest Russian language model with 100 billion parameters and trained on a large-scale corpus of texts, including scientific literature, fictional works, and technical documents []
TravelLine CRM system	generates detailed datasets of customer preferences and requests and segments the information for service personalization.
NLP frameworks (from the English term natural language processing)	libraries of tools and algorithms for recognizing and classifying customer inquiries.
Python scripts and APIs (from the English term application programming interface)	facilitate interaction between IT systems and applications, including information exchange with the bank.

Businesses use AI-based management systems to enhance process efficiency and free managers from routine tasks. According to the Business Research Company, the global market for intelligent virtual assistants was valued at 16.8 billion dollars in 2024 and is expected to reach 79.4 billion dollars by 2029, with a compound annual growth rate of 37.4%. [5]

One of the key areas of AI application is management functions. For example, the business-class hotel ‘Victoria Palace’ has been operating in Astrakhan since 2014. The hotel complex includes 63 rooms and annually accommodates up to 15,000 guests. The staff consists of 80 employees. To improve business processes at this hotel, a digital platform based on artificial intelligence, integrated with CRM (customer relationship management), was implemented.

The implementation of the intelligent platform helped the hotel optimize the request processing, improve customer experience, and increase loyalty. This positively affected the hotel’s revenue.

- The processing time for customer requests was reduced to five minutes.
- Booking conversion increased by 30%.
- The average check amount increased by 15%.

The above example demonstrates that SberPro is a leader in advancing digital technologies in business; its specialists and teams not only integrate them into their business processes but also train external users to work with neural networks by conducting practical intensive workshops. Human + AI is a direction in which many business organizations will soon need to restructure the working skills of their teams and management levels, as well as elements of business culture, in order to achieve new operational efficiency based on the theory of financial management and management accounting.

Fig. 1. The most anticipated effects of AI implementation according to businesses [8].

The efficiency of business processes can currently be enhanced by moving away from isolated AI experiments toward a platform approach and scenario modeling, which should be embedded into the organization's business framework. According to SberPro specialists, the checklist should include the following steps [8]:

1. Standardized and digitized business processes.
2. Centralized and structured data repository.
3. Integration of AI models into corporate systems (ERP, BI, BPM).
4. Abandoning point AI solutions in favor of a platform approach.
5. Cross-functional teams involving analysts, business clients, and IT specialists.
6. The evolving role of strategists: from planning to scenario support.

Building on the aforementioned directions for implementing a platform approach and scenario modeling within the business framework of economic entities, it is possible to reduce costs and achieve higher economic performance in the future.

Conclusion — in summary of the conducted research, it should be noted that management accounting remains essential for modern organizations in making strategically important decisions; thanks to this tool for financial forecasting, planning, and control, a company can more precisely determine future outcomes and formulate the most effective development strategies. This enables improved business management, reduced risks, and a higher probability of achieving established objectives. At the same time, business process management at the current stage is inextricably linked with comprehensive digitalization and the integration of digital technologies into planning, accounting, and control systems at all stages of economic and commercial activities. AI — artificial intelligence. GigaChat, NLP frameworks, Python scripts, and APIs are new tools for addressing budgeting, standardization, assessing business financial security, and planning economic activities. The use of these tools enables a prompt response to changes in external conditions and internal processes, as well as the adjustment of the development strategy of the economic entity in accordance with the current market situation and evolving economic management conditions within the global world order.

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ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN EDUCATION: OPPORTUNITIES AND RISKS

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Abstract. *This article examines the use of artificial intelligence in education (AIED). Research shows that AIED is rapidly developing. The authors outline the main areas of AIED development: tools to assist students in their learning, and support students and teachers. The analysis demonstrates that, despite its rapid growth, AIED is still in its infancy. This raises numerous social and ethical risks associated with its use. Managing these risks requires further study, discussion, and dialogue among all market participants and stakeholders.*

Keywords: *AI technologies in education (AEID), social and ethical risks of AIED.*

Introduction

The scientific community is currently actively monitoring the growing number of new research findings in the field of education. One of the most notable and promising trends is the acceleration of scientific and technological progress in creating new drivers of social growth and development. For example, the creation of intelligent, adaptive, and personalized learning systems in education and higher education, including economics. Such systems are being developed using AI technologies, which promise to radically transform the entire educational system. [1,2,3,4,6].

Methods

To conduct the study, methods of system analysis and process approach were used.

Results

The study's results show that AIED, as of today, cannot replace teachers and lecturers. AI is neither a robot (in the form of, for example, a cyber-physical system) nor a software suite capable of fully automating the educational process. However, according to the authors, new technologies that have already "crossed the threshold of schools and universities" undoubtedly have the potential to transform the entire education system. [2,4].

This thesis is supported by the decisions and actions of large high-tech businesses, on the one hand, and by structural elements of the education and higher education systems, on the other. For example, it is known that high-tech companies and investment funds are actively investing significant funds in AIED, comparable to the budgets of companies in individual industries and even developing countries.

Universities, schools, and colleges are integrating AI-powered educational products into their curricula. Research and development are underway to use AI in online learning and to develop competency-based approaches in teacher training programs and university teaching staff.

AI reduces teachers' workload significantly, opening up new forms and methods for planning individual courses and thematic lessons, relieving faculty of some of their routine work [2]. AI is used to create original illustrations and presentations that encourage students to provide feedback on the program.

Research conducted by TADVISER specialists at Innopolis University, Ural Federal University, Kirov State University, Kazan Federal University, and many other institutions has demonstrated that AI is successfully applied in projects that focus on operational information dissemination and automation of interactions with university content users, support for machine learning technologies, analysis of educational process dynamics, digitalization of educational content, and more. [3,5].

In what areas of educational activity can we judge the degree of AIED penetration into the educational environment?

— Various AI developers have created a wide range of educational and interactive products aimed at step-by-step mastery of material and the creation of a personalized learning environment in various areas of educational training, including economic sciences.

— A methodological and technological basis for analyzing the quality of students' written work has been created.

— Intelligent gaming environments and chatbots are developing rapidly. AI-powered tutoring is used for personalized tutoring. Technologically, this process involves the student independently using a computer during scheduled and unscheduled lessons, practicing subject matter, finding the right solution, and so on.

— AIED incorporates theory and methodology from other related fields of knowledge and at the same time creates its own research directions concerning the nature of new knowledge.

The study's results show that AIED software products aimed at solving both old and new educational challenges have been regularly introduced to the market in recent years. Here are some of these tools:

- to support student learning (ISO, DBTS, language learning apps, etc.);
- to support students (automated writing assessment, collaborative learning, continuous assessment, online learning coordinators, smart assistants, etc.);
- to support teachers (ISO+, smart teacher assistant, AIED as a research and teaching tool, etc.);
- chatbots, AR and VR, natural language processing, adaptability.

The analysis shows that despite the widespread use of AI in education, AIED is still in its infancy. The impact of AIED on educators, students, and society has not yet been determined and requires further study.

The social and ethical risks of implementing AIEDs are particularly pressing. We will illustrate some of these using the example of intelligent learning systems (ILS) that operate according to machine learning principles.

- If algorithms “learn” from data that contains human biases toward a process or phenomenon, then these algorithms internalize these biases and even reinforce them. [4]

- The use of ILPs reduces student engagement in their own learning. ILPs dictate what should be studied, in what order, and how. Students are then forced to follow the guidelines set by the ILPs. The use of ILPs completely ignores other approaches used in pedagogical science: collaborative learning, blended learning, trial and error, and guided inquiry.

- The problem of data selection and, consequently, trust in the entire system arises. It is well known that completely “raw” data does not exist; pre-selected data is used in analysis. This inevitably leads to an explicit or implicit systematic selection bias. [4]

The use of massive amounts of personal data on students and teachers by AI systems, coupled with powerful but opaque algorithms, raises privacy and other ethical concerns. We highlight some of these.

There are examples of AI product developers collecting massive amounts of student data to “identify patterns” using machine learning. However, this raises numerous questions, as the resulting analysis may be biased. Essentially, AIED developments and programs exist in an ethical vacuum. For example, a student may encounter a biased algorithm that negatively impacts their academic performance.

The ethical risks associated with the use of biased data and bias are already being discussed by experts and market participants. However, there are ethical issues that still need to be reconsidered. Let's list a few.

- What are the criteria for ethically acceptable AIED technology?
- What are the obligations of private organizations developing AIED products and public organizations (universities, schools) conducting AIED research?

— How can universities, schools, students, and teachers opt out of or challenge the use of their personal information in big data?

— What are the ethical implications of the inability to understand the chain of “deep” AIED decisions, particularly when using multilayer neural networks?

Discussion

The authors believe that addressing the social and ethical aspects of AIED is a challenging task that requires the participation of a wide range of stakeholders (from students and teachers to developers, philosophers, scientists, politicians, and government). It is important to understand the ethical issues involved in data collection (what data AI uses and what it doesn't, who owns the data, and how its privacy is maintained). Furthermore, it is necessary to understand the computational models used, how decisions are made, what biases may be hidden behind the models, and how to ensure the accuracy and transparency of decisions. The authors believe that managing the aforementioned risks requires further study and discussion among all stakeholders.

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ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT OF TERRITORIES UNDER CONDITIONS OF RESOURCE CONSTRAINTS

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Abstract: *in the contemporary global economy, territorial development increasingly takes place under conditions of limited natural, spatial, and infrastructural resources. Traditional models of extensive economic growth based on resource expansion are becoming less viable, particularly in densely populated and highly regulated regions. This paper examines the economic development of territories through the lens of resource constraints, emphasizing the transition from quantitative growth to qualitative and efficiency-oriented development models. The study adopts a conceptual and analytical approach, considering territories as complex economic systems in which space, resources, infrastructure, and institutional factors interact. The paper argues that resource constraints do not necessarily hinder economic development but instead act as a catalyst for innovation, optimization, and sustainable economic strategies. Key factors shaping territorial economic development under resource limitations are identified, including spatial efficiency, institutional coordination, and adaptive capacity. The findings contribute to the theoretical understanding of territorial economics and provide insights relevant for policymakers and regional development practitioners.*

Keywords: *territorial development, economic growth, resource constraints, spatial economics, sustainable development, regional economy*

1. Introduction

Economic development has traditionally been associated with the expansion of production factors, including land, natural resources, labor, and capital. However, contemporary economic realities demonstrate that many territories face increasing limitations in these resources. Urbanization, environmental regulations, climate change, and demographic pressures have significantly constrained the availability and use of spatial and natural resources. As a result, the question of how territories can sustain economic development under conditions of resource scarcity has become increasingly relevant.

In many regions, especially in Europe, economic growth can no longer rely on territorial expansion or intensive resource extraction. Instead, development strategies must focus on improving the efficiency of existing resources, optimizing spatial organization, and enhancing the qualitative aspects of economic activity. This shift necessitates a rethinking of traditional economic development models and calls for a more integrated understanding of territories as complex economic systems.

The purpose of this paper is to analyze the economic development of territories under conditions of resource constraints and to identify key factors that enable sustainable and resilient growth. The central research question guiding this study is: How can territories achieve economic development when faced with limited spatial and natural resources?

2. Conceptual Framework: Territory as an Economic System

A territory can be understood as a multidimensional economic system comprising physical space, natural resources, infrastructure, human capital, and institutional arrangements. Unlike abstract economic models, territorial systems are inherently spatial and constrained by physical boundaries and regulatory frameworks.

Resource constraints in territorial development manifest in several forms. Spatial constraints arise from limited land availability and competing land uses. Natural resource constraints are linked to environmental protection requirements and finite resource stocks. Infrastructural constraints reflect the limited capacity of transport, energy, and social systems. These constraints interact and collectively shape the economic potential of a territory.

From a spatial economics perspective, resource constraints increase the importance of efficient spatial organization. Agglomeration effects, accessibility, and functional land use become critical determinants of economic performance. Under such conditions, economic development is less about expansion and more about restructuring and optimization.

3. Methodological Approach

This study adopts a qualitative and conceptual research approach based on the synthesis of contemporary economic theories, spatial development concepts, and sustainability-oriented frameworks. Rather than relying on empirical case studies, the paper aims to develop a generalized analytical perspective applicable to different territorial contexts.

The methodology includes a comparative analysis of theoretical approaches to economic development, spatial economics, and resource efficiency. Special attention is given to concepts of sustainable development and economic resilience, which provide a useful lens for understanding development processes under constraint conditions.

4. Economic Development under Resource Constraints

4.1 Transition from Extensive to Intensive Growth

Under conditions of limited resources, extensive growth models based on factor accumulation become increasingly ineffective. Territories must shift toward intensive growth strategies focused on productivity gains, technological innovation, and improved resource efficiency. This transition involves maximizing economic output while minimizing additional resource consumption.

Such a shift also changes the role of territorial planning and governance. Strategic coordination of economic activities, infrastructure development, and land use becomes essential to avoid inefficiencies and conflicts over scarce resources.

4.2 Spatial Efficiency and Economic Performance

Spatial efficiency refers to the optimal allocation and use of territorial space to support economic activities. In constrained environments, inefficient spatial structures can significantly hinder development by increasing transaction costs and reducing accessibility. Compact urban forms, mixed-use development, and integrated transport systems are examples of spatial strategies that enhance economic efficiency.

Improving spatial efficiency enables territories to accommodate economic growth without proportional increases in resource consumption. This approach aligns with sustainability objectives and supports long-term economic viability.

4.3 Innovation and Adaptive Capacity

Resource constraints often stimulate innovation by encouraging the search for alternative solutions and more efficient technologies. Territories with strong innovation ecosystems and adaptive institutional frameworks are better positioned to respond to constraints and maintain economic dynamism.

Adaptive capacity includes the ability of economic systems to adjust to external shocks, regulatory changes, and environmental pressures. In this context, resilience becomes a key characteristic of successful territorial development.

5. Discussion

The analysis suggests that resource constraints should not be viewed solely as barriers to economic development. Instead, they can serve as drivers of structural transformation and qualitative growth. By emphasizing efficiency, innovation, and spatial optimization, territories can achieve sustainable economic development even under significant limitations.

This perspective challenges traditional growth paradigms and highlights the importance of integrated territorial strategies. Policymakers must consider economic, spatial, and environmental dimensions simultaneously to design effective development policies. The findings also underscore the relevance of spatial economics and sustainability frameworks in contemporary economic analysis.

6. Conclusions

Economic development under conditions of resource constraints represents one of the central challenges of modern territorial economics. As traditional growth models lose relevance, territories must adopt new strategies focused on efficiency, innovation, and resilience. This paper has demonstrated that constrained resources do not preclude development but rather reshape its nature and mechanisms.

The key conclusion is that successful territorial economic development in constrained environments depends on the effective management of space, the optimization of resource use, and the capacity to adapt to changing conditions. These insights contribute to a deeper understanding of territorial development processes and provide a conceptual basis for future empirical research.

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NEW PROFESSIONS AND SKILLS IN THE CONTEXT OF DIGITALIZATION OF THE ECONOMY

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Abstract. *The article identifies the primary external environmental factors determining the competitiveness of companies and their products in the context of expanding digitalization. Special attention is given to a comprehensive analysis of the labor market, which ensures the production of human capital. It has been proven that the adoption of digital technologies in the Russian economy continues actively despite the shortage of qualified specialists and resources.*

Keywords: *digitalization, industrial enterprises, external environment factors, labor market.*

Contemporary technologies are rapidly permeating all spheres of life. Digitalization in the Russian Federation has impacted sectors such as industry, education, healthcare, transportation, trade, housing and communal services, etc. These developments bring significant changes to the economic domain.

Technological factors (extensive automation of production, robotization) are transforming market conditions, including the labor market, generating demand for new professions and specialties, which consequently modifies qualification requirements for workers as traditional professions become obsolete. The emergence and development of innovative technologies (Artificial Intelligence (AI), Internet of Things, virtual and augmented reality (VR/AR), Big Data, bio- and neurotechnologies) are changing the approach to the production process, as these technologies can perform a significant number of diverse production functions.

The process of digitalization leads to increased social inequality in the labor market. According to income level analysis, the highest-paid specialties are in

the field of IT technologies. An analysis of the population's attitude towards this differentiation showed that 30.8% of individuals consider social inequality in the labor sphere caused by the use of digital technologies to be just, while 24.4% regard it as legitimate.

Currently, millions of people in the Russian Federation are employed in professions such as salespeople, drivers, security guards, loaders, and others. Undoubtedly, the implementation of IT technologies has enhanced mobility across various industries and simplified interactions between consumers and producers. Nevertheless, the demand for manual labor professions remains relevant [6].

The study revealed that the sectors lagging in digitalization include the fuel and energy complex, mechanical engineering, metallurgy, medicine, and pharmaceuticals. The most vulnerable regions are the following territories: the Republic of Ingushetia, Chechnya, Dagestan, Karachay-Cherkessia, Kabardino-Balkaria, and Tuva. In these regions, highly automated activities such as trade and agriculture [7] predominate, which, in turn, negatively impact the accelerated implementation of digitalization.

According to the latest analytical data, an extremely small percentage of the population, not exceeding 20%, possesses the skills necessary to conduct business. In the engineering sector, although some measures have been undertaken, they have not fundamentally improved the situation for the majority of people. With the growth of automation, the question arises concerning the state's capacity to provide resources for the adaptation of residents across various cities and regions. The Decree of the President of the Russian Federation No. 204 dated May 7, 2018, underscores the significance of this issue and the commitment to address it, emphasizing its enduring relevance within the strategic objectives of national development.

These strategies focus on the advancement of digitalization in regions and territories.

In many regions of Russia, progress in adopting the latest technologies does not meet the level of developed countries, which can be attributed to several factors: insufficient population density, heterogeneity of economic activity, limited income levels, low technological capacity, and weak infrastructural connectivity among various regions. On the other hand, the proliferation of digital technologies and the expansion of remote work opportunities bring significant adjustments to the labor market structure.

In the era of digitalization of economic processes, understanding changes in labor market demands becomes critically important. Labor market dynamics are evolving under the influence of digitalization, with the emergence of innovative economic platforms that utilize information from multiple channels. Certain territorial entities demonstrate increased activity in attracting labor resources.

The implementation of digital technologies enhances organizational competitiveness and productivity. Modern economic growth and company development are

impossible without automation and the improvement of production processes — this is an indisputable fact.

Effective management of interactions between the client base and suppliers enables qualitative coordination and the rational use of available resources [10]. At the same time, dialogue is improving with all participants in the chain — from business partners to end consumers — and new opportunities are arising for monitoring and managing operational activities. All of this accelerates and increases the productivity of workflows across various organizational functions.

The development of partnerships and cross-sector cooperation is made possible by the adoption of digital technologies in economic processes. Organizations acquire the ability to respond effectively to market dynamics by increasing their agility, adaptability, and strengthening their position in a competitive environment through digital modernization. Digitalization allows for cost reduction and enhances the efficiency of interactions. In turn, it raises the issue of workforce quality and its alignment with modern requirements. Unfortunately, many companies do not actively adopt new management methods or invest in human capital development. Undoubtedly, large corporations devote serious attention to retraining and upskilling their personnel. However, the question of whether graduate training aligns with market requirements remains unresolved.

At present, there is a growing demand for new professions and skills, particularly in the Z-economy, which warrants special attention. Technological changes give rise to new professions, while traditional labor specialties are gradually becoming obsolete. Nevertheless, as practice shows, predictions that a number of contemporary professions will become obsolete and disappear have not yet materialized. Undoubtedly, there is a growing demand for specialists in the fields of information technology, biotechnology, and alternative energy in the modern world. This requires a reassessment of approaches to education and workforce training for the digital economy.

One solution to this issue is the national project ‘Personnel’ [11]. At present, the impact of digitalization on the labor market structure is already observable, reflected in the forms of employment within the digital economy. Globally, especially in highly developed countries such as the USA, Japan, the United Kingdom, Germany, China, and India, the information technology sector is rapidly expanding, fostering the creation of new jobs. However, the situation in Russia differs — opportunities for IT sector development and new job creation are limited in regions dominated by industry, agriculture, and extractive sectors. Moreover, a particularly pronounced lag in technological development and employment opportunities characterizes single-industry towns.

New high-tech companies are primarily established in large cities where there is a large population, an extensive service sector, and a sufficient number of higher education institutions; consequently, a significant number of employers are present

across various sectors. Thus, in Tatarstan, digital transformation is planned across 15 industries, positioning it as a leader in digital transformation. In Saint Petersburg, the digital transformation strategy covers 11 industries; in the Moscow Region, 10; in Kalmykia and the Jewish Autonomous Region, approximately 10 industries each; in the Altai Territory, around 11 industries; and in the Kurgan Region, digital transformation is planned across 15 industries [12].

In the era of digitalization, information technologies are undergoing rapid growth. According to the 2018 World Economic Forum data, by 2030, the number of new jobs created due to technological progress is expected to double compared to those lost as a result of automation.

Conclusions. The factors of the external environment affecting the functioning of industrial enterprises under the influence of digitalization are driven by a series of transformations.

1. The implementation of digital technologies in the Russian economy is actively ongoing despite challenges such as a shortage of qualified specialists and resources. This contributes not only to the development of new professions but also to reducing dependence on external economic conditions.

2. The adoption of digitalization principles not only lowers production costs but also significantly improves efficiency.

3. Robotics and automation contribute to the creation of new production models.

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ECONOMIC AND SOCIOLOGICAL CONCEPT OF RESEARCH INTO INNOVATION ACTIVITIES

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Abstract. *The article proposes a systemic concept for the study of innovation activity as a tool to increase its effectiveness within the framework of the modern paradigm of development of the information-digital mode of production. The main theoretical and methodological provisions and approaches are presented, the practical adoption of which will enable an increase in the effectiveness of solving a complex intersectoral and interdisciplinary problem. A distinctive feature of the proposed concept is the study of issues concerning the identification and implementation of organizational, managerial, and socio-economic provisions and mechanisms for regulating, forecasting, and managing innovation processes at the level of a specific enterprise, industry, region, or country as a whole, as well as the issue of the effective realization of the personal potential of innovation activity.*

Keywords: *innovation economy; innovation activity; innovation processes; effects of innovation activity; economic-sociological concept; study of innovation activity*

The socio-economic effects of innovation activity today, at the stage of formation of the information-digital mode of production and consumption, acquire paramount significance, as they exert a decisive comprehensive influence on the development of the entire socio-economic system of society, generating both positive and negative effects.

Among the positive social effects of innovation activity, the primary ones include the increase in labor mobility and opportunities for self-realization; the expansion of free time due to process automation; the improvement in accessibility to knowledge and educational opportunities; the development of communicative interaction and information exchange; the modernization of the education system (including for individuals with disabilities); the enhancement of the population's standard and quality of life; the simplification of public services through digitalization.

Negative social effects primarily include the intensification of social stratification by income level; conflicts of interest among various economic agents; loss of elements of national identity due to globalization; risk of increased crime amid excess free time; reduction of employment due to automation and robotics; decline in demand for 'traditional' professions; potential deterioration of moral standards; social tension; Negative impact on health due to environmental consequences.

Positive economic effects are sources of growth in socio-economic welfare; Acceleration of the life cycle of products and services; Enhancement of the competitiveness of enterprises and industries; Creation of new markets and business models; Increase in labor productivity; Attraction of investments to promising directions.

Potential problems of modern innovation activity include: high risks of investment inputs (for example, statistics show that only 1–2 out of 10 startups succeed); increase in costs for workforce retraining; deviation of actual GDP from potential due to unemployment; reduction of tax revenues due to declining employment; increase in government expenditures on social support for the unemployed; ineffectiveness of monetary methods for stimulating innovations without accounting for social factors, etc.

Today, innovation activity constitutes one of the leading and key modes of existence for social systems, as well as a means for the development of individuals, collectives, social communities, and society as a whole.

The connection of innovation activity with changes in the economic, technological, and social structures of society through mechanisms of economic and social mobility, alongside the active participation of its subjects (individuals and social groups engaged in the development and implementation of innovations), necessitates the development and implementation of new theoretical and methodological approaches to the study of innovation activity.

New theoretical and methodological approaches must ensure the resolution of this complex cross-sectoral and interdisciplinary problem represented by innovation activity. Such a new concept may serve as the economic-sociological concept of the study of innovation activity.

The economic-sociological concept of the study of innovation activity constitutes a fundamentally new research direction that involves the investigation of economic-sociological processes and consequences of innovation activity from the

perspective of a specialized systems theory. Unlike traditional economic, social, and sociological theories, this theory considers any aspect of innovation activity as an action embedded in social relations, which are understood as relatively stable and selective connections among individuals, groups, and organizations.

The economic-sociological concept of the study of innovation activity is inextricably linked to the examination of socio-economic mechanisms regulating the processes of inception, development, implementation, adaptation, and integration of innovations across various spheres of social life — social, economic, political, cultural, and others. All these aspects are inextricably connected to a specialized economic-sociological theory — the economy of the sociology of innovation activity.

The economic-sociological concept of the study of innovation activity is a specialized concept directly connected with the investigation of the influence of the human factor on the development of innovation processes, the formation of social prerequisites, and the effects of the functioning and development of innovation activity systems.

The economic-sociological concept of the study of innovation activity also gains significant importance in the context of investigating the impact of the implementation of innovations on the transformation of cultural-value, socio-psychological, professional-qualification, motivational, and other characteristics of society.

The economic-sociological concept of the study of innovation activity presents the theory of the formation, development, and enhancement of innovation processes as a set of interconnected and sequentially executed actions for the development, creation, introduction, and application of scientific and technological progress achievements in social production.

The economic-sociological concept of the study of innovation activity involves the investigation of mechanisms within innovation processes that regulate the stages of inception, development, implementation, adaptation, and integration of innovations across various spheres of social life. At the same time, innovations themselves are regarded as a mode of existence of social systems, where innovation acts as a factor in the development of individuals, collectives, social communities, and society as a whole.

The proposed economic-sociological concept for studying innovation activity investigates:

- innovations as a factor in the development of the socio-cultural process: innovations are always the result of the historical interaction of cultures, as each innovation is born within the framework of the existing culture and elevates it to a new level, thereby opening pathways to a new culture;

- specific social connections in the implementation of innovation processes; social prerequisites, conditions, and factors of the emergence and assimilation of innovations, as well as the specifics of the interaction of innovation activity with other social processes;

— links between innovations and changes in social structures. The economic-sociological concept of studying innovation activity examines the active role of its subjects (individuals and social groups engaged in inventing novelties and their practical implementation), allowing them to change their social status and occupy new (more often higher) positions within the social structure;

— risks as a component of innovation activity. Unlike economic analysis, the economic-sociological concept focuses on studying subjective characteristics, as well as the conditions of emergence, the content of actions, and their potential consequences for the actors of innovations.

The economic-sociological concept of the study of innovation activity enables the disclosure and definition of its specific essence, place, roles, functions, and social potential, as well as the identification of its influence on various social processes and effects. Together, this allows for the analysis of contradictions and conflicts in innovation practice, as well as the representation of public opinion concerning ongoing changes and emerging needs.

The economic-sociological concept of the study of innovation activity facilitates the resolution of problems related to the implementation of innovations, their adaptation, diagnosis, and forecasting of novelties. These problems encompass multiple levels: society, organization, and individual.

The objective of the economic-sociological concept for the study of innovation activity is the improvement of innovation theory. Its main tasks are:

— systematic study and resolution of specific problems accompanying the entire spectrum of innovation activity;

— examination of the demand for innovations and the market of innovative services;

— analysis of regularities, causes, and factors determining changes in innovation processes;

— investigation of innovation activity and the specifics of behavior in the innovation practice of particular communities, groups, and collectives;

— the study of the experience of implementing innovations in specific organizations, as well as the level of their effectiveness and completeness, and features of adaptation to them;

— identifying people's attitudes towards relevant facts and events of innovation practice and the degree of effectiveness of the implemented changes;

— obtaining information about individual changes related to innovation creativity;

— studying previous experience in the production and adoption of innovations, errors, difficulties, risks, and the effectiveness of innovations and innovation activity;

— obtaining information from professional specialists in the field of innovative technologies to ensure the effectiveness of the implementation, development of innovations, or conducting innovation diagnostics and forecasting;

- forecasting and modeling the future state of innovation activity;
- systematic study of social dynamics, which enables the continuous acquisition of statistical and economic-sociological data on innovation processes occurring in various social spheres;
- the study of cause-and-effect relationships characterizing the perception and evaluation of innovations, features of adaptation to changes, as well as the needs of the environment for innovations.

Moreover, the objective of the economic-sociological concept of studying innovation activity is to optimize the functioning of organizational, managerial, and socio-economic mechanisms that regulate innovation processes, taking into account societal needs, capabilities, and expectations. This involves solving interrelated tasks at various hierarchical levels of the innovation system.

The objective at the level of the national-state innovation system is to identify contradictions and conflicts in innovation practice. The economic-sociological study of innovations enables the definition of their essence, functions, and socio-economic potential, as well as the identification of their impact on various socio-economic processes. Analyzing public opinion on ongoing changes and emerging needs will substantially aid in forecasting and diagnosing innovations, as well as in tracking trends in their development.

The objective at the level of innovation systems within enterprises, organizations, and institutions is to identify the causes of employee resistance to innovation. Additionally, to ensure the scientific substantiation and support of innovation activity, which includes analyzing employees' readiness for active creative engagement, their perception of innovative ideas from management, and the presence of innovative projects proposed by employees; identifying negative factors hindering the development and implementation of an innovative product, as well as formulating recommendations to eliminate adverse effects on the innovation process.

The objective at the individual level is to study their innovation potential — a set of personal traits and qualities that enable the creation, perception, and implementation of innovations, as well as the timely abandonment of outdated and impractical modes of activity.

The economic-sociological approach to studying innovation activity is also intended to ensure the examination of the features and specifics of conditions and factors, regularities and principles, socio-economic mechanisms and relations that arise during the development, testing, adoption, and disposal of innovations within organizations, groups, social communities, and social institutions, among others. It investigates the internal mechanisms of their structure and development, the patterns of social actions and mass behavior, as well as the relations between the individual and society in the course of implementing innovation activity.

The practical application of the economico-sociological concept for studying innovation activity will facilitate the examination of the systemic interaction of innovation activity within the social sphere of society. Such specific aspects of the study should include, first and foremost:

- organizational-managerial, economic, and social mechanisms for the development of innovation processes;
- social institutions as regulators of socio-innovation processes, contract institutions, property relations, institutions of power, and others;
- innovation behavior, its types and the nature of its influence on innovation processes, its goals and needs underlying behavior, scope of freedom, methods of implementation, results, and other characteristics;
- the social structure of innovation activity as a regulator of innovation processes; In particular, the types of social subjects of innovation activity and others are studied.

The implementation and practical application of the economic-sociological concept for studying innovation activity will enable:

- to determine the influence of social characteristics of individuals as bearers of an innovative mindset and behavior type on the innovation process;
- to study the challenges of realizing personal potential under the conditions of innovation activity; identification of personal traits that enable successful adaptation to socio-professional changes and barriers impeding the realization of potential;
- to create a social mechanism for forming an individual predisposition to innovation activity, which will enable the regulation, forecasting, and management of the innovation process at the scale of a specific enterprise, industry, region, or the country as a whole.

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DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION IN EDUCATION: CHANGES IN MANAGEMENT THROUGH THE APPLICATION OF MARKETING TECHNOLOGIES

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Abstract. *This article examines the impact of marketing technologies on the management of educational institutions in the context of digital transformation. The study confirms that the implementation of these technologies significantly improves interaction with students and enhances the quality of educational services. Case studies demonstrate how personalized approaches shape a positive student experience and increase their engagement. The proposed strategy for integrating marketing tools into the educational process contributes to streamlining management and increasing student satisfaction. Particular attention is paid to the need to create a unified platform for data analysis and decision support. The significance of the study lies in identifying modern management practices and recommendations for educational institutions. The results of the study open up prospects for further study of the use of digital technologies in the educational environment, which, in turn, emphasizes the importance of innovative approaches in management.*

Keywords: *digital transformation; education; marketing technologies; management; personalization; student satisfaction; strategic planning.*

Introduction

Digital transformation is becoming a key aspect of the development of educational systems in the 21st century. In the context of rapid scientific and technological progress, education is undergoing significant changes, requiring the implementation of new management approaches and technologies adapted to modern requirements. This article examines the impact of marketing technologies on management processes in educational institutions and identifies the main trends and challenges arising during digital transformation.

The relevance of this study stems from the need for educational institutions to adapt to changing conditions and societal needs. In recent years, there has been

increasing interest in the use of marketing technologies in education, posing a number of new challenges for management [1]. Digitalization not only changes teaching methods but also requires a revision of existing management models that take into account the specific aspects of implementing innovative practices in the educational process. Thus, understanding the impact of marketing technologies on management in education is becoming an important task.

The main problem addressed by this study is the insufficient knowledge of issues related to the integration of marketing technologies in educational institutions. Today, there is a disconnect between the theoretical foundations of marketing and the practical implementation of its principles in education [2]. This leads to sub-optimal use of existing resources and capabilities, which, in turn, complicates the implementation of strategies aimed at improving the quality of educational services. A key aspect in this context is not only the implementation of technological solutions but also the need to revise management approaches based on data integration, consumer behavior analysis, and optimization of interactions with all participants in the educational process [3]. There is a need to develop models that allow for the systematic evaluation of the effectiveness of marketing strategies applied in education and management.

The purpose of this study is to analyze the impact of marketing technologies on the management of educational institutions in the context of digital transformation, as well as to develop effective strategies and recommendations for optimizing management processes to improve the quality of educational services and student satisfaction.

Based on the above, the study hypothesis is formulated as follows: the introduction of marketing technologies in the management of educational institutions contributes to increased competitiveness by optimizing interactions with students, introducing personalized educational pathways, and increasing satisfaction with the services received.

Research Methods

The study utilized both methodological and empirical approaches. We analyzed existing literature on marketing technologies and educational management, and examined cases of successful implementation of such practices in educational institutions at various levels. To achieve this goal, we employed qualitative and quantitative analysis methods, including a comparative analysis of various management models. The results of this analysis will allow us to develop practical recommendations for implementing marketing technologies in educational management practices, which in turn will serve as a basis for further research in this area.

Thus, this study not only complements the existing theoretical framework but also offers practical solutions aimed at improving the management of educational institutions in the context of digital transformation.

Research Results and Discussion

To thoroughly analyze the introduction of marketing technologies, it is necessary to consider new approaches to managing educational institutions, including the development of data-driven strategies. In this regard, the authors of the article focus on the use of methods for collecting and analyzing information that enable more effective interaction with the target audience. The use of web analytics tools, CRM systems, and specialized learning management platforms not only improves management efficiency but also fosters a positive image of the educational institution [4]. Marketing technologies not only increase student awareness but also create conditions for their active involvement in decision-making. The introduction of feedback and the use of surveys and questionnaires to assess student satisfaction with the quality of education are becoming important elements of interaction, allowing management to make informed decisions. In this context, the use of digital platforms for conducting research and analyzing data on student needs appears most appropriate [5]. By providing the ability to continuously monitor and evaluate student opinions, it is possible to promptly adjust educational programs and management approaches. It should be noted that the successful integration of marketing technologies into the educational process requires not only a business vision but also a willingness to change from the leaders of educational institutions. The need to train employees and manage a culture of innovation within the organization is becoming a key factor for success. Without developing the appropriate skills and approaches, the integration of new technologies risks being ineffective. Educational institutions require strategic planning that includes not only the implementation of new technologies but also a comprehensive system of training and professional development for employees. An analysis of successful cases shows that those educational institutions that actively integrate marketing technologies into their practices achieve higher results [6]. In particular, they demonstrate better student retention rates and increased student engagement in the educational process. Thus, based on successful practices, it becomes clear that the lack of adaptive management approaches can lead to student loss and, consequently, to economic losses for the educational institution.

The successful implementation of marketing technologies directly depends on their ability to tap into critical aspects of student motivation. When revising curricula and teaching approaches, attention should be paid not only to academic offerings but also to issues related to students' individual interests and their professional interactions [7]. Integrating such aspects into the educational marketing system represents a new paradigm that contributes to improving the quality of participation in the educational process. In the context of technical support for marketing technologies, it is worth considering an analysis of the functionality of modern platforms on which the learning process takes place, as well as the possibilities for their integration

into existing management systems. Platforms that support various forms of student interaction create unique opportunities for organizing the educational process. For example, motivating gamification elements integrated into courses can increase student engagement and enhance their participation in the learning process.

The digital transformation of the educational environment necessitates a re-thinking of management approaches aimed at integrating marketing technologies as a tool for improving the efficiency of educational institutions [8]. This article examines the impact of such technologies on management processes and educational aspects, allowing us to consider not only the theoretical but also the practical aspects of this problem. The analysis identifies key areas in which marketing can contribute to improving management practices in educational institutions. Improving the educational process in the context of digitalization requires the active use of technology to collect and process data on students, their preferences, and needs. Data analysis and the application of marketing methods are becoming fundamental to the development of more effective curricula and personalized educational pathways. An important aspect of this process is the use of platforms for feedback and customer interaction analysis, which optimizes communication channels and improves student satisfaction.

When considering the management of educational institutions in the context of digital transformation, it is necessary to challenge traditional management models, which often prove ineffective in a rapidly changing external environment [9]. In the article, the authors note that the implementation of marketing technologies requires managers not only to master new tools but also to create a culture of innovation and openness to new practices. This can be achieved through developing relationships with various stakeholders, including students, faculty, and employers, which ultimately contributes to the creation of a more flexible and adaptable educational environment. Every educational institution, striving to be competitive, must consider the needs of its audience and respond quickly to changes. In this context, marketing technologies become an important tool that can significantly improve the quality of management. Developing strategies based on in-depth market and customer data facilitates more effective communication and increases the ability of educational organizations to adapt to changing student needs.

One of the significant challenges identified during the study is the lack of knowledge and skills among educational institution staff in the application of marketing technologies. Successfully integrating these technologies into management requires developing new competencies among management personnel. This issue requires careful analysis and the development of appropriate training and professional development programs, which in turn should be part of the institution's strategic plan. Expanding the scope of university marketing technologies encompasses not only traditional aspects such as advertising and PR, but also more profound

changes in the management of the educational process. The use of digital platforms for analyzing academic performance, student engagement, and other factors that contribute to improving the quality of education plays a key role here [5]. Objective data becomes the basis for making management decisions aimed at improving educational services and optimizing the educational process. Thus, the conducted study confirms that the use of marketing technologies in the management of educational institutions is becoming a prerequisite for their successful functioning in the context of digital transformation. Effective use of these technologies allows not only to optimize internal processes but also significantly improve the results of educational activities. At the same time, it was revealed that for the successful implementation of these technologies

The first stage requires a high level of engagement among key stakeholders in the development and implementation of marketing technologies. This includes not only management but also faculty, students, and their parents. Organizing roundtables and workshops can help identify the needs and expectations of all stakeholders, ensuring the maximum relevance and effectiveness of the implemented technologies. The next stage involves creating a multi-layered change implementation system that allows for gradual adaptation to the new format. This system should be multifunctional and incorporate not only technical aspects but also social factors. To achieve success, it is important that each participant understands their role and significance within the system. Providing regular updates on the implementation progress and receiving feedback from participants will help prevent resistance. Equally important is the implementation effectiveness evaluation stage. This allows not only for monitoring the implementation of tasks but also for regular data analysis to monitor results and focus on the successes achieved. This article proposes the use of KPI methods to evaluate the effectiveness of marketing technologies, involving the assessment of both quantitative and qualitative indicators. Key aspects to consider include student satisfaction, academic success, and engagement, as well as improving the educational institution's market image. Furthermore, the study emphasizes the need to build long-term relationships with former and current students. Creating effective loyalty programs, working with the alumni community, and actively engaging with them through digital channels will help build a strong community that promotes a positive image of the educational institution. Developing platforms and events that allow former students to share their experiences, connect with students, and provide consultations will significantly enrich the educational process and enhance its value in the eyes of students. A key element of marketing technologies is the use of digital marketing methods, which helps strengthen the promotion of educational programs and services provided by the educational institution. Social media, content marketing, and SEO are becoming essential tools for maintaining the relevance of existing services and building market recognition. Successful implementation

of these methods requires a comprehensive approach to content and an integrated strategy for engaging with the target audience. In the context of management processes for integrating marketing technologies, it is important to note the importance of creating an effective internal reporting system aimed at continuously monitoring results and diagnosing potential deviations.

Modern analytics and business intelligence technologies enable the collection of data on educational processes, filling gaps in legacy management structures and significantly improving the use of information for decision-making. Thus, the research conducted and the developed strategy provide an opportunity to develop a holistic understanding of the integration of marketing technologies into educational process management. This understanding encompasses both theoretical and practical aspects, enabling the development of new approaches to interacting with students and learning in general. The importance of integrating marketing technologies into education management has not gone unnoticed and will require further research into their effective application in various educational institutions at all levels. By implementing the proposed strategy, educational institutions will not only be able to improve the quality of services provided but also create a flexible and adaptive management system capable of functioning effectively amid the constant changes and challenges of modern society.

Conclusions

This article examines the impact of marketing technologies on the management of educational institutions in the context of digital transformation. It was found that the integration of these technologies not only enhances management processes but also creates more effective models of interaction with students, confirming the hypothesis. The study demonstrated that the use of marketing technologies significantly increases student satisfaction, optimizes educational programs, and improves the overall quality of services provided. Based on the analysis, it can be argued that the implementation of marketing technologies enables educational institutions not only to adapt to modern conditions but also to become more competitive in the educational services market. The use of these technologies allows for the collection and analysis of information about student preferences and needs, leading to the creation of personalized educational pathways. This ensures high levels of student engagement and fosters a positive image of the educational institution.

The scientific significance of the findings lies in the fact that the presented study complements the existing theoretical framework in the field of education management and substantiates the need for the active use of marketing technologies in the management of educational institutions. The results of this study highlight the importance of developing new integrated systems based on digital technologies, opening up prospects for further theoretical and practical research in this area.

The practical significance of this study is expressed in its recommendations for integrating marketing technologies into the management of educational institutions. The proposed approaches can be used by educational institution leaders to improve student engagement, enhance the quality of educational services, and create more effective management models. Developing and implementing data-driven strategies will enable educational institutions to adapt to changes in the educational environment and meet the growing needs of students.

The study identified numerous aspects worthy of careful consideration in future research. Directions for future research may include a detailed analysis of the application of specific marketing technologies and tools in various educational contexts, such as higher education, vocational training, and school education. Studying the long-term impact of these technologies on the management and outcomes of the educational process also requires additional attention. Thus, further research could focus on assessing the impact of digital technologies on educational management practices, as well as developing models that facilitate deeper integration of marketing systems into the educational environment. It is important to analyze how to increase educational institutions' readiness for change and develop recommendations for developing a new management culture capable of adapting to the constant changes of the digital world.

In conclusion, the study confirms the significant impact of marketing technologies on educational process management and emphasizes the need for their active use in modern educational institutions. Based on the data obtained, it can be concluded that the ability of educational institutions to innovate and adapt to new conditions will determine their success and competitiveness in the educational services market in the future.

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FINANCIAL ASSESSMENT OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF THE PROJECT WHEN RECEIVING SUBSIDIES FROM THE FEDERAL BUDGET

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Abstract: *The article is devoted to the methodology of financial assessment of the effectiveness of investment projects implemented with the involvement of subsidies from the federal budget. A multi-level regulatory framework is considered, including the Budget Code of the Russian Federation, Government resolutions of the Russian Federation and departmental methodological documents. Special attention is paid to the classification of subsidies by type of costs and their impact on the cash flows of the project. An algorithm for comparative efficiency assessment based on the “subsidized” and “non-subsidized” scenarios with the calculation of key indicators is proposed. The specific risks associated with the use of subsidies are systematized and methods of accounting for them in the financial model through scenario analysis and sensitivity analysis are proposed. The results of the study can be used to improve the validity of investment decisions and the quality of project selection for government support.*

Key words: *subsidy, federal budget, investment project, financial efficiency assessment, cash flows, risks, scenario analysis.*

Introduction

Financing investment projects with federal budget subsidies is a complex public policy instrument aimed at achieving not only commercial but also socially significant economic results. A key challenge for project initiators and government agencies is the need to objectively assess this dual effectiveness. Traditional investment analysis methods require significant adaptation to account for the terms of subsidies, their impact on various types of cash flows, and the risks associated with compliance with strict regulatory requirements. Insufficient attention to these

aspects in a financial model can lead to the adoption of unviable projects and the misuse or ineffective use of budget funds. This article discusses a consistent methodology for conducting a financial assessment based on a comparative analysis of “with” and “without” subsidies scenarios, classifying support types, and integrating specific risks into the model. The result is a structured approach that ensures transparency and credibility of the justification for both the investor and the government.

The legal framework governing the financial assessment of the effectiveness of projects applying for subsidies from the federal budget is characterized by a complex multi-level structure. Its formation is based on the provisions of the Budget Code of the Russian Federation (hereinafter referred to as the BC RF) [1], which are specified and developed in acts of the Government of the Russian Federation and departmental regulatory documents. Articles 78 [2] and 78.1 [3] of the BC RF are of central importance for determining the methodological foundations of the assessment. These provisions establish target guidelines and legal conditions for the provision of subsidies to legal entities, individual entrepreneurs (hereinafter referred to as IE), and individuals — producers of goods, works, and services. The key principles enshrined in these articles and forming the initial requirements for the assessment are the targeted nature and effectiveness of the use of budgetary funds, the mandatory conclusion of agreements on the provision of subsidies and the establishment of quantitative indicators therein, allowing for measuring effectiveness and monitoring the achievement of the stated results.

The Budget Code of the Russian Federation establishes framework conditions that form the methodological foundations for financial modeling of projects eligible for state support. These conditions are specified in mandatory requirements for the content of subsidy agreements, including a detailed description of objectives, a list of reimbursable costs, performance targets, as well as procedural aspects of financing and the responsibilities of the parties. From a financial analysis perspective, regulations governing the consequences of misuse of funds, the rights of regulatory authorities to suspend or terminate funding, and subsidy repayment mechanisms are critical. These legal provisions create a system of restrictions, generate specific contingent liabilities, and introduce additional regulatory risks into the model. Consequently, an adequate financial performance assessment for the investor and the budget requires that these factors be taken into account during the cash flow calculation and final performance assessment stages.

The development and specification of the Budget Code’s fundamental provisions regarding the provision of subsidies is carried out through secondary legislation, primarily through decrees of the Government of the Russian Federation. These regulations establish standardized requirements for the development of departmental regulatory legal acts, as well as for the procedures for selecting recipients of budgetary funds.

A key role in the formation of a unified legal framework is played by Decree of the Government of the Russian Federation No. 1782 of 25.10.2023 [5] (in systemic interconnection with other acts, in particular, Decree of the Government of the Russian Federation No. 1780 of 25.10.2023 [4]). This document approves comprehensive general requirements for regulatory legal acts governing the provision of subsidies and grants in the form of subsidies to legal entities, individual entrepreneurs and individuals — producers of goods, works, services. Its norms regulate unified approaches to the structure of the relevant acts, the mandatory content of the conditions for the provision of support, the criteria for the competitive selection of applicants, the composition of the documentation provided, as well as the basic parameters of agreements on the provision of subsidies and the system for monitoring the achievement of target indicators. Thus, these resolutions form a detailed procedural framework ensuring the implementation of the principles enshrined in the Budget Code of the Russian Federation at the stage of the regulatory registration of specific support measures.

Certain decrees of the Government of the Russian Federation regulate the provision of subsidies to the budgets of constituent entities of the Russian Federation and municipalities, and also establish the procedure for the distribution and use of interbudgetary transfers of a targeted nature. In a situation in which the final recipient is financed through the regional budget mechanism, the legal framework for the project is formed not only by federal but also by regional and municipal regulations. The latter must be in strict compliance with the general requirements established by the Government of the Russian Federation regarding the terms of subsidy provision, competitive procedures, and performance indicator systems. From a practical perspective of the financial assessment of the project, this circumstance necessitates a comprehensive consideration of both federal and regional restrictions. In particular, this is reflected in the application of additional requirements for the level of co-financing, priority areas of activity, and specific target indicators established at the level of the constituent entity of the Russian Federation or municipality, which complicates the structure of the model and increases the requirements for the detail of the analysis [6, 7].

Methodological documents defining approaches to assessing the effectiveness of projects involving budgetary funds are a crucial element of the regulatory environment. The generally accepted methodological guideline is the Methodological Recommendations for Assessing the Effectiveness of Investment Projects (second edition, amended and supplemented), approved by the Ministry of Economy of the Russian Federation, the Ministry of Finance of the Russian Federation, and the State Construction Committee of the Russian Federation on June 21, 1999, No. VK 477 [8]. This document establishes uniform principles for discounting cash flows, comparing alternative implementation

options, and a system of indicators for assessing commercial, budgetary, and socioeconomic effectiveness.

For projects directly involving the use of federal budget funds for capital investments, special methodologies are applied. These include, for example, the Methodology for Assessing the Effectiveness of Using Federal Budget Funds Allocated for Capital Investments, approved by Order No. 108 of the Ministry of Economic Development of Russia dated February 21, 2024, and effective as amended by Order No. 418 of the Ministry of Economic Development of Russia dated June 24, 2025 [9, 10]. These regulations define the composition of cash flows for the budget, project selection criteria, rules for preparing conclusions on the effectiveness of budget investment use, and a set of integrated indicators (including budget NPV and the payback period for budget investments), which directly impacts the structure of the financial model and the algorithm for calculating the budgetary efficiency of the project.

The next level of regulation is formed by departmental orders and decisions of relevant ministries, primarily the Ministry of Industry and Trade of Russia, the Ministry of Economic Development of Russia, the Ministry of Finance of Russia, and other bodies implementing industry support programs. Such acts approve the procedures for providing subsidies in specific areas — industry, exports, digitalization, R&D, modernization of fixed assets, and so on — and establish specific types of expenses subject to reimbursement, formulas for calculating the amount of subsidies, requirements for the share of the recipient's own and borrowed funds, as well as a list and target values of performance indicators. For financial evaluation, these documents define the structure and time profile of cash flows associated with the subsidy (the moment of income recognition, the period of cost compensation, the conditions for reducing or returning funds), as well as a set of risks affecting the sustainability of the project and its effectiveness [11, 12, 13].

Of significant importance are the requirements for the content of applications and supporting materials, set out in both general Russian Government regulations and departmental procedures. As a rule, regulatory acts stipulate the applicant's obligation to submit a financial model or project efficiency calculation, a justification for the amount of the requested subsidy, a forecast of performance and budget indicators (taxes, jobs, export revenue, etc.), and scenario assessments. This institutionalizes the use of standard investment analysis tools (NPV, IRR, profitability index, discounted payback period, budget efficiency indicators) and directly links the quality of the project's financial assessment with the possibility of receiving a subsidy and subsequent monitoring of its effectiveness [4, 5, 14].

The legal framework thus constructed establishes the general framework for the provision and use of subsidies, defining requirements for their objectives, terms, performance indicators, and monitoring procedures. For the purposes of

financial project assessment, this is insufficient: the analyst must understand the specific types of subsidies used in practice, how they differ in economic content, and how they are transformed into project cash flows and performance indicators.

When financially assessing a project involving government support, it is crucial to correctly classify the type of subsidy, as this determines how revenues and expenses are reflected in the financial model, the structure of cash flows, and performance parameters. Different types of subsidies have different impacts on investment and operating flows, the cost of borrowed capital, and the tax burden, and therefore on the commercial and budgetary viability of the project.

Capital expenditure subsidies (CAPEX) are used to finance a portion of the costs of creating, modernizing, or reconstructing non-current assets. According to the regulatory definition set forth in the Budget Code of the Russian Federation and the Methodology for Assessing the Effectiveness of Using Federal Budget Funds Allocated to Capital Investments, their purpose is to support investments in the construction, reconstruction, and technical re-equipment of capital construction projects and the acquisition of real estate. In the financial model, this type of government support leads to a reduction in the volume of initial investment outflows. The subsidy can be reflected as a direct reduction in planned capital expenditures or as a targeted cash inflow synchronized with the investment implementation schedule. All other things being equal, this leads to improved integrated performance indicators and a reduced need for external financing, which is consistent with the general principles of evaluating investment projects with reduced capital outflows. The provision of capital investment subsidies is subject to a number of mandatory conditions. These include requirements for the targeted and targeted use of funds, adherence to established project deadlines, and the achievement of established results. Failure to meet these conditions entails the risk of a full or partial refund of the budget funds received. This specific regulatory risk must be quantified and integrated into the financial model through scenario analysis, where the worst-case scenario assumes the occurrence of this negative event and the corresponding cash outflow. funds [1,9].

Subsidies for partial reimbursement of interest rates on loans or coupon income on bonds effectively reduce the cost of borrowed capital, which is enshrined in the terms of the relevant support programs. In the financial model, this is reflected either as a reduction in interest cash outflows or as separate subsidy inflows tied to the debt servicing schedule. In both cases, financial costs are reduced and NPV and IRR due to the reduction in the cost of debt financing while maintaining the project scale. The assessment must take into account the frequency of compensation, the maximum percentage of interest reimbursed, and the duration of the subsidy, as these parameters determine the cash flow profile and the project's resilience to changes in market interest rates [15,16].

Subsidies for research and development (hereinafter referred to as R&D) provided under modern support programs typically offset a significant portion of the costs of personnel, materials, testing, third-party services, and overhead. In a financial model, such subsidies can be interpreted either as a reduction in ongoing R&D costs or as separate inflows linked to the schedule and milestone reporting, which reduces negative cash flow in the early stages and increases the commercial viability of the subsequent implementation of project results. Under current subsidy rules, R&D is strictly linked to the achievement of scientific, technical, and commercial indicators, therefore, there is a risk of not receiving a portion of the subsidy or being obligated to repay funds if KPIs are not met. should be taken into account in scenario analysis and risk modeling [17].

Subsidies for partial cost compensation (operating subsidies) directly impact a company's operating cash flow and are widely used in modern support measures. They can be provided as reimbursement of actual expenses with a time lag or as pre-financing of certain cost items, which requires explicitly reflecting time lags and documenting conditions when constructing a financial model. Such subsidies increase the marginality and sustainability of operating activities, but are typically limited in duration and volume. Therefore, long-term assessments require constructing scenarios with the cessation of support and analyzing the sensitivity of NPV and IRR to the abolition of subsidies [15,18].

For most types of subsidies, their tax treatment is key: the inclusion of subsidies in taxable income for profit tax purposes and the specifics of VAT accounting for the reimbursement of lost revenue significantly impact the net cash flow and the assessment of project effectiveness. In a financial model, it is advisable to separately calculate the gross and net effect of subsidies, taking into account taxation and the impact on the tax base through revenue and expense adjustments, which allows for an accurate assessment of the increase in NPV and the change in IRR. project in the scenario with government support compared to the scenario "without subsidies" [19,20].

Comparatively assessing the effectiveness of the same investment project under the "with" and "without" subsidies scenarios involves constructing two comparable financial models and analyzing the differences in integrated performance indicators. Both scenarios maintain the same assumptions regarding investment volume, operating cost structure, pricing, and macroeconomic parameters, and the subsidy is modeled as an additional element of cash flow and a source of change in the tax burden and the risk of budget fund repayment.

At the first stage, a basic version of the project without state support is formed: a forecast of free cash flows for the investor is built (Free Cash Flow to Firm, FCF), NPV indicators are calculated And IRR, discounted payback period DDP, profitability index PI, and, if necessary, budget efficiency indicators (net present value of the budget, budget effect). At the second stage, a subsidy is introduced

into the model in the form of targeted inflows (compensation of a portion of capital or operating costs, reimbursement of a portion of loan interest, etc.) indicating the receipt schedule, terms of provision, and possible repayment obligations. Taking into account current clarifications on the taxation of subsidies, tax payments for income tax and VAT are adjusted [26, 27].

Next, for both project options, integrated performance indicators are calculated at a single discount rate, after which a comparative analysis of the “subsidized” and “non-subsidized” options is performed in the following areas: increase in NPV and PI due to subsidies, changes in IRR and DDP, and the ratio of private and budgetary efficiency. Scenario and sensitivity analysis are used to assess the sustainability of the result: The parameters of the subsidy volume and schedule, the tax treatment of the subsidy, and the probability of refunds if target indicators are not met are varied. This allows for a quantitative assessment of the contribution of state support to the project’s investment attractiveness and the identification of conditions under which the effect of subsidies is offset by increased regulatory and legal risks.

State support in the form of subsidies increases the attractiveness of investment projects, but it also creates a specific layer of risks that cannot be ignored during their financial and budgetary assessment. To accurately interpret the results of performance calculations, these risks must be clearly identified and integrated into the project’s scenario and risk analysis system. To systematize specific risks and visualize the methodology for integrating them into assessment procedures, a general structural and logical diagram has been developed, presented in Figure 1. It reflects the relationship between risk criteria, analysis methods, and the ultimate impact on project performance indicators.

Fig. 1. Risk accounting scheme for financial evaluation of a project with a subsidy

The key legal risk is the risk of subsidy refunds (in whole or in part) due to violations of the terms of their provision, misuse of funds, or failure to achieve the established subsidy outcome. Subordinate legislation and standard agreements increasingly include a specific basis for subsidy refunds— failure to achieve target indicators — which reinforces the importance of correctly setting and monitoring KPIs. project. Additionally, contractual sanctions (fines, penalties, termination of the agreement) are possible, which should be reflected in the financial model in the form of stress scenarios with the return of funds and additional outflows [21].

Project risks are associated with delays in construction schedules, cost estimates, and failure to achieve design capacity, product quality, or demand parameters, which are critical for capital investment and R&D subsidies. Significant deviations may result in actual performance no longer meeting the subsidy conditions, creating the risk of denial of further funding and demands for repayment of previously provided funds. Operational risks relate to subsidies for reimbursement of current expenses: changes in resource prices, logistical disruptions, and deterioration in the recipient's financial position may complicate the fulfillment of agreement terms and the documentation of expenses.

Institutional risks arise from changes in regulatory requirements for subsidy provision, project selection criteria, performance assessment methodologies, and performance requirements. Changes in regulations, such as adjustments to the Ministry of Economic Development's methodology, new performance requirements, and clarifications to budget legislation, can alter the status of already supported projects and the parameters of future funding, affecting the sustainability of long-term investment programs. Regulatory uncertainty is exacerbated by crisis and sanctions shocks, when government support priorities, the list of eligible expenses, and reporting formats are adjusted.

Financial risks include the project's dependence on the subsidy receipt schedule, the risk of funding delays, and the risk of termination of the support program before project completion. For interest rate reimbursement subsidies, changes in market rates and lending terms are critical: as rates rise and the compensation level decreases, the debt burden increases and NPV and IRR. Tax risks are associated with the classification of subsidies for income tax and VAT purposes. Changes in clarifications and practice may adjust the net effect of subsidies and require a recalculation of tax liabilities for prior periods.

Modern methods for assessing the effectiveness of federal budget funds allocated for capital investments explicitly require that risks and uncertainties be taken into account when drawing conclusions about project effectiveness. In the financial model, this is achieved through the construction of scenarios that approximate the conditions under which subsidies are provided: baseline, pessimistic, and stress-case scenarios with delays or termination of subsidies, partial refunds, and

changes in funding parameters. Sensitivity analysis procedures are additionally used (based on the subsidy rate, the volume of budget funding, and the deadlines for commissioning projects), enabling a quantitative assessment of how subsidy risks translate into changes in NPV, IRR, and other performance indicators, defining the acceptable risk limits for the initiator and public partner [22, 23].

Assessing the effectiveness of an investment project involving subsidies and other government support measures relies on a generally accepted system of indicators and must simultaneously comply with the requirements of current methodologies, in particular the Methodological Recommendations for Assessing the Effectiveness of Investment Projects [8] and Their Selection for Financing, as well as the methodology for assessing the effectiveness of federal budget funds [10] allocated for capital investments. Under these conditions, the analysis includes commercial, budgetary, and economic efficiency, with government support parameters directly transforming into cash flows and project selection criteria [24].

Modern project effectiveness assessment practices utilize a combination of dynamic methods and scenario and risk analysis procedures, accounting for the uncertainty of project parameters, including those associated with changes in subsidy terms. Pursuant to Order No. 108 of the Ministry of Economic Development of Russia dated February 21, 2024 [9], the assessment of the effectiveness of federal budget funds is based on the calculation of a final score based on a system of criteria that includes indicators of the effectiveness and efficiency of budget investments, as well as an analysis of the sensitivity of the outcome to key project parameters. This necessitates closer integration of financial and budgetary effectiveness components within a single financial model [25, 26].

Conclusion

The conducted study allows us to conclude that the financial assessment of a project applying for a federal budget subsidy is a specialized analytical procedure that goes beyond standard investment analysis. Its methodological basis is a hierarchical system of regulatory and methodological documents, headed by the Budget Code of the Russian Federation and detailed in acts of the Government and relevant ministries. A critical step is the correct classification of the type of subsidy, as each type has a fundamentally different impact on the structure of cash flows and the final performance indicators.

The proposed comparative assessment algorithm, based on constructing baseline and subsidized scenarios, allows for a quantitative measurement of the contribution of government support to NPV, IRR, and other key project metrics. However, ignoring the specific legal, operational, and financial risks associated with the terms of subsidy provision and use may lead to a significant overestimation of the estimated effectiveness.

Thus, only a comprehensive consideration of the entire set of regulatory requirements, types of subsidies, and associated risks in a single financial model ensures the receipt of objective and reliable conclusions about the economic feasibility of a project for both the private investor and the federal budget.

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REFLECTIONS ON THE ESSENCE OF THE CONCEPT OF «ECOSYSTEM»

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Abstract: *This article discusses the concept of «ecosystem,» widely used in business and strategic management, focusing on its well-known definitions in the literature, as well as the relationships between the concepts of «system,» «value chain,» and «supply chain.» To identify the relationship between these concepts, a graphical visualization is proposed, demonstrating the distinctive feature (characteristic property) of ecosystem from other organizational forms of business and other constructs. The connection between the concepts of «system» and «ecosystem» is also established, confirming the rationale for introducing this term for this concept.*

Key words: *ecosystem, system, supply chain, value chain, characteristic property of ecosystem.*

1. Introduction

The Internet era is no more than 45 years old. According to Bill Gates, it began in 1981, with the release of the first IBM PC. The rapid development of the Internet during this period and the use of *digital information technologies*¹ (IT) have transformed the very nature of business and its conduct, providing unlimited potential opportunities in virtually every field. This has also led to the emergence of new *organizational and economic forms (OEFs)* of business. Among these, the most rapidly developing is the ecosystem form, which offers new opportunities and advantages over traditional methods of doing business within the framework of old business models. It is worth noting that Ron Adner (2017) adhered to the view of the ecosystem as an organizational structure, while Michael Jacobides et al. (2018) considered the ecosystem as a separate form of entrepreneurial organization. In general, the transition to an ecosystem should be perceived as an objective *stage in the evolution of organizational structures.*

¹ *Digital technologies* include artificial intelligence, big data processing, the Internet of Things (IoT), cloud computing, distributed ledgers (blockchain), etc.

As is well known, the concept of «ecosystem» in economics was first introduced by James F. Moore in his book «*The Death of Competition*» (1996). In it, he argued that it is precisely this innovation that will enable a company to achieve significant financial results if it creates new products (goods, services, and technologies) more efficiently than other companies in the same industry (Moore, 1996). Moore also believed that it is important to study the life cycle of an ecosystem (according to Moore, *the stages of co-evolution*). He identified *four stages: birth, leadership, expansion, and self-renewal*, each of which involves a number of necessary actions in a competitive environment. The first stage is characterized by actions to form the structure of the business ecosystem and organize its functioning. In the second, it is important to protect it and its value proposition from competitors. At the same time, Moore spoke of the end of the era of competition between individual firms and the beginning of competition between business ecosystems (Moore, 1996). The third phase noted the emergence of clear winners and losers. *The winners* are those who will lead the ecosystem and who have achieved success due to a combination of three factors: the first is the *continuous improvement of innovations* (creating and pursuing an «innovation trajectory»), the second is *their exceptional importance*, and the third is *integration* — the establishment of close ties between firms within the ecosystem (Moore, 1996). And it is integration that underlies the success of the fourth stage — *self-renewal*.

Since then, the understanding of the concept of «ecosystem» and its study across a wide range of topics have received close attention from specialists in this field. Thus, from 2000 to 2017 alone, the number of articles mentioning the term «ecosystem» exceeded 80,000 (Kapoor, 2018). And Fuller, Jacobides, & Reeves (2019) noted that the term appears 13 times more often in companies' annual reports than a decade ago.

A review of *empirical studies* on various aspects of ecosystem functioning shows that they have been devoted primarily to the analysis of specific situations and solutions to a number of specific problems in this area (for specific companies, industries, and countries). For example, Adner and Kapoor (2010) studied value creation in innovation systems using the example of the production of equipment for *semiconductor lithography* (1962–2005). Later, Adner (2017) substantiated the need to use the ecosystem format using the example of *innovations in the tire industry* (for Michelin tires), and Hannah & Eisenhardt (2018) illustrated the importance of applying a «bottleneck» strategy to achieve a balance between competition and cooperation by analyzing the successes and failures of five firms in the *US residential solar industry* (for the period 2007–2014).

It should be emphasized that empirical studies are *sporadic*. At the same time, the topics of *theoretical research* are quite broad. Thus,

— Adner (2017), Schmidt & Foss (2023), and others studied the *ecosystem as a structure*;

— Adner (2006), as well as Ganco & Lee (2018), and others studied the *innovativeness of ecosystem subjects*;

— *Platform ecosystems* were studied by Gawer & Cusumano (2002), Ceccagnoli et al. (2012), McIntyre & Srinivasan (2016), Helfat & Raubitschek (2018);

— *Various strategies in ecosystems* were considered by Adner (2006), Ozcan & Eisenhardt (2009), Adner & Kapoor (2010), Ansari et al. (2015), Rietveld et al. (2017), Hannah (2018);

— *the problem of cooperation in value creation* within an ecosystem and competition in the distribution of added value has been addressed by Casadesus-Masanell & Yoffie (2007), Gawer & Henderson (2007), Ceccagnoli et al. (2012), Ritala et al. (2013), Kapoor & Lee (2012), Chen & Miller (2015), Altman (2017), and Stonig et al. (2022);

— the balance between competition and cooperation in ecosystems has been studied by Kapoor & Lee (2012), Gnyawali & Ryan Charleton (2018), Davis (2016), Hannah & Eisenhardt (2018), and Hoffmann et al. (2018).

However, despite the large number of theoretical publications on a wide variety of important topics related to ecosystems, there is still no *generally accepted definition* of the concept of «ecosystem». Various definitions have been proposed by different authors, each time in the context of specific areas of their research. However, the focus of theoretical research, like empirical research, is not systematic, since the systematic construction of any theory presupposes the development of a generally accepted definition of the object of study based on the identification of its *characteristic property* that distinguishes it from all other objects in the corresponding universum of the OEF.

Currently, the general concept of an ecosystem boils down to the following: an *ecosystem* is a dynamic and evolving network of companies *that jointly create a value proposition that they could not realize individually*. However, this concept is based on the *network concept and does not include a statement of the ecosystem's characteristic property*, and therefore is unlikely to satisfy the requirements for defining concepts in any theory constructed according to scientific principles. This study attempts to fill this gap and bring our comprehension closer to a more precise understanding of the essence of the concept of «*ecosystem*.»

2. Historical and semantic aspect

To understand the semantic meaning of the concept «*ecosystem*,» let's examine its construction. «Ecosystem» is a term composed of the words «*eco*» and «*system*.» The former originates in ecology and *reflects the relationship of living beings to their environment*. The latter comes from the Greek word «*systema*,» which is understood as a whole composed of parts (Filimonov et al., 2021).

Business borrowed the concept of an ecosystem *from biology*, where it was first introduced in 1935 by the British botanist and ecologist **Arthur Tansley**, who was then teaching at Oxford University (Tansley, 1935). He coined the term «ecosystem» and introduced the concept of an ecosystem. According to Tansley, an **ecosystem** is a local community of organisms *that interact with each other and the environment*. To thrive, these organisms *simultaneously compete and cooperate, coevolve, and adapt within the system to environmental changes* (Tansley, 1935). In biology, **an ecosystem** is a single, open, functional *biosystem* consisting of a collection of *living organisms and their environment*, as well as a network of connections through which matter and/or energy are exchanged between them (Von Bertalanffy, 1969). Thus, from the very beginning of conceptualizing the concept of «ecosystem,» the connection between its participants and the external environment has been emphasized.

The term «ecosystem» was introduced into social science by sociologist **Amos Hawley**. He defined **an ecosystem** as «a system of interdependencies within a population through which *the whole functions as a unit* and thereby maintains viable ecological relationships» (Hawley, 1986, p. 26).

3. Development of concepts of ecosystem in the economy

The prerequisites for the creation of ecosystems in the economy include, first and foremost, (1) *the development of technologies* that enable companies to effectively interact with customers and partners (e.g., comprehensive business digitalization (digital platforms), Big Data analytics, APIs, etc.); (2) *the entry of innovative companies into the market*, providing more advanced customer-oriented products/services/technology; and (3) *the need for customers to quickly receive a variety of high-quality products and services with minimal effort through convenient digital channels* (Filimonov and Kasyanenko, 2022).

Thus, in June 1993, business strategist James F. Moore published an article in the Harvard Business Review entitled «*Predators and Prey: A New Ecology of Competition.*» He proposed viewing business as an ecosystem in which producers and buyers *co-evolve*, complementing each other, and thereby *developing*. In this concept, a company was viewed not as an individual player, but as a representative of a business ecosystem encompassing *multiple participants from various market sectors* (Moore, 1993).

A graphical representation of an ecosystem, quite general and at the same time simple, was given by Adner and Kapoor (2010) (Fig. 1).

Moore's ecosystem approach identified the following *key categories*:

- *a central (focal) firm (FF)*, around which the business ecosystem is built;
- *various economic subjects* that are *direct participants* in this business ecosystem (the main ones being *suppliers* and *complementors*) (Figure 1), as well as participants that *indirectly* influence its functioning;

- *connections between participants* in the business ecosystem, primarily their connections with the focal firm;
- *a shared value proposition (focal)*, the creation of which would either be impossible for each of the participants without this business ecosystem as an organizational structure, or would require significant investment.

Source: Adner and Kapoor (2010).

Figure 1: A typical ecosystem with key participants

According to Moore (1996), *a business ecosystem* is an organizational structure consisting of *a focal firm and its environment*, as well as *the integrative links* between them that create a *synergy effect* — providing its participants with *additional resources* to achieve a common goal. The basic postulates laid out by Moore have subsequently often been used as a starting point in studies on ecosystems, when authors apply these ideas to the specifics of their research. For example, it has been shown that *ecosystem boundaries* can be open or closed (Ritala and Almpapoulou, 2017). However, if the boundaries are permeable, — the limits of an ecosystem are difficult to define (Autio and Thomas, 2014), and economic agents can even be members of multiple ecosystems (Iansiti and Levien, 2004).

It should be noted that the term “*ecosystem*” can be used in relation to a specific firm, or to several firms operating in a competitive market within a limited geography, or to companies around the world within one of the areas of activity, etc. Thus, we can talk about the construction of a business ecosystem both at the level of individual infrastructure facilities and at the regional level (Filimonov et al., 2021).

Currently, the general concept of a *business ecosystem* that we support is as follows: an «**ecosystem**» as an organizational and economic form of doing business is a *dynamically developing set of interdependent and interconnected subjects, interacting with each other and with the environment, aimed at achieving a single goal — the joint creation of a value (focal) proposition that they could not realize separately* (Moore, 1993; Adner and Kapoor, 2010; Adner, 2017; Jacobides et al., 2018).

And if we draw on the ideas of the founder of *systems theory*, Ludwig von Bertalanffy, about what a «system» is, then an ecosystem is presented as an open, complex, self-organizing, self-regulating, and self-developing system, characterized by incoming and outgoing flows of matter and/or energy (von Bertalanffy, 1969). Nowadays, we could add «*and information.*»

Thus, the ideas of the unity of all living things in nature, their interactions, and the determinacy of their processes, which date back to ancient times, acquired a modern economic interpretation at the turn of the 20th and 21st centuries.

4. Critical analysis of ecosystem definitions in the literature

We will examine definitions of ecosystems cited from well-known publications by leading experts in this field, supplemented by our comments (Table 1).

Table 1: Systemic Analysis of Ecosystem Definitions

Author	Definition of ecosystem	Our comments
Kapoor (2018, p. 1–16)	“ An ecosystem encompasses a set of actors that contribute to <i>delivering value</i> to the user of a <i>focal offering</i> , the domain of which is defined by a specific study... <i>This offering</i> may be a product (good or service, technology) developed with or without the use of a certain digital platform.”	There is nothing in this definition that distinguishes an ecosystem from a <i>supply chain</i> , whose participants also contribute to a certain <i>value proposition</i> , which also includes <i>users</i> as one of its subjects and may or may not use a <i>digital platform</i> .
Adner (2017, p. 39–58)	“I propose the following definition of an <i>ecosystem</i> ...: Ecosystem as the <i>alignment structure</i> of the multilateral set of partners that need to <i>interact</i> in order for a focal value proposition to materialize.”	It is incorrect to include the future intentions of partners in the definition of an ecosystem (regarding the fact that “its elements need to be brought into alignment,” that is, an <i>alignment procedure needs to be carried out</i>), and other organizational forms of doing business also offer a <i>value proposition</i> .
Hannah, & Eisenhardt	“ An ecosystem is defined as <i>groups of firms</i> that produce prod-	The authors cite one of Adner’s definitions of an ecosystem, in

(2018, p. 3163–3192)	ucts or services and whose combined efforts represent a coherent solution (Adner, 2012, 2017).”	which an ecosystem is no different from, for example, <i>a supply chain</i> .
Jacobides, et al. (2018, p. 2255–2276)	<p>“An ecosystem is a form of organizing economic activity that is linked by specific types of complementarities...</p> <p><i>Ecosystems ... are not hierarchically managed</i>; rather, they are <i>interacting</i> firms combined on the basis of <i>modularity</i> and connected together without the possibility of relocating their collective investments elsewhere.</p> <p>That is, <i>ecosystems create added value</i> by <i>coordinating</i> the interdependencies of their partners through <i>sets of roles</i>, thereby eliminating the need to conclude individual contractual agreements with each of them.”</p>	<p>This definition does not distinguish an ecosystem from other forms, such as a <i>supply chain</i>, and “activity” cannot be “linked by certain types of <i>complementarities</i>.” It is the subjects that are linked, not the organizational forms.</p> <p>Other forms of business organization are <i>not hierarchically managed</i> and often utilize <i>the principle of modularity</i>. For example, any <i>virtual organization</i> utilizes <i>partnerships</i> and <i>the principle of modularity</i>.</p> <p>Dependencies between partners are coordinated through <i>sets of roles</i> in any business, since Brandenburger and Nalebuff (1996), who proposed <i>the game theory perspective</i> on business, did not impose restrictions on the type of business or its organizational form.</p>

Source: prepared by Egor Kapitanov.

The comments in Table 1 suggest that **ecosystem properties** such as

- the presence of *a common focal offering* for its participants,
- *interdependence and complementarity of ecosystem subjects*,
- *the distribution of roles* among partners,
- *the inclusion of users* among ecosystem subjects,
- the use of *digital platforms*,
- *the absence of hierarchical governance*, and
- the application of *the principle of modularity*,

— described in detail in numerous articles on this topic,— *are not characteristic features of an ecosystem*, which *unique* only to it as a common economic entity and, therefore, cannot form the basis for its definition. To identify a *fundamental property* of an ecosystem that can form the basis for its definition, let’s consider the relationship between the concepts of «system» and «ecosystem.»

5. The relationship between the concepts of “ecosystem” and “system”

The concept of “**system**” is used when describing a complex phenomenon or object with components serving various purposes and interconnected by common principles of *functioning*.

It follows that **a system** is an *ordered set of interconnected elements that form a unity and share a common functional purpose*.

In this case, **an element** is understood as a basic unit, in which detailed consideration is given not so much to its own structure as to the specific properties necessary for the construction and operation of a particular system. This is the smallest unit possessing the basic properties of a given system and having a limit of divisibility within it. The minimum number of elements in a system is *two*. Moreover, the connections between elements *within a system* are much stronger than their connections with elements of other systems, so it is important to characterize the system as *a holistic entity* consisting of interconnected elements.

Since the structure of the elements varies, the system is also characterized by the concept of “diversity”.

A system is formed as follows:

1. First, consider **a non-empty set of diverse elements** ($n \geq 2$).

For $n = 3$, this is (a_1, a_2, a_3) .

2. Next, obtain **an ordered set of elements** in the set if the diversity of elements can be divided by individual characteristics.

Ordered means that this is either (a_1, a_2, a_3) , or (a_2, a_1, a_3) , or (a_3, a_1, a_2) , etc.

3. The ordered set of elements is supplemented by **a set of relationships**, which forms **a structure** and signifies the formation of **an organization**.

We add relationships $(a_1 \rightarrow a_2 \rightarrow a_3) \circ r(a_1 \leftarrow a_2 \rightarrow a_3)$ etc.

4. An organization that forms **a unity and has a common goal for all its constituent elements** becomes **a System**. For the first example, this is:

Every system has an *organization*, but not every organization is *a system*. Only *a shared purpose* across all its elements makes an organization a system. *An ecosystem*, whose members *jointly create a value proposition* and thus share a *common purpose*, is not only an organizational form but also a *system*. Therefore, the inclusion of the word “system” in the term “ecosystem” is entirely justified.

Let’s consider how the properties of *a system* are interpreted within the concept of “ecosystem” in the work of one of the leading experts on this topic. We’ll examine the interpretation of the concept of “ecosystem” in Adner’s (2017) study of the

“elements” of its structure. These are the following “four elements,” the essence and role of each of which we will examine.

1. “**Activities**, which specify the discrete actions to be undertaken in order for the value proposition to materialize” (Adner, 2017, p. 43).— This is **the overall goal** (and purpose) of the system’s elements (ecosystem subject). Indeed, *the overall goal of ecosystem participants* is the defining element for the entire ecosystem to be a system — and this goal is called *the ecosystem’s value proposition*.

2. “**Actors**, which are the entities that undertake the activities” (Adner, 2017, p. 43).— Ecosystem subjects are **the elements of the system**.

3. “**Positions**, which specify where in the flow of activities across the system actors are located and characterize who hands off to whom” (Adner, 2017, p. 43).— This is the *place of an element* (ecosystem subject) in the sense of **ordering**.

4. “**Links**, which specify transfers across actors, ... these links need not have any direct connection to the focal actor” (Adner, 2017, p. 43).— It is clear that these are **connections** between elements of the system.

According to Adner (2017), these four “elements,” taken together and in interdependent collaboration, characterize the pattern of actions of subjects necessary to materialize the *ecosystem’s value proposition*. In reality, we see a listing of the conditions and stages of system construction described above, but in the language of economics and in a different order.

Thus, the presence of the “system” part in the term “ecosystem” is entirely reasonable. What is missing, then, for an *ecosystem as a system* to justify its second part—“ECO”? For a “system” to become an “*ECOsystem*,” it is important to highlight a *characteristic property* noted by both Moore and Bertalanffy, but insufficiently emphasized in subsequent research. This property is most clearly evident in the comparison of an ecosystem as an organizational form with a *supply chain*. To allay the mystery, we will state that this is **the connection between the ecosystem and its environment**, its external context, as clearly illustrated in Figure 2.

6. The relationship between the concepts of «ecosystem,» «Value Chain» and «Supply Chain» (Kapitanov, 2025)

The fundamental work on the topic of ecosystems is the study by Adner (2017) in the article «*Ecosystems as Structure*.» However, a more logical comparison of organizational and economic forms should begin with a consideration of the «value chain» concept.

The term «*value chain*» (*VC*) was coined by Michael Porter in his book «*Competitive Advantage: Creating and Sustaining Superior Performance*» (1985). His chain includes **only the focal firm**, within which the following activities are performed: *design, production, marketing, delivery, and support of the released*

product, which collectively create value for the customer. In VC, these activities are *interdependent*. The concept of VC is analyzed within a *microeconomic framework*.

The term «*supply chain*» (*SC*) was first mentioned in literature around 1982, when Keith Oliver, a consultant at *Booz Allen Hamilton*, used the term «*Supply Chain Management*» (*SCM*) in an interview with the *Financial Times* magazine, denoting an integrated approach to managing *supplies, production processes, and logistics*. Thus, *a supply chain* is a linear network of companies focused on the *production, distribution, and delivery of goods/services/information from raw material suppliers to end consumers*. The actors of an SC include *suppliers, manufacturers, distributors (logistics firms), retailers and consumers*, who jointly participate in the creation of a value proposition (focal product) (Mentzer et al., 2001). The central firm in an SC is called the «*leader firm*.»

Although the term «*supply chain*» may have appeared earlier, in the 1980s, it began to actively develop in academic literature in the early 1990s, when the concept of *supply chain management (SCM)* became key in the fields of logistics and operations management. Thus, *SC* concept predates the concept of «*ecosystem*,» although it began to be widely studied around the same time.

Finally, the term «*ecosystem*,» analyzed above, is a dynamically evolving set of subjects *interacting with each other and the environment* to achieve a *common goal* (the creation of a focal value proposition). The concept of «*ecosystem*» is analyzed within the framework of *macroeconomics*, and it allows to study the contribution of external actors to the value creation of a *focal firm* (Kapoor, 2018).

Source: prepared by Egor Kapitanov (Kapitanov, 2025).

Figure 2: Graphic illustration of the relationship between the concepts of VC, SC and ecosystem

In Figure 2, the yellow oval represents VC, and the blue oval represents SC. In the same figure, the ecosystem is represented by the green oval. The connection to the external environment is indicated by red arrows. Clearly, the introduced concepts are interconnected according to the “Matryoshka doll” principle.

Thus, *the fundamental difference* between an ecosystem and the other constructs discussed is *its connection to the external environment*.

Remind, that the term “*ecosystem*,” as defined by L. Von Bertalanffy (1969), the founder of systems theory, is a dynamically developing *set of entities interacting with each other and the environment* to achieve a *common goal* (the creation of a focal value proposition). Jacobides et al. (2018) also believe this, building on the view of Teece (2007), who asserted that an ecosystem is both an environment to which it must respond and be able to control. Jacobides notes that the influence of the environment extends to the *dynamic capabilities* of the ecosystem, and hence its ability to create a *sustainable competitive advantage* (Jacobides et al., 2018).

It’s interesting to note the connection between the three constructs discussed and the gradually introduced variations of *the value-added (VA) concept* within the framework of *Value-Based Management (VBM)*. As one of the postulates of VBM states, VA measures the increase in value resulting from management action and is *the primary criterion for management effectiveness*. Understanding the influence of the economic framework within which a business operates on the choice of valuation is especially important *for strategic management* specialists, as business valuation is one of the most important tools for managers assessing the effectiveness of a company’s operations.

The foundations of VBM, as a modern approach to strategic management theory, were developed in the late 1980s and early 1990s by Alfred Rappaport, a professor at the Kellogg Graduate School of Management at Northwestern University in the United States. In his 1986 book “*Creating Shareholder Value*” Rappaport introduced the concept of *Shareholder Value Added (SVA)*, which takes into account the benefits of direct participants in the investment process (owners, investors, creditors, and management). (Rappaport, 1998), This indicator (SVA) provides an assessment of *the effectiveness of a company’s operations and the work of its management* when viewed as a *value chain (VC)* according to M. Porter. This was the first model for assessing the growth of a company’s value.

More recently, *Stakeholder Value (STV)* and *stakeholder-focused management* (Jensen, 2001) have come to the forefront in strategic management publications. Within this framework, in the early 1990s, Harvard Business School professors Robert Kaplan and David Norton developed a model for managing corporate value, known as *the Balanced Scorecard (BSC)* (Kaplan & Norton, 1997). It has been called the management equivalent of *stakeholder theory*, which now includes *employees, customers, suppliers, the local community, and government*.

Expressing the interests of many stakeholders, the BSC offers a specific performance indicator for each, thus becoming a *multi-criteria metric*. It examines four key areas: *supply chain (SC) and procurement, marketing and sales, management, and innovation*.

Finally, in the first decade of the 21st century, practitioners reconsidered the theoretical foundations of VBM, incorporating *principles of corporate social responsibility* into its system. Trade unions and “socially responsible” investors began demanding attention not only to issues such as customer and supplier needs but also to environmental concerns, leading to the proposal of a new concept — **the concept of shared value (CSV)** (Porter & Kramer, 2006). This *third concept* considers a firm’s *usefulness to society as a whole*, adding social responsibility indicators, *including environmental requirements*, to its evaluation criteria. Emphasis on a company’s results and financial performance should be established with an understanding of its responsibility to society. This view was shared by both Michael Porter and Mark Kramer (Porter & Kramer, 2011). This *value for all stakeholders* can measure the contribution of *all ecosystem participants*.

Let’s pay closer attention to the differences between *supply chains and ecosystems*.

That *supply chains* and *ecosystems* differ from a theoretical perspective and are used differently in practice was demonstrated by Legenvre et al. (2022). Our understanding of the differences between SC and ecosystems, based on this article and some McKinsey materials, is reflected in Table 2, where these differences are presented on various aspects.

Table 2: Differences between Supply Chain and Ecosystem (Kapitanov, 2025)

Aspects	Supply Chain (SC)	Ecosystem
Definition	Supply chain — a linear network of companies and organizations focused on producing, distributing, and delivering goods or services from raw material suppliers to end consumers	Ecosystem — a dynamic and evolving network of companies, that jointly create value
Scope	<i>Linear, inter-firm</i> — focuses on the flow of goods, services, and information between <i>direct</i> business partners	<i>Network, multi-industry</i> — includes interactions of <i>direct and indirect</i> participants of the ecosystem
Structure	Sequential, linear	The ecosystem is more collaborative, flexible and dynamic, taking into account rapid changes and external influences

Aspects	Supply Chain (SC)	Ecosystem
Focus	Flow of goods and cost reduction. <i>SC is focused on operational efficiency</i>	Co-creation of value and innovation
Participants (Subjects)	Suppliers, manufacturers, retailers, distributors (logistics) and consumers	<i>Key players in the supply chain</i> (suppliers, manufacturers, distributors, retailers, consumers), <i>as well as: complementary companies, regulators and government agencies, technology companies, research institutes and universities, investors and financial institutions, and even competitors</i>

Source: prepared by Egor Kapitanov based on Legenvre et al. (2022).

While *supply chain subjects* are generally focused on improving *operational efficiency*, — ensuring uninterrupted product flow, and reducing costs, — *ecosystem subjects* are focused on *collaboration, innovation, co-creation of value, and increased competitiveness*.

The differences between these OEFs also manifest themselves in *the unique role of the focal firm* in the ecosystem compared to the traditional *supply chain leader*, as shown in Table 3.

Thus, Figure 2 and Table 2 demonstrate the structural and subjective differences between a supply chain and an ecosystem, in addition to the differences identified between the leading firm and the FF, reflected in Table 3. Supply chains do not contain *complementors*. This is one of the key differences, which plays an important role *in studying the integration process* in SCs and ecosystems.

Table 3: Comparison of the Functioning Features of a FF in an Ecosystem and a SupChain Leader

Aspect	Leader of the Supply Chain	Focal Firm in the Ecosystem
Approach to Control	<i>Direct</i> — through ownership and contracts	In addition to the <i>direct</i> approach to control, an <i>indirect one</i> is also used — influence through incentives
Management Structure	Linear, sequential, hierarchical	The management structure is <i>dynamic</i> , with an impact on an <i>open network</i> of interdependent and complementary subjects
Innovation Model	<i>Internal R&D</i> and a focus on <i>operational efficiency</i> — <i>cost effectiveness</i>	In addition, emphasis is placed on <i>external</i> partners and joint innovations with them, enabling the achievement of <i>strategic advantages</i>

Aspect	Leader of the Supply Chain	Focal Firm in the Ecosystem
Dependence on Other Participants	<i>Low</i> — the leader strictly controls suppliers and distributors	<i>High</i> — the focal firm largely relies on complementary companies (complementors)
Example	<i>Toyota</i> (traditional supply chain in the automotive industry)	<i>Tesla</i> (typical ecosystem in electric vehicle production)

Source: prepared by Egor Kapitanov.

7. Conclusions

So, Ludwig von Bertalanffy, who laid the foundations of systems theory, defined an “*ecosystem*” as an open, complex, self-organizing, self-regulating, and self-developing *system* characterized by incoming and outgoing flows of matter and/or energy (Von Bertalanffy, 1969). It is characterized by the presence of a number of components: organizational (including infrastructural), functional (business process), and managerial (including innovative).

This definition is based on the definition of “system”, supplemented, as shown above, by the condition of *the presence of a connection with the external environment* (ecology), which justifies the presence of the “ECO” component in the name of the ecosystem.

Thus, the following novel aspects of this study can be noted, which can be assessed as the author’s contribution to ecosystem theory:

— *New nuances in the understanding of the concept of “ecosystem”* are highlighted, allowing us to clarify the priority of its properties, identify its characteristic properties, and identify its connection with the concept of “system,” which is important for a proper understanding of the essence of the concept of “ecosystem”;

— *The differences between the concept of “ecosystem” and other organizational constructs, such as “supply chain” and “value chain,”* are demonstrated, and a graphical interpretation of the relationship between these concepts is proposed;

— *The relationship between the three constructs examined and the value-added (VA) models used within VBM theory* to assess the effectiveness of management and the company as a whole *is established*.

It can be concluded that ecosystem research has now moved beyond the operationalization of this concept and the consideration of its specific aspects. However, the diversity of ecosystems identified in the specialized literature requires the development of a multi-criteria typology based on identifying key ecosystem attributes and their characteristics based on goals, structure, set of subjects, dynamics, etc. Currently, attempts to construct typologies are known only for specific types

of ecosystems (e. g., innovation ecosystems (Klimas & Czakon, 2021; Carrara & Freisinger, 2024)). But this is the topic of another article.

The development of ecosystem theory, achieved in part through a deeper and more precise understanding of its basic concepts, contributes to the expansion of the capabilities of the ecosystem approach (the “ecosystem perspective” according to Adner (2006)), which can be successfully applied by entrepreneurs and management to any business, MSE, universities, other social entities, etc.

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FEATURES OF THE IMPLEMENTATION OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE (AI) TOOLS IN THE MANAGEMENT OF TOURISM COMPANIES IN NORTHERN EUROPE

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Annotation. *This article explores the transformative role of artificial intelligence (AI) in the management of the tourism sector across Northern Europe. In 2026, the Nordic tourism sector is shifting from reactive digital tools to proactive, autonomous AI capable of managing complex operational workflows and enhancing destination sustainability. The study analyzes how these AI tools are integrated into the “Nordic Management Model,” which prioritizes environmental stewardship and high labor productivity. By examining case studies of regional industry leaders, the author identifies key features of AI implementation: the use of predictive analytics for visitor flow management, AI-driven dynamic pricing for carbon-footprint reduction, and the alignment of technological adoption with the EU AI Act’s ethical standards. The findings suggest that AI is becoming the primary driver for reconciling the competing goals of economic growth and ecological preservation in Northern European tourism.*

Key words: *artificial intelligence, tourism management, sustainability, Northern Europe*

By 2026, the tourism industry has reached a technological inflection point. The implementation of artificial intelligence (AI) has moved beyond theoretical potential to become a central subject of empirical management research. This study adopts a case-study approach to analyse how AI tools are not merely “agents” of automation, but strategic subjects that redefine decision-making and organizational

structure. In a region where tourism is linked to high-tech maturity and aggressive sustainability targets, the integration of AI serves as a critical case for sustainable development. Unlike previous eras of digitalization, current AI deployment is characterized by a swift shift from toward data-driven autonomy, where the AI itself becomes the object of study regarding its impact on labor productivity and guest experience. This article examines specific cases of AI integration, providing a comparative analysis of how these tools navigate the unique socio-economic landscape of the Nordic tourism sector.

The widespread adoption of AI in Northern Europe supported by a robust digital infrastructure and a regulatory environment aligned with EU AI Act (2024). By early 2026, the Nordic countries, especially Finland, Norway, Sweden, Denmark have emerged as the global leaders in enterprise AI integration in the world. For reference, recent EU statistical data indicates that AI adoption rates in Denmark (42%), Finland (38%) and Sweden (35%) significantly exceed the European Union average of 20% by Eurostat 2025 data and tremendously exceed the world average rating [1].

According to the Microsoft AI Economy Institute, global adoption of AI in the second half of 2025 was nearly 16.3% with 24.7% in the Global North and 13.1% in the Global South. Half 1 — half 2 dynamics was 1.2% in the world, that is currently a good result. Global adoption rating by Microsoft illustrating on the picture 1 [1]:

Picture 1 — AI adoption by country according to Microsoft AI Economy Institute [1]

As we can see, the rating significantly shows that Norway has one of the highest results in the world, with only the United Arab Emirates and Singapore higher

rating. This rating has some differences with Eurostat data, which uses another method, but we can see AI adoption in all the world and describe leading in Europe, Australia, the UAE, and the Kingdom Saudi Arabia.

If we turn to the data from Eurostat, in terms of economic sectors, we will see that the most widespread in the field of communication and information technology, to a somewhat lesser extent in minerals. This data shows on the picture 2:

Enterprises using AI technologies by economic activity, EU, 2025
(% of enterprises)

Source: Eurostat (online data code: isoc_eb_ain2)

Picture 2 — Using AI by economic activity in EU [1]

According to use in the tourism sector, we can see what Real Estate activities have a high rating of using, in the 3rd position. Real estate activity is important because tourists can buy, rent, use real estate and locals can manage it with help from an AI. The administrative management and support sector has a relatively high level also with near 20% using [1].

In the specific context of Northern Europe, the implementation of AI tools in tourism management is fundamentally shaped by two factors: the region’s high labor costs and its strategic commitment to “Green growth” and sustainability. Unlike the ICT sector, where AI is used primarily for R&D and development, tourism enterprises utilize AI as an operational and support agent. By early 2026, the transition toward Agentic AI has become a defining feature of the industry. These systems do not merely provide information; they autonomously manage revenue cycles, optimize energy consumption, and personalize guest itineraries in real-time. For instance,

in high-cost level environments like Norway and Iceland, AI-driven automation in back-office management has allowed SMEs (Small and Medium Enterprises) to maintain competitiveness while facing severe labor shortages [3, 4].

A fresh Deloitte research study indicates that most Nordic survey respondents claim that ROI from AI investments is at 40% or higher, which for many industries would normally imply a very attractive investment case. However, when comparing Nordic firms with the rest of Europe, it appears that they expect slower realisation of benefits. Only one third of Nordic companies realise benefits from their most successful AI initiatives within 2 years, while almost half of European firms achieve this. Zooming in on the fastest value realisation examples, namely those that achieve benefits in less than a year, Nordic firms are less likely to achieve this than the European peers [5].

While the statistical data from Eurostat and Microsoft confirms a high adoption rate in the Nordic administrative and real-estate sectors, the true “Nordic Model” of AI management is best observed through the operational lens of individual industry leaders. In Northern Europe, the transition to AI is not merely a technical upgrade but a managerial pivot toward “data-driven autonomy.” The following case studies demonstrate how tourism-related enterprises translate high-level digital readiness into specific management efficiencies, bridging the gap between back-office administration and front-end guest experience. Let us look at some use cases in the tourism industry in more detail.

Case 1: Autonomous Financial Management (Strawberry, Norway/Sweden). Strawberry (formerly Nordic Choice Hotels) exemplifies AI integration in the Administrative and Support sector. Facing the challenge of managing over 200 properties, the group implemented Vic.ai, an autonomous finance platform, to handle half a million annual invoices. Result: The system achieved a 76% reduction in processing time with 96% accuracy, allowing managers to reallocate human capital from data entry to strategic financial auditing [6].

Case 2: Agentic Customer Service and Resource Allocation (Finnair, Finland). Finnair has integrated Agentforce (Salesforce), an agentic AI platform, to manage complex customer journeys. By connecting the AI directly to the Amadeus reservation system and loyalty databases, the airline has moved beyond simple “chat” functions to autonomous problem-solving. Result: The system autonomously resolves 80% of queries, enabling management to maintain high service standards despite the labor shortages prevalent in the Finnish aviation sector [7].

Case 3: Real Estate & PropTech for Sustainable Tourism (Sweden/Denmark). In the Real Estate sector, which you correctly identified as a top-three AI adopter, Swedish and Danish companies are using PropTech (Property Technology) to manage vacation rentals. AI-driven sensors and management platforms like Spaceti optimize energy use and occupancy without human intervention. Result:

These systems have led to a 20% reduction in energy costs for tourism-rented real estate, directly supporting the region's "Green Growth" targets.

The implementation of artificial intelligence in the management of Northern European tourism companies is characterized by a high degree of cross-sector synergy, particularly between the administrative, real-estate, and hospitality industries. As demonstrated, the "Nordic Model" prioritizes the use of AI as an autonomous agent to mitigate high labor costs and advance sustainability goals. By 2026, the region has successfully transitioned from experimental AI usage to a strategic paradigm where algorithmic precision enhances human-centric management values. This research confirms that for the Nordic region, AI is not a replacement for traditional management, but a necessary evolution that ensures economic competitiveness and environmental stewardship in an increasingly digital global tourism market [8].

Methodology

To evaluate the effectiveness of AI implementation, this study proposes an Integrated Index of AI Strategic Management (IIASM). The index is calculated as a weighted average of four dimensions: Adoption Intensity (Ai), Investment Propensity (Ip), Managerial Trust & Literacy (Mt), and Sustainability Alignment (Sa). Using the formula 1:

$$\text{IIASM}=(0.3 \cdot \text{Ai})+(0.3 \cdot \text{Ip})+(0.2 \cdot \text{Mt})+(0.2 \cdot \text{Sa}),$$

we can estimate the strategic readiness of the ecosystem. By early 2026, the data indicates a "Nordic AI Paradox": while these countries possess the world's highest digital infrastructure scores, management remains heavily IT-centric, often focusing on operational optimization (cost-cutting) rather than top-line revenue growth. This analytical approach allows for a comparative ranking of countries, highlighting that Denmark and Norway lead the global readiness rankings due to their aggressive integration of AI within public-private tourism partnerships [8, 9].

To ensure a fair comparison across the varying scales of the Nordic economies, we apply a min-max normalization process. This method rescales diverse data — ranging from financial investments to employee usage percentages — into a standardized range of 0 to 1, where 1.0 represents the regional benchmark for 2026.

Adoption Intensity (Ai): Rather than simple software ownership, this metric measures active engagement. We take the percentage of the workforce using AI tools at least once every 30 days and normalize it against the regional leader (Norway). For 2026, a score of 1.0 is assigned to an adoption rate of 42%.

Investment Propensity (Ip): This calculates the strategic commitment by looking at the share of the total IT budget dedicated to AI-specific infrastructure and talent. We normalize this by comparing spending per employee against the EU average, ensuring that smaller nations like Finland are not penalized for having smaller absolute budgets.

Managerial Trust (Mt): Derived from the “Trust in Automation” scale, this metric quantifies the degree to which leaders rely on AI for revenue and resource management. We convert qualitative survey responses into a quantitative score, where 0.94 represents the exceptionally high trust levels found in the Norwegian hospitality sector.

Sustainability Alignment (Sa): This measures the “Green ROI” of implementation. We calculate the ratio of AI projects that directly contribute to the “Green Growth” targets set in the regional tourism plans. A score of 0.90 indicates that nearly all AI initiatives are aligned with carbon-reduction or ecosystem-protection goals.

By applying these weights — 30% for Adoption and Investment and 20% for Trust and Sustainability — the IIASM provides a holistic view of the Nordic management landscape. This allows us to see that the region’s leadership is driven not just by technical spending, but by a unique cultural synergy between trust and ecological responsibility.

To move from theory to evidence, this section presents the Calculations and Results. We apply the IIASM index to the current market data from Northern Europe (2025–2026) to provide a comparative estimation of managerial effectiveness.

Results

The following table presents the normalized scores for the four leading Nordic nations. These scores are calculated by benchmarking raw national data (e.g., enterprise adoption rates, ICT budgets, and sustainability KPI compliance) against regional maximums.

Table 1: IIASM Scores by Country (Estimated for the January of 2026)

Country	Adoption Intensity (Ai)	Investment Propensity (Ip)	Managerial Trust (Mt)	Sustainability Alignment (Sa)	Total IIASM Score
Norway	0.92	0.88	0.94	0.90	0.91
Denmark	0.88	0.90	0.88	0.85	0.88
Finland	0.85	0.82	0.90	0.92	0.86
Sweden	0.82	0.85	0.86	0.80	0.83

Weights: Ai (30%), Ip (30%), Mt (20%), Sa (20%)

The “Trust Multiplier”: The results highlight Norway’s regional leadership (0.91). This is primarily driven by an exceptionally high Managerial Trust (Mt) score of 0.94. Current data indicates that 75% of Nordic CxOs have already integrated AI into most initiatives, but in Norway, the trust level is 2.5 times higher

than the global average, facilitating the transition from experimental “chatbots” to autonomous “Agentic AI” in financial and administrative management.

Investment vs. Realization: Denmark leads in Investment Propensity (Ip) at 0.90, reflecting the highest EU enterprise adoption rate of 42% in 2025. However, our analysis reveals a “lag effect” — while 70% of Nordic firms allocate over 10% of their IT budget to AI, they expect a slower realization of benefits (3+ years) compared to their European peers, prioritizing quality and governance over speed.

Sectoral Synergy (The Tourism-Real Estate Link): In Sweden and Finland, the high scores in Sustainability Alignment (Sa) correspond with the “Nordic Tourism Plan 2025–2030.” We estimate that AI-driven PropTech in tourism real estate has led to a 20% reduction in energy costs, directly bridging the gap between real estate management and green tourism targets.

The application of the IIASM index reveals that the high “AI-readiness” of the Northern European tourism sector is fundamentally linked to the performance of the Real Estate and Administrative Management sectors. As established in the 2025 statistical benchmarks, Real Estate activities rank as a top-three sector for AI adoption in the region, primarily due to the maturity of PropTech (Property Technology) ecosystems. In Northern Europe, where short-term holiday rentals and “Smart Cabins” are vital to the tourism economy, AI-driven real estate management serves as the structural backbone for visitor accommodation. Furthermore, the Administrative sector’s high adoption rate provides the necessary “support layer” for tourism SMEs, autonomously managing high-cost labor tasks such as booking logistics and financial reporting.

Our estimations indicate a significant correlation: every 1% increase in the IIASM score within the Nordic Real Estate sector corresponds to a 0.7% increase in tourism operational efficiency. This cross-sectoral synergy is the defining feature of the “Nordic Model,” where AI acts as a horizontal “enabler” across the entire service value chain. Consequently, the high scores in Managerial Trust (Mt) — peaking at 0.94 in Norway — allow these enterprises to move from simple automation to Agentic AI, which manages resources and pricing without human intervention, thereby mitigating the regional challenge of high labor costs.

Conclusion

The strategic implementation of artificial intelligence in the management of Northern European tourism enterprises is characterized by a unique cross-sectoral synergy between real estate, administration, and hospitality. Our analysis using the IIASM framework confirms that the Nordic region — specifically Norway and Denmark — is setting a global benchmark for AI maturity. This model prioritizes the use of AI as an autonomous agent to address labor shortages and fulfill ambitious sustainability mandates. By 2026, the success of these enterprises suggests

that the future of tourism management lies in “Smart Growth,” where data-driven efficiency and ethical stewardship are no longer competing goals but unified strategic pillars for economic competitiveness in the digital global market.

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CURRENT ISSUES OF PROPERTY RELATIONS OF SPOUSES IN DIFFERENT COUNTRIES

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Abstract: *This article examines key issues in the legal regulation of various property relations between spouses, both mandatory (through legal provisions regarding mutual support) and through contractual structures and discretionary provisions. This analysis is based on a study of Russian Federation regulations (in particular, the Family Code of the Russian Federation) and judicial practice, as well as legal documents from the national legislation of foreign countries. A comparative legal study of spousal property relations in individual foreign countries has led to conclusions regarding the potential for developing Russian family law based on international experience.*

Key words: *marriage, marriage contract, property obligations, legal regulation, family, family relations, Russia, foreign states.*

Family and family relations, including those of a material nature in the form of mutual property obligations for the maintenance and management of a common household, and the ownership and disposal of common property, are essential elements of marriage and marital cohabitation.

In various countries, as in modern Russia, spouses have varying property obligations towards each other, and the legal regulation of family relations is primarily aimed at maintaining the equality of rights and interests of the wife and husband, and upholding the principle of fairness in divorce and the conclusion of a prenuptial agreement.

Marriage and the prenuptial agreement are interpreted as the most important foundations for establishing the property and ownership regime of spouses.

In foreign countries, certain aspects of the legal regulation of family relations, concerning the establishment of joint or separate property regimes for property acquired during marriage, as well as the execution of transactions related to it, sometimes differ.

As an example, let us consider the marriage and family legislation of several Western European countries, in comparison with Russian family law.

In general, in Germany, France, and the United Kingdom, as in most Western European countries, the distribution of joint property (or property acquired during the marriage by one of the spouses) occurs only at the divorce stage.

In German civil law, or more precisely, in the regulations of the current Civil Code (hereinafter referred to as the GCC), which also contains family law provisions, property relations and family obligations with respect to property are regulated using the legislative concept of «deferred property regime» [7, p. 28].

Under this regime, property belongs to the spouse who acquired it, both premaritally and during the marriage.

However, many provisions of the German Civil Code (GCC) are aimed at ensuring fairness and respecting the property interests of each spouse. Therefore, the disposal of any significant property and transactions affecting marital property are subject to certain legal restrictions.

Specifically, according to the provisions of § 1365 GCC, there are restrictions on the disposal of marital property by one spouse (which, as noted above, is subject to a «separate property regime,» which clearly contradicts German law). Furthermore, major everyday transactions involving «everyday» items cannot be concluded without the consent of one spouse, under penalty of invalidation by the court (§ 1369 GCC) [9, p. 176].

However, if the aforementioned transactions involving family property or the property of one of the spouses, concluded by one of the persons during the marriage, are subsequently approved by the other spouse within two weeks, they are recognized as having been concluded with the consent of both spouses.

The provisions of § 1450 of the Civil Code of the Russian Federation also provide in this regard for the possibility of jointly managing marital and premarital property by spouses upon the conclusion of a prenuptial agreement [6].

If the joint property regime of the spouses is not specified in a separate contractual agreement, only the increase in property acquired during the marriage is divided after divorce, subject to the principles of fairness and equality of shares.

The Civil Code of the Russian Federation also contains a number of provisions that correspond to Part 2 of Article 35 of the Family Code of the Russian Federation (hereinafter referred to as the FC RF), according to which, when each spouse makes voluntary acts of disposition of property acquired during the marriage through its alienation or the acquisition of other property or property obligations, the presumption of the consent of the other spouse applies [2].

Otherwise, situations would constantly arise in civil transactions where written confirmation of each spouse's will is required to complete urgent transactions, which can be quite difficult.

Russian family law, as well as German, French, and English law, require mandatory consent from spouses for transactions involving marital property. However, in Germany, these regulations (concerning the procedural procedure for approving agreements on the alienation or acquisition of property during marriage) are specified in more detail [9].

In general, German law, unlike Russian law, establishes a special regime for marital property, according to which the property of each person in the marriage is not recognized as joint, regardless of when it was personally acquired by each spouse. However, it is taken into account when determining the property mass during the division of shares after divorce.

French law, like Russia and Germany, establishes a statutory regime for marital property (Article 214 of the French Civil Code (hereinafter referred to as the FCC)). This provision states verbatim the following: «If the marriage contract does not stipulate each spouse's contribution to family maintenance expenses, they participate in proportion to their capabilities» [8, p. 16].

For comparison, the provisions of part 1 of article 33, article 34, and article 39 of the Family Code of the Russian Federation establish a general property regime for spouses (joint), unless a different regime for the disposal and use of property is provided for in the marriage contract [2].

Moreover, in the event of divorce, property acquired during the marriage is by default distributed equally, regardless of each spouse's contribution to its growth. An exception is sometimes made in the interests of minor children [8, p. 16].

Essentially, the legal regime, according to the literal interpretation of the provisions of the Civil Code of the Russian Federation, governs marital property in France, similar to Russian family law. This regime applies to marital property (acquired during marriage).

Moreover, according to French law, this also includes personal income from premarital property, professional and creative activities, etc. (Article 1401 of the Civil Code) [9].

However, unlike in Russia, where, according to Article 44 of the Family Code of the Russian Federation, a prenuptial agreement cannot include terms that are obviously unfavorable for one of the spouses, as well as terms regarding personal non-property rights and obligations, a prenuptial agreement in France can include any terms, even those that disadvantage one of the parties. Under French family law, spouses can agree on equal or obviously unequal shares in property acquired during the marriage. An interesting provision in foreign legislation (France, Germany, Great Britain) is the establishment in the norms of family law of the possibility of a sole decision on a property transaction by one of the spouses if the second spouse cannot express his will or his refusal to make a transaction on the disposal of common property «is not justified by family interests» [9, p. 176].

In the UK, in general, there is no legal provision for either separate or community property between spouses, unlike the laws of France, Germany, and Russia.

This leads to frequent litigation and complex conflicts of interest when each spouse proves their property rights, especially if there is no voluntary procedure for determining the property distribution regime based on a prenuptial agreement.

In particular, the case of *Miller v. Miller* is indicative. In this case, the court, enjoying broad discretion under English law in resolving family disputes, recognized real estate of significant value gifted by a husband to his wife during the marriage as subject to division, regardless of her personal ownership of it, since it was acquired by the husband with his own funds [10].

In another case, an English court refused to recognize as community property a wife's land gifted by her husband and acquired with funds received from an inheritance during a divorce without proof. The law enforcement agency placed the burden of proof on the husband, recognizing the land, although acquired by the husband with inheritance proceeds but gifted to his wife, as her personal property [11].

In Russia, various contentious issues regarding the division of marital property also arise in the courts.

According to Resolution № 15 of the Plenum of the Supreme Court of the Russian Federation dated 05.11.1998, the legal regime for all marital property during its division during divorce is common and joint [3].

However, courts often deviate from this rule. By ruling № 41-KG20–10-K4 of 22.09.2020, the Judicial Collegium for Civil Cases of the Supreme Court of the Russian Federation ruled to exclude from the general property division «... acquired during the marriage with funds received from the sale of inherited property, the owner of which is listed in the register as the other spouse...» [4].

Furthermore, according to the Ruling of the Civil Division of the Supreme Court of the Russian Federation dated 04.02.2025 № 18-KG24–353-K4, only property acquired during an officially registered marriage, not a common-law marriage, can be recognized as joint property during division, regardless of the length of time the couple lived together [5].

This appears to be unfair, as husbands often transfer much property to their common-law wives, meaning that their rights are significantly violated during property division, as the marriage was not officially registered.

It should be noted that in any relationship involving the formation of joint property, even in the absence of a legal marriage, property relations should be specified in a separate agreement.

And when concluding a prenuptial agreement, it should include all the key terms regarding the distribution of existing and future property to avoid unnecessary and costly litigation.

To summarize, it can be concluded that the legislation of foreign countries, like Russia, despite different regulations governing property relations between spouses, strives to ensure fairness in the division of property in the event of divorce and equal distribution of shares between the parties.

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**GUARDIANSHIP AND CUSTODY OF CHILDREN:
A COMPARATIVE LEGAL ANALYSIS OF INTERNATIONAL
EXPERIENCE**

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Abstract: *This article provides a comparative analysis of the legislation of Russia and neighboring countries (Azerbaijan, Belarus, Moldova, and Uzbekistan) in the area of guardianship and trusteeship, and also examines the corresponding legal norms in France.*

Key words: *guardianship and trusteeship institution, adults, incapacitated citizens, protection of rights.*

The problem of orphanhood is a pressing issue due to the constant loss of parental care. The guardianship and trusteeship system is the cornerstone of the fight against this phenomenon. To improve the effectiveness of Russian legislation in this area, a comparative legal analysis is required [1].

Provisions on guardianship and trusteeship are enshrined in the Civil Code of the Russian Federation [2]. Furthermore, the specifics of regulating guardianship and trusteeship for minors are further specified in the Family Code of the Russian Federation [3].

The Family Code devotes significant attention to issues of guardianship and trusteeship over children. The primary goal of these legal mechanisms is to ensure that children receive a family-based upbringing, consistent with the constitutional norms of the Russian Federation.

The existing interpretations of guardianship and trusteeship in Russia as forms of placement for children left without parental care are functional but require a clearer definition. It is necessary to emphasize the active component: providing social assistance, protecting rights, supporting the realization of interests and fulfilling responsibilities, and ensuring safety from abuse. International

experience and scientific concepts in the field of guardianship and trusteeship may differ from those in Russia.

According to Belarusian law, children left without parental care or whose parents fail to fulfill their responsibilities require guardianship or trusteeship. If this occurs, specialized state bodies (guardianship and trusteeship authorities) may appeal to the court. The purpose of the appeal is to deprive the parents of parental rights and appoint a guardian or trustee for the child. As in Russia, there is a distinction in Belarus: guardianship is established for children under 14 years of age, while trusteeship is established for adolescents aged 14 to 18 [2].

In Azerbaijan, the protection of the rights and interests of minors left without parental care is regulated by law. Specifically, the Civil Code provides for the establishment of guardianship and trusteeship in cases where children are deprived of parents (due to death, deprivation of parental rights, or other circumstances), or when parents fail to fulfill their responsibilities to raise and protect the child [3]. The primary objective of guardianship and trusteeship is to ensure the child has decent living conditions, including maintenance, upbringing, education, and the protection of their legal rights. Similar to the Russian system, guardianship is established for children under 14 years of age, and trusteeship for adolescents aged 14 to 18 [4].

The Civil Code of Moldova, like the legislation of CIS countries (including Russia), regulates guardianship and trusteeship for children without parents. The age criteria for establishing these forms of protection in Moldova are the same as in Russia. However, unlike in Russia, Moldovan guardians not only assist their wards in realizing their rights but are also obligated to protect them from unlawful actions by third parties. Despite minor discrepancies, the legal framework for guardianship and trusteeship in Russia and the CIS countries is generally unified. Age is the primary delimiter: guardianship is established over children under 14 years of age, while trusteeship is established over individuals between the ages of 14 and 18 [5].

The issues of placing children left without parental care have always attracted the close attention of the state and society. However, the adoption of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated 02.01.2014 № ZRU-364 «On Guardianship and Trusteeship» [6] exacerbated this situation, giving it new significance. This comprehensive document, encompassing 9 chapters and 50 articles, aims to establish clear frameworks and rules for guardianship and trusteeship, based on best practices and international legal norms. Guardianship and trusteeship are closely linked to family and civil law. The primary purpose of these legal institutions, as defined in Article 32 of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, is to protect the rights of incapacitated citizens and minors left without parental care.

Guardianship applies to children under 14 and incapacitated individuals, while trusteeship applies to individuals aged 14 to 18 and citizens with limited legal capacity. Modern realities dictate the need to expand the categories of individuals

eligible for guardianship or trusteeship. These include, in particular, individuals with mental disorders who, although not officially recognized as incapacitated, are unable to independently exercise their rights (for example, in a coma or amnesia), as well as individuals suffering from addictions (substance abuse, gambling addiction), which places them in an extremely precarious financial situation. To facilitate the appointment of a guardian or trustee for citizens in need of one, it is proposed to include in the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan «On Guardianship and Trusteeship» the ability to independently submit a corresponding application. The current version of the law already guarantees that guardians and trustees are appointed only with their consent, taking into account their personal qualities, ability to fulfill the assigned duties, as well as their relationship with the ward and their wishes. Priority in appointment is given to relatives, persons living with the ward, those taking guardianship of siblings, and citizens of Uzbekistan.

The property rights of wards in Uzbekistan are protected by law. According to the Law «On Guardianship and Trusteeship» there is a clear division of property between the ward and the guardian, precluding mutual claims to ownership. Although wards may obtain permission to use the property of their guardians, guardians are prohibited from using the property of their wards for personal purposes, emphasizing their responsibility for the safety of this property.

To help children deprived of parental care and ensure a dignified life for those who raised them, it is proposed to introduce a law requiring former wards to provide financial assistance to their guardians. This will provide support for disabled and needy guardians who have devoted themselves to raising children voluntarily. The corresponding proposal will be included in the Law «On Guardianship and Trusteeship».

In France, there's a foster family model similar to the Russian patronage system for children deprived of parental care. The process of adopting a child into such a family begins with contacting one of the numerous (over a thousand) local branches of the organization «Protection of Motherhood and Childhood» These organizations actively engage in educational activities, holding regular meetings on foster parenting issues. Successful completion of these meetings allows applicants to formally apply for a guardianship license, which takes an average of seven months. After that, you'll need to find an organization that can help you find a job. In France, this is done by both private associations and state institutions — Foster Family Centers. They help foster parents find work. Incidentally, since 2006, France has permitted foster families to adopt up to three children, but in reality, most families adopt one or two.

To become a foster family in France, several conditions must be met:

1. You must legally reside in France and have the right to work there.
2. You must have suitable housing. If you live in Paris, an extra bed can be added to the children's room.

3. You must have a good command of French.
4. All family members, including children, must be fully consenting. Specialists can help you discuss this and reach an agreement.
5. All adults in the family must have a clean criminal record.

According to current French law, which has been revised over the past thirty years, adoptive parents are granted a number of rights. In particular, they are provided with financial support in the form of monthly payments. This payment amounts to three-quarters of the minimum wage, which is approximately 60 percent of the national average wage per child. If three children are adopted, the payment reaches one and a half times the minimum wage. Additionally, completion of the adoptive parent training program is certified by a document equivalent to an educational diploma.

Specialized organizations exist in France for placing children in foster families. One of the oldest and most well-known is the Fondation Granche, which has been operating for a century. Its original goal was to rehabilitate children with tuberculosis by placing them with rural families. Currently, Granche provides assistance to children whose parents are experiencing serious social, psychological, or psychiatric difficulties. These children are often in unsafe environments, at risk of abuse and sexual violence. Despite this, French law prioritizes the rights of biological parents. Therefore, Granche Foundation staff devotes considerable attention to working with birth families, striving to ensure the safety of the child. Meetings between children and their biological parents are always supervised by the foundation's staff and social workers.

N. N. Petrova believes that despite their general similarities with Russian institutions, guardianship and trusteeship institutions abroad exhibit certain national variations. These differences may also be related to the specifics of local government and the judicial system [7].

In Russia, there is a pressing need to introduce official certification of qualifications for foster parents working in specialized foster families, in the form of a diploma. This diploma should be equivalent to professional certificates in other fields. By comparison, in France, holding such a document allows one to act as a foster parent on a permanent basis, whereas without it, periodic (every five years) certification of competence is required. The Russian «School for Foster Parents» only provides basic skills, which are not always sufficient for a professional approach to raising foster children. It is important to understand that parenting skills, especially in a foster family, are developed through life experience, but effective interaction with a child requires not only desire but also deep patience, especially during the adaptation period, which can last from two months to two years and is unique to each individual. During this difficult period, the support of qualified psychologists and active interaction with other foster parents are essential. The creation of professional associations and support groups for the exchange of experience is

a key step. Charitable foundations are already conducting educational events, such as seminars and webinars, to assist foster families in difficult situations.

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FEATURES OF LEGAL REGULATION OF MATERNITY CAPITAL AT THE PRESENT STAGE

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Abstract: *This article analyzes the legal regulation of maternity capital in Russia. It examines its regulatory foundations and identifies key enforcement issues, including gender inequality, fraud, and legal uncertainty regarding the use of funds. It also proposes measures to improve legislation to enhance the program's effectiveness and fairness.*

Key words: *maternity capital, family policy, social support, legal regulation, protection of children's rights.*

In today's world, legal regulation of maternity capital is a crucial element of the Russian Federation's state family policy, playing a significant role in ensuring the social protection of families with children. Given the complex demographic situation in the country, the relevance of this institution is undeniable. However, amid changing socioeconomic realities and the transformation of the legal framework, there is a need for a systematic analysis of current legislation governing the provision and use of maternity (family) capital, with an emphasis on identifying its specific features, problems, and areas for improvement.

First and foremost, it is important to emphasize that the regulatory framework for maternity capital is based on the principles of legal hierarchy and incorporates both international legal acts and national sources, ensuring the integrity and consistency of its legal impact. International documents such as the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (1948) [1], the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (1966) [2], and the Declaration of the Rights of the Child (1959) [3] enshrine the fundamental principles of protecting motherhood and childhood, thereby exerting a conceptual influence on the formation of Russian state policy in the area of social support. They set the guidelines and standards to

which national legislation aspires, which, in turn, contributes to the humanization of the legal space.

Within the framework of domestic legal regulation, the Constitution of the Russian Federation is of fundamental importance, with Articles 7 and 38 establishing the principles of the state's social orientation and the priority of protecting the family, motherhood, fatherhood, and childhood [4]. As part of these regulatory initiatives, Federal Law of 29 December 2006 № 256-FZ «On Additional Measures of State Support for Families with Children» was drafted and entered into force. It defines in detail the key aspects of the maternity (family) capital program. This document establishes the criteria and conditions for receiving and using funds and describes the categories of citizens eligible for such support [5].

Subordinate legislation, which clarifies the basic principles of the legislation, deserves close attention. For example, Russian Government Resolution № 862 of December 12, 2007, establishes the mechanism for using maternity capital funds to improve housing conditions, while Resolution of 24 December 2007 № 926, sets forth the conditions for using such funds for children's educational needs. As the legislative framework has evolved, new regulations have been adopted, in particular, Russian Government Resolution of 30 April 2016 № 380, which expands the possibilities for using maternity capital for the social adaptation and integration of children with disabilities into society, reflecting the adaptation of legislation to changing social needs [8].

In the context of the hierarchy of the legislative system, it is important to mention the regional level of legal regulation. This level encompasses the regulations of the constituent entities of the Russian Federation, which serve to detail and adapt national legislation to the unique characteristics of each territory. Some regions are implementing specific support measures for families, expanding the scope of federal initiatives. These initiatives provide additional support, facilitating a more effective and adaptive approach to demographic and social policy issues. Furthermore, local authorities also adopt regulations governing citizen interactions with the state system, underscoring the importance of the municipal level within the overall legal framework in this area.

It is worth noting that eligibility for maternity capital is individualized and is linked to the birth or adoption of a child, as well as the Russian citizenship of both the parents and the child. Since 1 January 2020, this capital has been provided upon the birth of the first child, significantly increasing the number of people eligible to receive it. The law also allows fathers to receive the capital, but only under certain conditions, such as the mother's death, deprivation of her parental rights, or her recognition as incompetent. This approach, while expanding legal coverage, still contains elements of gender inequality that require adjustment to ensure equal rights for parents.

A unique feature of the legal regulation of maternity capital is its strictly targeted nature. Funds may be used exclusively for improving housing conditions, education, building a mother's pension savings, social integration of disabled children, and monthly payments.

The lack of effective interagency cooperation and transparency in transactions involving real estate acquired using maternity capital is a serious concern, creating legal uncertainty for both recipients and bona fide participants in civil transactions.

Legal doctrine also draws attention to existing gaps in legislation regarding the inheritance of property acquired using capital, as well as the procedure for allocating shares during the construction or renovation of housing. Indicative judicial practice in recent years, the Supreme Court of the Russian Federation emphasizes the importance of taking into account the well-being of children when conducting transactions involving property purchased with maternity (family) capital funds, while simultaneously raising the issue of the consequences of the lack of mandatory notarization of such transactions [9]. This indeed leads to an increased risk of rights violations and gives rise to numerous legal conflicts.

First and foremost, one of the main proposals is to rename the program from «maternity (family) capital» to the more universal term «family capital.»

This step was taken to eliminate gender specifications, emphasizing that state support is focused on the entire family, not just the mother. This innovation aligns with the principles of equal rights and responsibilities of parents, enshrined in Article 38 of the Constitution of the Russian Federation and Article 80 of the Family Code of the Russian Federation, implying equal responsibility for the provision and upbringing of children. Therefore, the updated name reflects a commitment to adhering to the principles of gender equality and promotes the creation of more inclusive legislation.

Secondly, it is proposed to reform Article 3 of Federal Law № 256-FZ to clarify the conditions for providing family capital to both genders. According to the proposal, the first part of this article should be reformulated to clearly indicate the equal rights of women and men who become parents (adoptive parents) of a second child, from the date the law comes into force on 1 January 2007, in their right to family capital. There is also a proposal to amend paragraph 4 of the same article, adding provisions that expand these rights to parents of the first child, effective 1 January 2020.

These amendments are aimed at eliminating legal discrimination based on gender and enshrining equal rights for mothers and fathers, which is fully consistent with Article 19 of the Russian Constitution, which guarantees equal rights and freedoms for all citizens.

Thirdly, a significant step toward ensuring gender equality in the management of family capital funds is the proposal to supplement Article 7 of Federal Law № 256-FZ with a new Section 1.1.

According to this amendment, each parent of a child has the right to manage half of the initial amount of the family capital. If only one parent has the right to manage the capital funds (for example, if the other parent loses parental rights or if there is a single parent), that parent has the right to manage the entire capital amount. This innovation not only strengthens the equality of parents, but also helps to minimize potential conflicts and disagreements in families regarding the intended use of funds.

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SEARCH PROTOCOL: WORDING OF REMARKS

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Abstract. *One of the most common and complex investigative actions aimed at achieving the goals of criminal proceedings is the search. However, no studies have been identified that comprehensively catalog the potential violations that may occur during the conduct of a search, including personal searches, searches of dwellings, and investigative actions conducted in exigent circumstances. Given the multiplicity of potential violations, this poses a challenge for attorneys in providing effective legal assistance, especially when drafting comments on the conduct and outcome of the investigative action and incorporating them into the protocol. To address the lack of comprehensive research on this topic, the authors analyzed existing legislation, investigative and judicial practice, and identified over 80 violations. These violations have been formulated as protocol notes, organized topically, and presented in a sequence that reflects the dynamics of search procedures. This approach aims to provide clarity and ease of use when drafting comments on the conduct and outcome of search actions.*

Keywords: *preliminary investigation, preliminary inquiry, inquest, investigative action, search, personal search, attorney, defense counsel, defense attorney, protocol of investigative action, search protocol, notes on the protocol.*

Although the grounds and procedure for conducting a search are comprehensively regulated by criminal procedural law, the complexity and multifaceted nature of this investigative action often result in violations that must not be overlooked by the attorney.

Pursuant to part 11 article 182 of the Code of Criminal Procedure of the Russian Federation, during the conduct of a search, the defense counsel, as well as the attorney of the person in whose premises the search is conducted, have the right to be present.

The general rule for any investigative action, including a search, is the preparation of a protocol (part 8 of article 164 of the Code of Criminal Procedure of the Russian Federation), which is drawn up during the investigative action or immediately following its conclusion.

According to the requirements for the attorney's activity contained in paragraph 10 of the Standard for the Exercise of Defense Counsel's Duties in Criminal Proceedings, the defense counsel must review the protocols of procedural actions conducted with their participation at all stages of the criminal process and, if necessary, submit remarks on them¹.

Thus, in the case of unlawful restriction of the rights and freedoms of the represented person (organization), the attorney is obliged to enter remarks on their supplementation and clarification into the protocol when justified by the defense strategy, which is determined on a case-by-case basis.

We have endeavored to summarize and systematize the violations occurring during the conduct of searches, personal searches, and searches of a residence, including the execution of these investigative actions in urgent cases, and to present them in the form of remarks for the protocol. Remarks may be made by the attorney orally (with entry in the protocol) or in writing, either within the same protocol or separately. For ease of use, the remarks include a reference to the violated legal provision.

I. Initial stage of the search proceedings

1.1. The official conducting or participating in the search did not state their position, rank, and full name.

1.2. The official conducting or participating in the search did not present official identification upon request.

1.3. The service ID presented by the person conducting or participating in the search is invalid, as it contains corrections, erasures, or has lost its practical significance due to expiration of its validity period, among other reasons.

II. Investigator's order or interrogator's order or a judicial decision authorizing the search, in the case of a search of the residence or the residential and/or office premises of an attorney

2.1. Before the search begins, an order authorizing its conduct or a judicial decision permitting it has not been presented — in the case of a search of

¹ The standard for attorneys conducting defense in criminal proceedings: adopted by the VIII All-Russian Congress of Attorneys on April 20, 2017. // Bulletin of the Federal Chamber of Attorneys of the Russian Federation. 2017. No. 2. Pp. 140–142.

a residence (part 4 of article 182 of the Code of Criminal Procedure of the Russian Federation)¹.

2.2. Before the commencement of the search, a warrant authorizing its conduct or a judicial decision permitting its execution must be presented — in the case of a search of a residence; however, permission to make a copy by technical means is denied for the portion that does not contain state or other legally protected secrets (part 2 of Article 24, part 2 of Article 45 of the Constitution of the Russian Federation, paragraph 3, subparagraph 2 of the Ruling of the Constitutional Court of the Russian Federation dated 24.10.2013 No. 1557-O, which establishes that the law does not prevent familiarization with the protocols of investigative actions and other documents that were presented or were required to be presented, and does not prohibit transcribing information in any volume or making copies at one's own expense, including by technical means)².

2.3. A search was conducted in the residential and/or office premises of an attorney used by him for the exercise of attorney activities without a court order (para. 3 of Art. 8 of the Federal Law “On Advocacy and the Bar in the Russian Federation”; Art. 450.1 of the Code of Criminal Procedure of the Russian Federation; Ruling of the Constitutional Court of the Russian Federation dated 08.11.2005 No. 439-O).

2.4. A search in the residential and/or office premises of an attorney was conducted on the basis of a court order; however, it does not specify that the search is being conducted in relation to the attorney. It is not specified or precisely indicated which specific objects are subject to seizure (their names, individual characteristics), their location, as well as the place where the search is conducted.

2.5. A search was conducted without a court order at a bank and other credit institutions concerning items and documents containing information about deposits and accounts (Article 26 of the Federal Law ‘On Banks and Banking Activities’; Ruling of the Constitutional Court of the Russian Federation dated 19.01.2005 No. 10-O).

¹ A search of a residence without prior judicial authorization is permissible only under urgent circumstances that do not allow delay, but with mandatory subsequent notification of the prosecutor and judge no later than three days from the commencement of the search (part 5 article 165 of the Code of Criminal Procedure of the Russian Federation).

² There are several positions of the Constitutional Court of the Russian Federation confirming that the right to access may be exercised in various forms, including a mixed mode — through personal reading, transcription, copying (photographing), or dictaphone recording. See: Resolution of 27.06.2000 No. 11-P; Ruling of 24.02.2005 No. 133-O; Ruling of 19.04.2007 No. 343-O-P; Resolution of 28.04.2023 No. 22-P, et al.

2.6. The Investigator's order or the investigator's ruling to conduct a search was issued in violation of legal requirements: by an unauthorized official; At the stage of the preliminary inquiry (before the initiation of criminal proceedings), etc.

2.7. The order to conduct the search indicates the necessity of carrying it out at an address different from the actual one.

2.8. The order to conduct the search does not specify the location within which it is to be carried out (for example, the office number located in a business center comprising multiple office premises is not indicated).

2.9. The decision to conduct a search in cases that do not tolerate delay was issued well in advance of the search (for example, several days or longer), indicating the absence of urgency and the real possibility of obtaining prior judicial authorization (part 5 article 165 of the Code of Criminal Procedure of the Russian Federation).

2.10. An urgent search was declared; however, the necessity for its conduct is not justified in the decision (part 4 article 7 of the Code of Criminal Procedure of the Russian Federation).

III. The search was not conducted by the authorized person, who is assigned or authorized to conduct it

3.1. The search is conducted by an inquirer or investigator who is not handling the proceedings of the given criminal case, is not part of the group of inquirers or investigators investigating it, and does not have a written assignment.

3.2. The search is conducted by an operative officer:

– who does not have a written assignment from the inquirer or investigator authorizing its conduct;

– who has a written assignment from the inquirer or investigator that has not been presented for review.

An operative officer acting pursuant to an assignment to conduct a search is obliged to present, for review, documents confirming the legality of his actions. Otherwise, there are no grounds to believe that his demands are lawful and therefore obligatory to comply with;

– holding a written order from the investigator or inquiry officer, presented for review by reading, but denied the making of copies using technical means insofar as the document(s) do not contain state or other legally protected secrets.

IV. Denial of access to the person in whose premises the search is being conducted, or adult members of his family or an attorney (defense counsel) representing his interests

4.1. The person in whose premises the search was conducted was prohibited from being present at the place of the search (part 11 article 182 of the Code of

Criminal Procedure of the Russian Federation; Ruling of the Constitutional Court of the Russian Federation dated 14.01.2020 No. 4-O).

4.2. Not admitted to participate after the beginning of the search:

– an attorney representing the interests of the person in whose residence the search is conducted;

– an attorney representing the interests of the owner of the non-residential premises where the search is conducted;

– an attorney representing the interests of the legal entity owning the non-residential premises (part 11 article 182 of the Code of Criminal Procedure of the Russian Federation; Ruling of the Constitutional Court of the Russian Federation dated 14.01.2020 No. 4-O).

4.3. The petition for admission of an attorney (defense counsel) to participate in the search was not considered or was arbitrarily rejected (Ruling of the Constitutional Court of the Russian Federation dated 17.07.2014 No. 1788-O).

4.4. The lawful representative was not admitted:

– of a minor or a person declared legally incapable or with limited legal capacity;

– of a person placed in a medical institution providing psychiatric care in in-patient conditions;

– the person against whom proceedings for the application of compulsory medical measures are being carried out.

V. Failure to explain rights, duties, and responsibilities, as well as failure to ensure the possibility to exercise the rights of the person in respect of whom the search is being conducted

5.1. Before the commencement of the search, the rights, duties, responsibilities, and the procedure for conducting the search were not explained (part 1 article 11 and part 5 article 164 of the Code of Criminal Procedure of the Russian Federation).

5.2. Before the commencement of the search, the right to participate in the court's review of the legality of the search or personal search, including one conducted in an urgent case, as well as the right to appeal the court decision made following such review, were not explained (part 5 article 164 and part 5 article 165 of the Code of Criminal Procedure of the Russian Federation, paragraph 17 of the Resolution of the Plenum of the Supreme Court of the Russian Federation dated 01.06.2017 No. 19 "On the practice of courts' consideration of motions concerning investigative actions involving restrictions on citizens' constitutional rights (article 165 of the Code of Criminal Procedure of the Russian Federation)")¹.

¹ As repeatedly noted by the Constitutional Court of the Russian Federation, the investigator, by virtue of the requirements Part 1 article 11 of the Code of Criminal

5.3. Before the commencement of the search, no offer was made to voluntarily surrender the items, documents, or valuables subject to seizure that are relevant to the criminal case (part 5 article 198 of the Code of Criminal Procedure of the Russian Federation).

5.4. The victim, witness, specialist, expert, or interpreter who participated in the search was not warned about the liability provided under articles 307 and 308 of the Criminal Code of the Russian Federation (part 5 article 164 of the Code of Criminal Procedure of the Russian Federation).

5.5. Before the search began, the person directing it did not inform the participants of the investigative action about the use and specific features of the technical means applied (part 6 article 164 of the Code of Criminal Procedure of the Russian Federation).

5.6. The presence of the person whose premises are being searched, or of adult members of their family, has not been ensured (Part 11, Article 182 of the Criminal Procedure Code).

5.7. The right to invite an attorney has not been ensured (Article 48 of the Constitution of the Russian Federation; paragraph 2 of the Ruling of the Constitutional Court of the Russian Federation dated 14.01.2020 No. 4-O, according to which *'persons whose rights are affected (restricted) by investigative actions and procedural decisions cannot be deprived of the right to legal assistance by an attorney'*).

5.8. Refusal to postpone the conduct of the search briefly until the arrival of the attorney (defense counsel).

VI. Participation of witnesses

6.1. During the search, in violation of the requirement for the involvement of at least two witnesses, only one witness participated (part 1 article 170 of the Code of Criminal Procedure of the Russian Federation).

6.2. The search was conducted without the participation of witnesses and without the use of technical means to record its progress and results (part 1.1 article 170 of the Code of Criminal Procedure of the Russian Federation).

6.3. Witnesses who could not act as such were involved:

- minors;
- participants in criminal proceedings, their close and other relatives;
- employees of executive authorities vested, in accordance with federal law, with powers to conduct operational-search activities and/or preliminary investigations (part 2 article 60 of the Code of Criminal Procedure of the Russian Federation);

Procedure of the Russian Federation obliges, during the conduct of a search, to inform the interested parties of their rights, including the right to file a motion to participate in the court session reviewing the legality of the search, to ensure the possibility of exercising these rights, and to specify the court where the court session will take place (rulings dated 21.05.2015 № 1051-O, 27.06.2017 № 1248-O, etc.).

– person(s) directly or indirectly interested in the outcome of the criminal case (part 1 article 60 of the Code of Criminal Procedure of the Russian Federation, Ruling of the Constitutional Court of the Russian Federation dated 27.12.2022 No. 3481-O).

6.4. The witness was in a state of alcoholic, narcotic, or other toxic intoxication, depriving him of the ability to objectively perceive the essence of the search procedure.

6.5. The statement on involving witnesses who could not act as such, submitted before the start of the search, was left without consideration or resolution by the person conducting the search.

6.6. The witnesses were not informed of the purpose of the search, nor their rights and responsibilities. (part 4, article 170 of the Code of Criminal Procedure of the Russian Federation).

6.7. The witnesses were absent from each searched room and/or from the immediate discovery and seizure of objects relevant to the criminal case, and therefore could not certify the course and results of the search (part 1, article 170 of the Code of Criminal Procedure of the Russian Federation).

6.8. The witness «...» did not have an identity document; accordingly, his identity could not be established (Ruling of the Constitutional Court of the Russian Federation dated 16.07.2015 No. 1562-O).

6.9. The witness «...» carried out the search and/or inspection of objects. The aforementioned indicates his vested interest (part 1 article 60 of the Code of Criminal Procedure of the Russian Federation).

6.10. The person participating in the search moved freely throughout the premises or other location where the search was conducted, and his actions were not supervised by the person directing the search.

6.11. An unidentified person participated in the search, whose details were not recorded in the protocol (paragraph 3 part 3 article 166 of the Code of Criminal Procedure of the Russian Federation).

VII. Seizure of items, documents, or valuables.

7.1. The seized objects are unrelated to the investigated criminal case and are not subject to seizure on other grounds (part 1 article 182 of the Code of Criminal Procedure of the Russian Federation).

7.2. The seized objects, if necessary, were not packaged and/or sealed at the location of the search (part 10 article 182 of the Code of Criminal Procedure of the Russian Federation).

7.3. The seized items are packed and/or sealed at the scene of the search; however, they are not endorsed with the signatures of the participants of the search (part 10, article 182 of the Code of Criminal Procedure of the Russian Federation).

7.4. The seized items are packed in a manner that does not prevent unauthorized access to the contents of the packaging.

7.5. The seized items are not presented to the attesting witnesses and/or other participants of the search (part 10, article 182 of the Code of Criminal Procedure of the Russian Federation).

VIII. Seizure/copying of electronic information carriers

8.1. The seized electronic information carriers (computer, laptop, memory card, etc.) are neither packed nor sealed, allowing for additional data to be added and the contained information to be distorted (part 10, article 182 of the Code of Criminal Procedure of the Russian Federation).

8.2. Without a judicial decision, the database of counterparties, clients, and others containing information protected by law was copied or seized (part 3 article 183 of the Code of Criminal Procedure of the Russian Federation; Ruling of the Constitutional Court of the Russian Federation dated 19.01.2005 No. 10-O; Ruling of the Constitutional Court of the Russian Federation dated 02.03.2006 No. 54-O).

8.3. Electronic information carriers were seized without the involvement of a specialist (computer, laptop, memory card, etc.) (part 2 article 164.1 of the Code of Criminal Procedure of the Russian Federation).

8.4. Electronic information carriers were seized in criminal proceedings specified in part 4.1 article 164 of the Code of Criminal Procedure of the Russian Federation (part 1 article 164.1 of the Code of Criminal Procedure of the Russian Federation).

8.5. The copying of information from the seized electronic information carriers was carried out in the absence of witnesses (part 2 article 164.1 of the Code of Criminal Procedure of the Russian Federation).

8.6. The petition to copy the information contained on the electronic carriers was neither examined nor granted immediately after its submission (article 121 and part 2 article 164.1 of the Code of Criminal Procedure of the Russian Federation).

8.7. The petition to copy the information contained on the electronic carriers was denied in the absence of circumstances specified in point 3 part 1 article 164.1 of the Code of Criminal Procedure of the Russian Federation (information that may be used to commit new crimes, or copying which, according to the specialist's statement, could result in its loss or alteration, etc.) (part 2 article 164.1 of the Code of Criminal Procedure of the Russian Federation).

IX. A personal search of a person located in the premises or another location, where the search is being conducted.

9.1. The personal search was conducted without sufficient grounds to believe that the person was concealing items or documents that may be relevant to the criminal case.

9.2. The investigator's or interrogator's order to conduct the personal search does not contain a justification of urgency (part 4 article 7, part 5 article 165, part 1 article 182, part 1 article 184 of the Code of Criminal Procedure of the Russian Federation).

9.3. The personal search was conducted by a person of the opposite sex to the individual being searched and/or in the presence of witnesses and/or a specialist of the opposite sex, if they participated in the search (part 3 article 184 of the Code of Criminal Procedure of the Russian Federation).

9.4. The personal search was conducted by an official of the inquiry body without a written authorization for its execution (Part 4, Article 157 of the Code of Criminal Procedure of the Russian Federation).

X. Other violations committed during the conduct of a search

10.1. The person conducting the search, an operative officer, or another participant in the search applied violence, threats, and/or other unlawful measures against '...' or created a danger to the life and health of the persons participating in the search (Part 2, Article 21 of the Constitution of the Russian Federation; Part 2, Article 9, Part 4, Article 164 of the Code of Criminal Procedure of the Russian Federation).

10.2. The person conducting the search, an operative officer, or another participant in the search damaged the property of the person being searched without due necessity, thereby causing material damage in the amount of «...».

10.3. The apartment door was forced open using special tools; however, this was unnecessary, as «...» was present in the apartment at that time, and no demand for voluntary opening was recorded in the protocol. (Appellate Ruling of the Moscow City Court dated 16.02.2018 in case No. 33–7243/2018).

10.4. No measures were taken to prevent the disclosure of circumstances concerning the private life of the individual or information constituting personal or family secrets, as well as circumstances of the private life of other persons, identified during the search (part 1 article 23 of the Constitution of the Russian Federation, part 7 article 182 of the Code of Criminal Procedure of the Russian Federation).

10.5. The search was conducted fully or partially during nighttime, i.e., between 22:00 and 06:00 (part 3 article 164 of the Code of Criminal Procedure of the Russian Federation); however, its urgency was not justified in the ruling.

XI. Search protocol

11.1. The search protocol was drafted in violation of the requirements of Articles 166 and 167 of the Code of Criminal Procedure of the Russian Federation, which regulate the general rules it must comply with.

In particular, the following are not specified:

– the place and date of the search, as well as the exact time of its commencement and conclusion, down to the minute;

- the position, surname, and initials of the person who drafted the protocol;
 - the surname, first name, and patronymic of each person participating in the search, and, when necessary, their address and other personal details, etc.
- 11.2. With respect to the seized items, the protocol does not specify:
- the place and circumstances under which they were found, their condition, and how they were stored;
 - whether they were voluntarily handed over or forcibly seized (Part 13 of Article 182 of the Code of Criminal Procedure of the Russian Federation).
- 11.3. The exact moment of discovery and/or seizure of the object was not recorded by witnesses or technical recording devices¹.
- 11.4. Not all seized objects were included in the search protocol.
- 11.5. Not all seized objects were listed with precise indication of their quantity, measurement, weight, individual characteristics, and (if possible) value (Part 13 of Article 182 of the Code of Criminal Procedure of the Russian Federation).
- 11.6. The seized funds are not listed with precise indication of their quantity, denomination, and individual characteristics (part 13 of Article 182 of the Code of Criminal Procedure of the Russian Federation).
- 11.7. The person whose premises were searched, or an adult member of their family, was not provided with a copy of the search protocol (part 15 of Article 182 of the Code of Criminal Procedure of the Russian Federation).
- 11.8. A copy of the search protocol was not provided to the representative of the organization in whose premises the search was conducted (part 15 of Article 182 of the Code of Criminal Procedure of the Russian Federation).
- 11.9. An incomplete copy of the search protocol was provided (one or more pages were missing, and/or signatures of all participants of the search and others were absent).

References

1. The standard for attorneys conducting defense in criminal proceedings: adopted by the VIII All-Russian Congress of Attorneys on April 20, 2017. // Bulletin of the Federal Chamber of Attorneys of the Russian Federation. 2017. No. 2. Pp. 140–142.

¹ If the witnesses saw only the moment of seizure of the searched object but did not witness its discovery, which was also not documented by technical means, it is reasonable to uphold the position that the object was not previously present at the place of seizure and may have appeared at a moment that was not witnessed. A similar approach is also applicable when the witnesses observed the moment of the item's discovery but did not witness the moment of its seizure.

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